

*Climate and cultural based design and market valuable
technology solutions for Plus Energy Houses*

Climate and cultural differences in energy use in domestic buildings

Deliverable D2.1

Dissemination Level: Public
Lead Partner: RMIT
Due date: 31 May 2020
Type of deliverable: Report
Status: Final version

Published in the framework of:

Cultural-E - Climate and cultural based design and market valuable technology solutions for Plus Energy Houses

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 870072

Authors:

Ralph Horne, Deputy Pro Vice Chancellor, Research & Innovation. College of Design and Social Context, RMIT University, Australia

Iván Luque Segura, Research Fellow, RMIT Europe

Contributors:

Lorenza Pistore, University Ca' Foscari of Venice

Wilmer Pasut, University Ca' Foscari of Venice

Hanne Liland Bottolfsen, SINTEF

Hugo Viot, Nobatek/INEF4

Simone Idler, Steinbeis - Innovationszentrum EGS (SIZ EGS)

Sandra Dei Svaldi, ICIE - Istituto Cooperativo per l'Innovazione

Nicola Silingardi, ICIE - Istituto Cooperativo per l'Innovazione

Revision and history chart:

Version	Date	Editors	Comment
0.1	15.05.2020	Ralph Horne, Iván Luque	Draft for revision
0.2	29.05.2020	Ralph Horne, Iván Luque	Revised draft

Disclaimer:

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 870072.

The content of this report does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed therein lies entirely with the author(s).

Contents

Executive summary	10
1 Introduction.....	17
2 Social practice and energy studies research	24
2.1 Social and cultural dimensions of energy demand.	24
2.1.1 Building Management System	25
2.1.2 Building Comfort systems	27
2.1.3 Technology solutions for building flexibility	29
2.2 Understanding the drivers of everyday energy practices.....	32
2.2.1 Individual householder factors	33
2.2.2 Household characteristics.....	34
2.2.3 Shared norms, values, expectations and rules	34
2.2.4 Building characteristics and operability	35
3 Climate Areas	36
3.1 Integrating Climatic Conditions within the Building Design	36
3.2 Climate and Culture – Interacting factors	37
4 Energy culture: cultural and social determinants of domestic energy demand	40
4.1 Energy Cultures Framework (ECF)	41
4.2 Implications of cultural and social drivers	43
4.3 Household composition and Time Geography of energy demand.....	44
5 Concept for the Atlas	48
6 Data sets for building the 2CAP Energy Atlas	52
7 Understanding culture and climate variables on energy demand at households' level	58
7.1 Sub-arctic climate.....	58
7.1.1 Energy consumption in households	58
7.1.2 Socio-economic factors.....	64
7.1.3 Climatic factors	64
7.1.4 Literature review	66
7.1.5 Considerations.....	73
7.2 Oceanic climate.....	74
7.2.1 Energy consumption in households	74

7.2.2	Socio economic factors.....	89
7.2.3	Climatic factors	93
7.2.4	Literature review	96
7.2.5	Considerations.....	103
7.3	Continental climate.....	104
7.3.1	Energy consumption in households	104
7.3.2	Socio-economic factors.....	112
7.3.3	Climatic factors	116
7.3.4	Literature review	119
7.3.5	Considerations.....	121
7.4	Mediterranean climate	121
7.4.1	Energy consumption in households	121
7.4.2	Socio-economic factors.....	130
7.4.3	Climatic factors	137
7.4.4	Literature review	144
7.4.5	Considerations.....	154
8	Designing the 2CAP Energy Atlas. Functionalities & Insights.....	155
8.1	Description of envisioned features and functionalities.....	155
8.2	Defining the expected outcomes from the 2CAP Energy Atlas for PEB design process.....	157
9	Overview of the process & Conclusions	158
	References	160

List of figures

FIGURE 1 - AVERAGE 24-HOUR ELECTRICITY USE PROFILE FOR SAMPLE OF 250 OWNER OCCUPIED HOMES. 2010-11 (DATA SOURCE DECC 2013: ANDERSON 2016C:3)..... 31

FIGURE 2 - KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLIMATE CLASSIFICATION IN EUROPE 39

FIGURE 3 - ENERGY CULTURES FRAMEWORK (2013)..... 41

FIGURE 4 - THE AGGREGATE PRACTICE PATTERN (BASED ON THE PRACTICES SEQUENCES OF ALL INDIVIDUALS) IN THE POPULATION (N=463) DURING A WEEKDAY DAY (PALM AND ELLEGÅRD 2011). 47

FIGURE 5 – FIGURATIVE COMPOSITION OF CONCEPT FOR THE ATLAS. SOURCES: (PVSITE PROJECT 2016; CASS AND SHOVE 2017; GE2O PROJECT 2013)..... 48

FIGURE 6 - EU BUILDING STOCK OBSERVATORY 52

FIGURE 7 - FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY END USE. BREAKDOWN OF FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION FOR IEA MEMBERS IN 2017 54

FIGURE 8 - EUROSTAT - ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND USE BY HOUSEHOLDS 2017 54

FIGURE 9 - COUNTRY PROFILES WITHIN ODYSSEE-MURE PROJECT 56

FIGURE 10 - OBSERVED TREND IN HEATING AND COOLING DEGREE DAYS (1981-2017) 57

FIGURE 11 - MONITORED VS. CALCULATED ENERGY USE AT SKARPNES, ZEB, PICTURE FROM PRESENTATION BY STEINAR GRYNNING, ÅSE L. SØRENSEN, JUDITH THOMSEN, LARS GULLBREKKEN..... 59

FIGURE 12 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN HOUSEHOLDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS, 2012, SSB .. 60

FIGURE 13 - TYPE OF END-USE ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN HOUSEHOLDS, NVE 61

FIGURE 14 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND TYPE OF ENERGY SOURCE IN HOUSEHOLDS, HISTORICAL AND PREDICTED, NVE 61

FIGURE 15 - SHARE OF FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY TYPE OF END-USE, EUROSTAT 62

FIGURE 16 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF RESIDENTIAL PER M2 AND YEAR, ODYSSEE-MURE.... 63

FIGURE 17 – MAIN DRIVERS OF THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION VARIATION IN HOUSEHOLDS, ODYSSEE-MURE..... 63

FIGURE 18 - TOOL INCLUDED IN THE PVGIS PLATFORM (LAST UPDATE 15/10/2019)..... 65

FIGURE 19: EXAMPLE OF A DETAILED SHEET OF CAVEZERO PROJECT 74

FIGURE 20 - INFORMATION AVAILABLE BY PROJECTS POWERHOUSEEUROPE 75

FIGURE 21 - COMEPOS WEB-PAGE AND LOCATION OF DEMO HOUSES..... 76

FIGURE 22 - AZEB WEB-PAGE AND DEMO HOUSES 77

FIGURE 23 - SEARCH WEB-PAGE OBSERVATORY BBC 79

FIGURE 24 - AVAILABLE INFORMATION FOR EACH PROJECT - OBSERVATORY BBC 80

FIGURE 25 - ZEBRA MONITORING TOOL 81

FIGURE 26 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF SPACE HEATING PER M2 82

FIGURE 27 - MAIN DRIVERS OF THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION VARIATION IN HOUSEHOLDS..... 82

FIGURE 28 - FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY SECTOR 83

FIGURE 29 - EUROSTAT DATA FOR HOUSEHOLD ENERGY CONSUMPTION 83

FIGURE 30 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION – RESIDENTIAL 84

FIGURE 31 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION DISTRIBUTION IN %..... 84

FIGURE 32 - EVOLUTION OF ENERGY USES SINCE 2000 (BASE 100) 85

<i>FIGURE 33: EVOLUTION OF ENERGY USES SINCE 1990 (BASE 100)</i>	85
<i>FIGURE 34 - TYPICAL ELECTRICAL APPLIANCES USE</i>	86
<i>FIGURE 35: RESIDENTIAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION (ALL END-USES) AND TREND IN ON SITE RE PRODUCTION AS SHARE OF TOTAL CONSUMPTION ON BUILDINGS</i>	87
<i>FIGURE 36: ON-SITE RENEWABLE ENERGY GENERATION</i>	87
<i>FIGURE 37: AVERAGE NUMBER OF APPLIANCES</i>	88
<i>FIGURE 38: FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN HOUSEHOLD BY TYPE OF FUEL (kTEP)</i>	88
<i>FIGURE 39 - FIGURE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA AVAILABLE IN EUROSTAT FOR OCEANIC CLIMATE</i>	89
<i>FIGURE 40 - SCREENSHOT OF THE TOOL</i>	90
<i>FIGURE 41 - SCREENSHOT OF REGIOVIZ FRANCE</i>	91
<i>FIGURE 42 - EXAMPLE OF AVAILABLE DATA IN THE OBSERVATORY OF TERRITORIES (FRANCE)</i>	92
<i>FIGURE 43 – SCREENSHOT DEGREE DAY - HEATING AND COOLING (FRANCE)</i>	94
<i>FIGURE 44 - TOOL INCLUDED IN THE SAME PLATFORM</i>	95
<i>FIGURE 45 - SCREENSHOT METEOFRANCE</i>	95
<i>FIGURE 46 - SCREENSHOTS SOLARGIS</i>	96
<i>FIGURE 47 - INDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL CLASSES IN THE REVIEWED STANDARDS CONCERNING OCEANIC CLIMATE</i>	97
<i>FIGURE 48 - OPERATIVE TEMPERATURE IN THE REVIEWED STANDARDS CONCERNING OCEANIC CLIMATE</i>	97
<i>FIGURE 49 - RELATION AMONG INDOOR OPERATIVE TEMPERATURE IN REGARD TO OUTDOOR MEAN RUNNING TEMPERATURE IN THE REVIEWED STANDARDS CONCERNING OCEANIC CLIMATE.</i>	98
<i>FIGURE 50 - RELATION BETWEEN VENTILATION RATE AND FLOOR AREA</i>	98
<i>FIGURE 51 - THE EFFECTS OF HOUSEHOLD AND BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS ON THE ANNUAL DOMESTIC ENERGY OF FRANCE.</i>	99
<i>FIGURE 52 - FOUR DIMENSIONS OF INFLUENCING FACTORS TO ENERGY-SAVING BEHAVIOUR</i>	100
<i>FIGURE 53 -MAPS OF THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE ACCORDING TO LOCAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIATIONS</i>	101
<i>FIGURE 54 - ENERGY CULTURE FRAMEWORK</i>	102
<i>FIGURE 55 - EFFECTS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS ON ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN DOMESTIC BUILDINGS.</i>	103
<i>FIGURE 56 - AKTIV STADTHAUS FRANKFURT, GERMANY, SOURCE: HEGGER HEGGER SCHLEIFF (HHS) PLANER + ARCHITEKTEN AG</i>	104
<i>FIGURE 57 - AKTIV-STADTHAUS: DISTRIBUTION OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF A PEH IN % AND AKTIV-STADTHAUS: DISTRIBUTION OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF A PEH IN kWh/(m²*a) ...</i>	105
<i>FIGURE 58 - WOULD YOU RECOMMEND A HIGHLY EFFICIENT HOME TO YOUR FAMILY AND FRIENDS? (PEB)</i>	106
<i>FIGURE 59 - INTERIOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY (IEQ) I</i>	106
<i>FIGURE 60 - INTERIOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY (IEQ) II</i>	107

FIGURE 61 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF GERMAN HOUSEHOLDS 2017 IN %, UMWELTBUNDESAMT..... 108

FIGURE 62 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF GERMAN HOUSEHOLDS 2017 IN KWH/M² LIVING AREA, OWN CALCULATIONS BASED ON UMWELTBUNDESAMT AND DESTATIS..... 108

FIGURE 63 - ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF HOUSEHOLDS IN GERMANY, DESTATIS 2019 109

FIGURE 64 - STROMSPIEGEL 2019 110

FIGURE 65 - GERMAN NUTS 2 111

FIGURE 66 - CLASSIFICATION OF BUILDING TYPOLOGY IN GERMANY, IWU 2011 112

FIGURE 67 - USED ENERGY SOURCES FOR HEATING IN GERMANY, BDEW 2019 114

FIGURE 68 SHARE OF ENERGY SOURCE FOR HEATING DEPENDING ON REGIONS, BDEW 2019 114

FIGURE 69 - FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF GERMAN HOUSEHOLDS, UMWELTBUNDESAMT 115

FIGURE 70 - PRICE FOR GAS AND ELECTRICITY OF HOUSEHOLDS (2018)..... 116

FIGURE 71 - PHOTOVOLTAIC GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (PVGIS)..... 117

FIGURE 72 - PVGIS: PV PERFORMANCE TOOL, STEP 1: CHOOSE LOCATION 118

FIGURE 73 - PVGIS: PV PERFORMANCE TOOL, STEP 2: INPUT TYPE OF PV, SLOPE AND AZIMUTH..... 118

FIGURE 74 - PVGIS: PV PERFORMANCE TOOL, STEP 3 RESULTS..... 119

FIGURE 75 - KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLIMATE CLASSIFICATION IN EUROPE 121

FIGURE 76 ODDYSSEE-MURE NATIONAL REPORTS EXAMPLES..... 122

FIGURE 77. LEVEL AND TREND INDICATORS FOR MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES..... 123

FIGURE 78. SHARE (%) OF FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN THE RESIDENTIAL SECTOR IN MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES BY TYPE OF END-USE (EUROSTAT 2017) 124

FIGURE 79. ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF HOUSEHOLDS BY ENERGY SOURCE..... 124

FIGURE 80. SHARES OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY ENERGY SOURCE IN HOUSEHOLDS..... 125

FIGURE 81. ENERGY UNIT CONSUMPTION OF ELECTRICAL APPLIANCE IN HOUSEHOLDS (2000=100)..... 125

FIGURE 82. MAIN DRIVERS OF THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION VARIATION IN HOUSEHOLDS..... 125

FIGURE 83: EXAMPLE OF A DETAILED SHEET CAVEZERO PROJECT (ITALY)..... 126

FIGURE 84. PERCENTAGE OF HIGH-PERFORMANCE BUILDINGS (NZEB) OUT OF THE TOTAL BUILDING BY REGION..... 127

FIGURE 85 - ITA NZEB PROJECT 128

FIGURE 86 - EU PROJECT WEBSITES 129

FIGURE 87 – ODYSSEE - MURE - TRENDS DIAGRAMMES (ITALY) 129

FIGURE 88 - STATIST DATA AVAILABLE AT EUROSTAT. 130

FIGURE 89. POPULATION BY AGE, SEX AND TYPE OF PROJECTION IN EU MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES..... 131

FIGURE 90. STATIST DATA AVAILABLE AT EUROSTAT. MEDIAN AGE OF POPULATION. CENSUS 2011 131

FIGURE 91. GDP PER INHABITANT. EUROSTAT REGIONAL YEARBOOK 2019 AND INCOME PER INHABITANT. EUROSTAT REGIONAL YEARBOOK 2019 132

FIGURE 92. DEGREE OF URBANIZATION. EUROSTAT REGIONAL YEARBOOK 2019 132

FIGURE 93 COMPOSITION OF THE ELECTRICITY BILL IN ITALY..... 133

FIGURE 94 - ANNUAL ELECTRICITY ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN ITALY 2000-20017..... 134

FIGURE 95 ANNUAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION – GAS PER REGION (ITALY) 135

FIGURE 96. POPULATIONS AND HOUSING CENSUS. DATA ON FAMILIES AND HOUSEHOLDS ... 135

FIGURE 97. PRIVATE HOUSEHOLDS BY TYPE, TENURE STATUS AND NUTS 2 REGION: TOTAL, OWNER..... 136

FIGURE 98. POPULATIONS AND HOUSING CENSUS. DATA ON POPULATION BY HOUSING ARRANGEMENTS. AGE OF PEOPLE 136

FIGURE 99. CHARACTERISTICS OF CLIMATIC ZONES 137

FIGURE 100. “SIZE” OF CLIMATIC ZONES. ORIGINAL PROCESSING ON DATA ENEA-ISTAT .. 137

FIGURE 101. GLOBAL SOLAR RADIATION (MIN/AVG/MAX) ON THE GROUND INTEGRATED ANNUALLY AND AGGREGATED ON A REGIONAL BASIS. 2005-2015. GRAPHIC ELABORATIONS AND DATA SOURCE: RSE (SOURCE: RDS 16002400)..... 138

FIGURE 102. GLOBAL SOLAR RADIATION ON THE GROUND INTEGRATED ANNUALLY AND AGGREGATED ON A MUNICIPAL BASIS. AVG 2005-2015 AND 2015. GRAPHIC ELABORATIONS AND DATA SOURCE: RSE (SOURCE: Rds 16002400)..... 138

FIGURE 103. RSE SOLAR ATLAS, FORECAST AND HISTORICAL DATA. SOURCE: [HTTP://SUNRISE.RSE-WEB.IT/](http://sunrise.rse-web.it/)..... 139

FIGURE 104. RSE SOLAR ATLAS, FORECAST AND HISTORICAL DATA. NEW FEATURES..... 140

FIGURE 105 - AVERAGE EXTERNAL TEMPERATURE AND RAINFALL YEARS 1961-2015 141

FIGURE 106 - MAXIMUM AVERAGE ANNUAL TEMPERATURES YEARS 1961-2015 AND ANOMALIES FOR THE MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM TEMPERATURES YEARS 1971-2000 142

FIGURE 107 - SCENARIOS FOR INCREASING THE MINIMUM TEMPERATURES IN WINTER AND MAXIMUM TEMPERATURES IN SUMMER..... 143

FIGURE 108 - SEASONAL MAX. AND MIN. TEMPERATURE..... 143

FIGURE 109 - EXTREME CLIMATE EPISODES (ICE AND HEAT WAVES) IN A MAJOR REGIONAL CITY 144

FIGURE 110 – THE SIMULATED THERMAL ZONES 144

FIGURE 111 – THE SIMULATED HEATING SET-POINT PREFERENCES. 145

FIGURE 112– COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASURED VALUES AND SIMULATED VALUES: (A) ENERGY DEMAND FOR HEATING AND COOLING NEEDS, (B) ENERGY GENERATION FROM PV SYSTEM.. 146

FIGURE 113 – COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASURED VALUES AND SIMULATED VALUES: (A) AIR TEMPERATURE INSIDE THE LIVING ROOM, (B) RELATIVE HUMIDITY INSIDE THE LIVING ROOM.. 147

FIGURE 114 – MONTHLY ENERGY DEMAND AND GENERATION FROM PV SYSTEM FOR CITIES CONSIDERED ACROSS SOUTH EUROPE. 148

FIGURE 115 – SUGGESTION FOR NZEB PERFORMANCE THRESHOLD IN SOUTHERN EUROPE’S MEMBER STATES. 149

FIGURE 116 – PERCENTAGE OF OCCUPANT BEHAVIOURS FOR THERMAL DISCOMFORT IN WINTER IN FUNCTION OF THE CONSTRUCTION YEAR. 150

FIGURE 117 – PERCENTAGE OF OCCUPANT BEHAVIOURS FOR THERMAL DISCOMFORT IN SUMMER IN FUNCTION OF THE CONSTRUCTION YEAR. 150

FIGURE 118 – OCCUPANCY PROFILES FOR TWO OCCUPANCY SCENARIOS FOR AN AVERAGE WEEKDAY 151

FIGURE 119 – INFLUENCE OF SEPARATED ENERGY USES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION UPON VARIATION OF FAMILY SIZE, OCCUPANTS’ BEHAVIOUR, AND EQUIPMENT TYPOLOGY 152

FIGURE 120 – INFLUENCE OF SEPARATED ENERGY USES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION UPON VARIATION OF FAMILY SIZE, OCCUPANTS’ BEHAVIOUR, AND EQUIPMENT TYPOLOGY 152

FIGURE 121 – INFLUENCE OF SEPARATED ENERGY USES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION UPON VARIATION OF FAMILY SIZE, OCCUPANTS’ BEHAVIOUR, AND EQUIPMENT TYPOLOGY \ 153

FIGURE 122 - CERPLAN PROJECT WEBAPP SCREENSHOT 155

List of Tables

TABLE 1 - ENERGY CULTURES FRAMEWORK (ECF). MODIFIED VERSION - SOURCE: ENERGISE 12

TABLE 2 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO MATERIAL CONDITIONS 13

TABLE 3 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO ATTITUDES, PERCEPTIONS AND SOCIAL NORMS 13

TABLE 4 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO EVERYDAY PRACTICES 14

TABLE 5 - 2CAP ENERGY ATLAS - DATA VARIABLES CATEGORISED BY SOCIO-CULTURAL DRIVERS WITHIN THE ECF 51

TABLE 6 - SHARE OF FUELS IN THE FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN THE RESIDENTIAL SECTOR, 2017, NORWAY, EUROSTAT 62

TABLE 7 - POPULATION DENSITY - NORWAY (PERSON PER KM2) 64

TABLE 8 - GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT GERMANY, DESTATIS 82111-0001 112

TABLE 9 - DISPOSABLE INCOME PRIVATE HOUSEHOLDS GERMANY, DESTATIS 82411-0001113

Executive summary

In the CULTURAL-E project, **cultural and climatic considerations will be incorporated into the Plus Energy Building (PEB) designs** which are being implemented as part of the residential buildings' demo projects located in four European climatic areas. As a means of contributing to defining a new approach, which enhances the buildings' pre and post occupancy developments, the current deliverable, D.2.1 'Climate and cultural differences in energy use in domestic buildings', aims at upgrading PEB's energy performance predictions guided by users' everyday practices.

Culture includes a range of demographic, social and linguistic factors, and extends from traditions, habits and conventions to the role of knowledge, rules and expectations. Energy cultures broadly relate to those aspects of culture that are invoked by, and affect, energy consumption and related energy services. Factors such as caring for other family members, health and wellbeing, as well as expectations and conventions of comfort are known determinants of variations in energy use.

This literature review on **cultural and climatic related aspects of domestic energy demand, is the basis for an understanding of household practices** in the context of the development of user-involved smart energy technologies. It addresses the gap between building design expectations and the reality of household energy performance. This gap exists both as a result of particular understandings of energy demand and ways in which energy efficiency is viewed as a technical activity. Energy is often considered to be a transacted product much like a movie, where a conscious decision is made to consume it, and there are various means as to how this might occur. Energy efficiency then comes to be about providing information to inform this choice. In reality, many other social, economic, and cultural factors are in play, beyond individual choice. Comfort, for example, is not simply a personal choice, for example, it is also a matter of convention, looking after others' presumed comfort needs, or maintaining standards of comfort that are socially rather than individually maintained. Hence, energy demand is shaped by social and cultural factors. Moreover, comfort is also dependent upon health, body mechanics, clothing styles and availability, knowledge of how comfort is maintained, and rules, often within social groups, about what is acceptable, etc. Henceforth, frames such as **social practices are adopted to** help explain and accommodate these broader parameters. More importantly, from the perspective of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs), and the associated adoption of user-focused smart technologies, these factors, as well as the temporal variations in energy demand, and the spatial variations across climate zones and cultures, are important in considering **the wider uptake of PEBs**.

In the following pages, the findings and outputs of the research are summarised, they could be grouped in these two core actions: (i) Literature review and meta-analysis, (ii) Defining the vision of the Atlas and data searching

1. Literature review and meta-analysis

The first five chapters of the report deliverable 2.1 ('this report') focus on a comprehensive meta-analysis of social sciences literature review, aiming at understanding how cultural and climatic factors may impact PEBs design. They articulate how energy demand is configured by the timing and location of a range of interconnected social practices and the 'energy intensity' of these performing practices.

Moreover, when we come to reflect about the design of the building management system and how the interface might fare in responding to and informing users' energy practices, we find that households adopting smart home technologies, tend to receive configured indoor settings that increase energy consumption, thus subverting any attempts at sustainable lifestyle goals that occupants may intend to achieve. Aiming to disrupt this 'solutionism' raised by home technologies, **the user interface will need to provide understandable information to give to the user the ability and the tailored details needed to change parameters in an informed way** and will put in place strategies to reduce energy consumption and improve indoor conditions.

Thermal comfort standards on which the technology design is formed are based on very specific and stable indoor climate conditions. Rather, buildings should give occupants the chance to adjust the conditions to suit themselves, within ecological parameters. Discomfort is increased if control is not provided. The indoor comfort strategies, by which occupants' ventilation practices are shaped during the design, construction and handover of PEBs, may need to integrate practice theory concepts in order to ensure that new homes can enable, and perhaps even encourage, people to live comfortably yet with minimum resource use.

For purposes of informing design, energy demand at domestic level can be portrayed as the result of INTERPLAY of the following 4 sets of factors:

- Individual aspects
- Household characteristics
- Shared norms, values, expectations and prescriptions
- Building characteristics and operability

The literature review also describes how climatic conditions interact with building design and how approaches to building design respond to climate and culture. Bioclimatic architecture includes the use of mechanical systems when required but otherwise passive design to increase building performance while responding to energy efficiency principles (Goulart, S. and T. Pitta 1994). Despite 'the proven advantage of integrating bioclimatic concepts into building design' (Maciel 2007), the reality is that a 'human factor' is hard to manipulate and predict. Hence, **understanding the interrelated variables that culture and climate bring into building science, is essential in developing clear guidance to enable successful PEB design.**

Indoor comfort expectations and indeed ‘climate needs to be understood equally as an idea that takes shape in cultures and can therefore be changed by cultures’ (Hulme 2015). The concept of Energy Culture integrates cultural and social drivers towards understanding domestic energy demand. A multidisciplinary approach is needed in an attempt to explain “what makes people consume energy in the ways they do”. According to Shove (2003), occupants’ actions are deeply influenced by social norms, as well as cultural and economic factors. Thus, instead of focusing on individual actions and attitudes, the focus should be put on the transformation of collective conventions (Vischer 2008).

While cultural and social determinants of domestic energy demand are important considerations for PEBs design, they do not lend themselves well to integrated modelling of household energy demand. In fact, while social practice, cultural habits, adaptation and social norms largely explain energy end-use, we are only at the beginning of systematically cross-analysing social and cultural data with building modelling data. At this preliminary stage, selected bundles of everyday practices are juxtaposed in the implementation of a multi-layer analysis of building data. This approach has its base in studies of technology and society, seeking to open the way to new avenues for modelling energy demand, ‘beyond the usual technology and economic-based approach’ (Wilhite and Shove 1998).

The work of Stephenson et al. (2010) outlines an '**Energy Cultures framework (ECF) for understanding the factors that influence energy demand**, providing a structure for addressing the problem of multiple interpretations of 'behaviour' by suggesting that it is influenced **by the interactions between three core vectors: norms, energy practices and material culture**. As stated in ENERGISE (2019), ECF’s goal is to identify cultural and social aspects that can influence measures towards energy efficiency. Table 1 shows a modified version of the Energy Cultures Framework (ECF) as the ENERGISE project produced.

Element	Examples
Material conditions	Technologies, energy infrastructure, household characteristics such as insulation, energy sources and heating devices
Attitudes, perceptions and social norms	Aspirations, expected comfort levels, environmental concern, respect for tradition, social acceptability of wasteful/resource-intensive activities
Everyday practices	The temporal and spatial dynamics of practices unfolding in the home that play a role in when and how the home is heated, as well as what rooms are heated and when (such as cooking and washing), use of appliances, use and maintenance of technologies

TABLE 1 - ENERGY CULTURES FRAMEWORK (ECF). MODIFIED VERSION - SOURCE: ENERGISE.

We build on the cultural and social drivers in the ECF and propose three core categorizations as shown in tables 2, 3, and 4, namely material conditions; to attitudes, perceptions and social norms; and everyday practices, respectively.

Material conditions		
Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information, etc	Income	Household size, design and construction
Driver	Definition	
Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information, etc	How technologies shift energy and associated costs, either by enabling efficiency or by enabling different energy demand patterns (more or less) through the establishment of new norms of technology-adaptive living.	
Income	Estimating how household income impacts on the adoption of specific measures and technologies	
Household size, design, construction	Impact on the energy demand and on the implementation of systems, technologies and materials.	

TABLE 2 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO MATERIAL CONDITIONS

Attitudes, perceptions and social norms			
The role of policy, regulations, laws and subsidisation	Demographic factors	Routines and habits, social conventions	Social responsibilities, time-space considerations
Driver	Definition		
The role of policy, regulations, laws and subsidies	Policies etc. encouraging consumers in adopting measures and incentives available for households		
Demographic factors	How demographic factors at NUTS2 level impact on household energy demand		
Routines and habits, social conventions	Social conventions across climate zones, social classes, and generations		
Social responsibilities, time-space considerations	Space and time organization in everyday life linked to social performed activities, e.g. work management and organization		

TABLE 3 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO ATTITUDES, PERCEPTIONS AND SOCIAL NORMS

Everyday practices					
Routines and habits	Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations	Expectations and prior experiences	Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies	Composition, relationships and interactions between household members	Temporal and spatial arrangements
Driver			Definition		
Routines and habits			Individuals' normalised (unquestioned) actions		
Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations			Space and time organization in everyday life linked to individually performed activities		
Expectations and prior experiences			Ideal conditions and lessons learnt		
Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies			Education level and skills which allow efficient use of a system or technology		

Composition, relationships and interactions between household members	Family structure, generation turnover, internal dynamics
Temporal and spatial arrangements	Space and time organization in everyday life linked to household characteristics

TABLE 4 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO EVERYDAY PRACTICES

We further developed 2 key concepts for PEBs: Household composition and Time Geography of energy demand.

Time and space promote constraints on energy demand in people’s everyday life, (Ellegård 2017). Time geography research offers a means to consider several household members’ daily activities at the same time, recognising that the time-space context in which the activities are performed might constrain a household ability to reduce energy use. This perspective emphasises the ways in which timing, location and synchronisation between activities and individuals are drivers that enable or disable energy efficiency in people’s everyday life. For example, energy demand from housing appliances might increase with rising numbers of devices and more frequent use, together with the individualization of appliances. Time geography serves to cluster the various energy cultures within different climatic areas and regions by using an empirical method, which responds to the principles of the user centric design.

2. Defining the concept for the Atlas and data searching.

In the following sections of this report, the concept for the 2CAP Energy Atlas is described. The research was focused on compiling the literature review findings and the data variables which will populate the mapping exercise. We introduce the concept for the Atlas as a design tool by addressing the following questions: *How can the Atlas tool be conceptualised to support the PEB design process? How can user energy behaviour be integrated into an Atlas?*

The Atlas configuration is expected to contain 2 different layers of information:

- **The 1st LAYER based on an interconnected GIS map** is composed by data sets related to the EU building sector, defined by the following tasks: (i) “National and local regulatory frame and boundary conditions for PEBs”; (ii) “Culture and climate as variables in energy use in domestic buildings”.

Energy consumption variables related to energy consumption data by domestic services will be detailed at household level:

- 1st Level of accuracy: Data from occupied High-Performance Residential Buildings.
- 2nd Level of accuracy: NUTS2 is the expected level of detailed information extended to EU territories.

Climatic variables describe the key conditions for characterising the 4 main climatic areas

Socio-economic variables describe the key conditions for characterising the socio-economic differences among EU territories.

- **The 2nd LAYER on energy demand patterns** from the lens of ‘everyday practices’, ‘rules’, ‘demographics and social norms’ and ‘material conditions’ refers to each territory and climate area defined previously. This text and graphical material aims to indicate general trends in order to inform the future design of PEBs.

With the scope to frame the different data variables of the 2CAP Energy Atlas within the ECF and the ‘cultural and social drivers’ categorization, developed in tables 2,3 and 4 of this report, an integrated table has been composed (Table 5) to show how data variables are categorised by socio-cultural drivers within the ECF.

A series of key data sources are also identified, which will be utilised in populating the 2CAP Energy Atlas:

- The EU Building Stock Observatory (BSO)
- IEA Energy Efficiency Indicators 2019
- Eurostat – Energy Consumption in Households 2017
- The Odyssee-Mure project
- European Environment Agency (EEA)

The research focuses on understanding culture and climate variables on energy demand at household level in the four climatic areas: Sub-arctic, Oceanic, Continental and Mediterranean. It provides data sources and description elements to characterise the territories of each climate:

1. Energy consumption in households
2. Socio-economic factors
3. Climatic factors

The literature review brings relevant findings on various aspects related to culture and climate as: Indoor temperature preferences, perceived indoor air quality, oversupply of heat, control of the indoor climate management systems, media attention, relative indoor air humidity, knowledge about own energy consumption, etc.

The design options for the 2CAP Energy Atlas platform have also been explored. Which include descriptions of envisioned features and functionalities and definitions of the expected outcomes for PEB design. **Several GIS applications are available and have been assessed as part of the research activities conducted.** Mapstore technology is expected to satisfy CULTURAL-E requirements. This technology is a highly modular open source WebGIS framework developed by GeoSolutions to create, manage and securely share maps and mashups. The Atlas should bring designers to new levels of

knowledge; current experience should be captured and improved. **The Atlas, as a data visualization library, will add to energy designers' sources of input in designing PEBs.**

The principal expected outcomes from the Atlas are advise to building designers, as the main target users:

- Contributing to the understanding of current and future energy demand scenarios at household and building levels.
- Indicating conditions where particular technology approaches might best be used or avoided, supporting the dimensioning of RES, bringing key criteria for dimensioning storage systems.
- Informing operability and interface design of the BMS depending on cultural-climatic patterns and practices.
- Characterisation of comfort level standards in consideration of cultural and climatic factors.

1 Introduction

The contents of the present deliverable D2.1 are structured as follows:

Section 2 is focusing on social practice and energy studies research. The contents are divided in two subsections:

- 2.1 Social and cultural dimensions of energy demand.

In the CULTURAL-E project, cultural and climatic considerations are incorporated into the Plus Energy Building (PEB) designs, aimed at improving the energy post-occupancy energy performance of the building. This approach acknowledges that energy cultures and practices shape and are shaped by technologies and that these combinations can enable energy positive (energy plus) buildings.

Although there are a wide range of different schools of thought on factors shaping domestic energy demand, a dominant concept is centred upon an idealised energy consumer, characterised as a person who is driven by functional and rational decisions about their energy use at home. This idea of deliberate, conscious consumption implies that such consumers know what uses energy and how much; that they have choices to switch to reduce energy; that they are singularly motivated to do so; that they are making decisions for themselves rather than on behalf of others, or for caring responsibilities etc; and that they have a close understanding of air movement, heat transfer, and other functions of buildings and materials.

Since most of these assumptions do not hold most of the time, research has increasingly disrupted this view, and sought new ways of understanding the imbricated relationships between buildings, energy, domesticity, as well as social and cultural practices.

This chapter reflects on how technologies and patterns of user demand intersect with PEBs by a process of literature review on the following themes related to (i) cloud-based management systems, (ii) building comfort systems and (iii) technology solutions for building flexibility.

- 2.2 Understanding the drivers of everyday energy practices.

Key aspects of domestic energy use are defined based on the literature review spanning social science energy research:

1. Individual householder factors

- Personal views, values and convictions
- Routines and habits
- Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations
- Expectations and prior experiences
- Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies

2. Household characteristics

- Composition, relationships and interactions between household members
 - Temporal and spatial arrangements
 - Income
3. Shared norms, values, expectations and prescriptions
- The role of policies, regulations, laws and subsidisation
 - Demographic factors
 - Routines and habits, social conventions
 - Social responsibilities, time-space considerations
4. Building characteristics and operability
- Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information, etc
 - Household size, design and construction

It is the INTERPLAY of the 4 sets of factors above that are the key to understanding the cultural and social aspects of energy use. Hence, it is the interrelationships, e.g. through time, social practices, etc that we can understand how to specify the design of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs).

Section 3 of the deliverable focuses on Climate Areas, it brings insights on how climatic conditions determine the Plus Energy Building (PEB) design process, while reflecting on the relation among cultural drivers and climatic territories. The research focused on two themes included in the following subsections:

- 3.1 Integrating Climatic Conditions within the High-Performance Building Design

A brief literature reference re-visioning how climatic variables have been integrated within the Building design standards in recent decades.

- 3.2 Climate and Culture as interconnected factors

This section offers some insights from the literature review on how climate and culture variables are interconnected and become interdependent.

In **Section 4**, the literature review focuses on the concept of Energy Culture and key variables for PEB, the contents are distributed in three subsections:

- 4.1 Energy Cultures Framework (ECF)

The insights on this section reflect on the energy culture concept and its evolution, aiming to cluster energy cultures within EU societies and territories. To do so, the ECF is used as a methodological guide to characterise the singularities within each cluster.

According to Stephenson et al. (2010), 'the energy culture framework suggests that consumer energy behaviour can be understood at its most fundamental level by examining the interactions between norms (e.g. beliefs, understandings), material culture (e.g. technologies, building form) and energy practices (e.g. activities, processes)'. In addition, as stated in the ENERGISE project (2019), 'Energy cultures

can also vary substantially within countries or across geopolitical boundaries, which draws attention to the need for new units of analysis ‘beyond the nation-state’ as part of new and innovative cross-national and cross-cultural comparisons in energy research’.

- 4.2 Implications of cultural and social drivers

Different drivers are potentially responsible for differences in household management and energy demand. In this section, these findings have been reported in tables categorized according to the ECF, as implemented in the ENERGISE project (2019).

- 4.3 Key Concept for PEBs: Household composition and Time Geography of energy demand

This section describes how family structure impacts on energy demand, and how it is configured by means of PEB design. Households are diverse, and also often contain internal diversity. When intending to design Plus Energy Buildings accounting for social practices, this diversity must be duly accounted for.

As exposed by Palm and Ellegård (2011), time-geography generates ‘opportunities to research projects, to visualize daily activities and discuss the constraints encountered...to capture the unique and complex, intertwined everyday life activity pattern of each household [...] integrating the conceptual framework developed within time geography could help to figure out how various households or household clusters use energy. Household energy use is a collective rather than individualized process’.

Section 5 introduces an initial Vision for the Atlas, as a design tool, by addressing the questions:

- How to design the 2CAP Energy Atlas as a tool for supporting PEB design process?
- How to integrate individual’s energy behaviours into an Atlas?

Also, it considers the beneficiary target groups and the existing knowledge gaps which might be covered as a new support tool for PEB design.

Section 6 deals with the data sets for building the 2CAP Energy Atlas, providing a description of the sources identified for characterising energy demand by domestic services/uses in European households, which will be used to generate the data set in order to be incorporated in the 2 CAP Energy Atlas. It also includes a list of the socio-economic and climatic factors foreseen to be hosted in the Atlas.

Section 7 aims at understanding culture and climate variables on energy consumption at household level. The section brings the key elements for Climate and cultural differences/similarities in the 4 main EU climatic areas:

- 7.1 Sub-arctic climate

- 7.2 Oceanic climate
- 7.3 Continental climate
- 7.4 Mediterranean climate

Section 8 aims at providing the first reflections about the designing the 2CAP Energy Atlas, its functionalities and potential outcomes. It is divided in two subsections:

- 8.1 Description of envisioned features and functionalities

Assessment of available GIS platforms which respond to the envisioned Atlas structure, together with the description of the potential functionalities.

- 8.2 Defining the expected outcomes from the 2CAP Energy Atlas for the PEB design process

Through the analysis of the expected outcomes, the implications for the relevant project objectives are highlighted.

Section 9 gives an overview of the process & conclusions.

This includes:

- A brief account of the research process which integrates data statistics, GIS and social science theories on energy demand at household level.
- A concluding reflection about the added value contributed by key findings within the current research process.

As an introduction to the literature review for the present deliverable, several key terms frame the discussions on building energy efficiency in a social context, which in turn inform the PEB design criteria. These key terms are further explored in the following chapters, including the links to CULTURAL-E. Meanwhile they are introduced in the following glossary:

- **Building systems** are the techno-material arrangements, such as the Electrical, HVAC, Security, Life Safety, Lighting, Utilities, Telecom, and Energy Management. These systems are rarely, if ever, independent entities; rather, they usually depend on each other and upon human interactions to operate efficiently and effectively. Building systems can be defined as the relationship between equipment, assemblies and components. They are often evaluated and controlled both as an independent unit and as a part of a larger network and the whole building.
- **Climate** broadly describes the average weather in a place over time; however, it can be understood culturally, as a function of the relationship between people and environment. Climate has a clear link to techno-material configurations that

enable building occupants to be healthy and comfortable in buildings through different local external weather conditions. However, importantly, it also configures social and cultural traditions (clothing, social codes, events, identities, etc) that in turn shape how people use buildings, including through ‘a widening and changing range of cultures, resources, practices, artefacts and rituals’ (Hulme 2015).

- **Culture** is concerned with ideas, customs and expressions, including artistic expression. In this context, it is particularly relevant how values, traditions, social codes, symbols and practices relate to substantive and material forms. When people inhabit buildings, they do not simply adapt to the technology, they shape it through their pre-existing beliefs and practices; they bring with them ‘a historically transmitted pattern of meaning embodied in symbols, a system of inherited conceptions expressed in symbolic forms by means of which men [sic] communicate, perpetuate and develop their knowledge about and attitudes towards life’ (Geertz 1973).
- **Energy Culture** refers to consumer energy behaviour at its most fundamental level by examining the interactions between norms (e.g. beliefs, understandings), material culture (e.g. technologies, building form) and energy practices (e.g. activities, processes) (Stephenson et al. 2010).
- **Energy demand** is the energy attributable, in this case, to a building, arising from its operation – which includes the fulfilment of its service function to the occupancies for which it is designed. This is a complex emergent outcome of the everyday practices performed in connection with the building, as a nexus of (i) the social practices in which occupants are engaged, (ii) the time spans over which these practices are performed and (iii) the location(s) and surrounding conditions within which they take place.
- **Energy practices**, in social-science energy research, are conceptualised as the energy demand arising from people’s performance of everyday life.
- **Flexibility** refers to how social practices are configured; the kind of interconnections that exist between practices; the societal ordering of practices in time and space; how technologies and supply chains constitute forms of energy dynamics and how they relate to convictions of choice (DEMAND Centre 2018).
- **Household** is defined as one person or a group of people who use a specific accommodation as their only or main residence in which energy demand is divided and performed by householders. Care may be delivered by one householder to another. Household composition may affect life and health expectations and outcomes for its members. Households are highly heterogeneous and dynamic, in type, function, and form.
- **Human computer interaction** (HCI) in this case refers to how people interact with digital technologies and to what extent these are successful – in terms of human and environmental outcomes, across different contexts. As its name

implies, HCI consists of three parts: the user, the computer or technology itself, and the ways they work together.

- **User behaviour** in this case describes the more overt planned, cognitive and conscious decisions that surround the interactions that households have with heating, cooling and ventilation systems, openings or other techno-material arrangements. Each of these elements may have an impact on building performance, with implications for plus energy targets. However, conscious behaviour can only explain a relatively minor part of human-techno-material interactions that underpin energy performance, since it is more individual-focussed than, for example, ideas of energy cultures and social practices.

Accordingly, the themes which have been object of the literature review are:

- **Understanding energy demand**

Our literature review aims at understanding how cultural and climatic variables shape domestic practices which, in turn, are configuring energy demand at household level.

How do cultural and climate drivers affect the standardization of domestic practices? At what level do they determine household energy demand needs? This literature review focuses on how everyday life is influenced by climate conditions and common social patterns, which define the way energy demand is socially conceived, accepted and reproduced. Understanding users' interpretations of standard practices and how they culturally configure the need to consume energy can support PEB design.

- **Energy efficiency**

How are energy efficiency practices and technologies culturally integrated into household energy demand depending on climate conditions? This question suggests the need to investigate the average household's adaptation to change, when new housing elements and performance criteria are applied to daily practices.

- **Home comfort**

How do cultural conventions of domestic comfort vary in different climatic areas? Understanding the conventions of comfort could bring further insights into better articulating the relationship between material conditions, daily rhythms and where those practices are performed in relation to different home environments.

- **Influencing demand**

How should evolving cultural patterns of energy demand be addressed when designing PEB's? The meta-analysis intends to open a debate on how to incorporate PEB technologies and design concepts into a households' energy practices, aiming to enable the user to put strategies into practice which may reduce the existing gap from design expectation and post-occupancy performance.

- **Adapting social practices**

PEB design depends on understanding how practices might change in a new home environment and how such changes might be facilitated (or not) by the cultural and climatic factors where the buildings are located. The socio-technical context that accommodates domestic energy-demanding practices is determined by shared conventions and beliefs. Nonetheless, infrastructures, appliances and practices could be designed to play a key role to support energy conservation in households.

- **Temporal and spatial variation**

There is a clear need for a more sophisticated analysis of spatial, temporal and social variations in end-use practices in order to produce more refined scenarios of future demand, and to inform current policy initiatives and critically examine their effects. At a minimum, this depends on conceptualizing the spatial and temporal 'profiles' of energy demanding practices and understanding how these evolve.

- **Energy Flexibility**

How can energy 'flexibility' be interpreted? This literature review opens the debate on the capacity of a household living in a PEB to use energy in different locations, or at different times of the day or year (i.e. through storage or by changing the timing of activities), or to rearrange practices aiming at enabling an energy positive balance among production and demand.

- **Domestic IT Use**

What are the cultural and climatic implications for domestic IT use? Automated devices can provide active management of energy demand, but how can they be configured to an energy culture frame in which social practices prevail? This literature review aims to bring insights on how IT devices might interact with domestic practices, e.g. space heating, laundry practices or cooking.

2 Social practice and energy studies research

2.1 Social and cultural dimensions of energy demand.

It is well understood that **households are key actors in determining final energy demand of residential buildings**. However, normative conceptualisations of the relationship between housing energy demand and households are limited to a focus on behaviours. Thus, a dominant ideal energy consumer is characterised as a ‘persona’ who is intended to develop functional and rational decisions about their energy use in the functioning of the buildings’ typology.

More recent scholarship takes a flatter ontological view in accepting the complexities of socio-material relations. **Households “use” energy** not primarily through conscious or hedonistic choices relating to energy or utility, or costs and benefits, but **as a result of a complex set of social and cultural practices**. They may be caring for others (humans or non-humans) or they may be simply fulfilling social conventions. Their daily practices are mainly “below the radar” in that they take place as parts of routine domestic life, punctuated by crises when things do not work or for some reason change is required. Academic studies of social and cultural life have therefore begun to disrupt the concept of the conscious energy user, in an attempt to reach new ways of understanding the nature of the building energy performance as it relates to social life.

According to Anable et al. (2014), ‘understanding energy demand depends, above all, on understanding the timing and location of a range of interconnected social practices. It also shows that we need to combine data on the sequencing, synchronisation, timing, location and performance of a range of social practices, [...] and over time’.

Based on the above definition of **energy demand**, Anable et al. (2014) stated that its variation is related to:

- (i) variation and change in the **performance of social practices** that directly or indirectly require energy;
- (ii) variation and change in the **temporal and spatial distributions** of these performances;
- (iii) variation and change in the **‘energy intensity’** of these performances

The insights from CULTURAL-E are planned to allow designers, decision makers and researchers to (i) define the current performing cultural and climatic drivers of the practices’ dynamics for domestic energy demand over space and time; (ii) understand the processes that replicate practices over time; and (iii) support PEB design by anticipating resource intensity arising from interactions between occupants, climate, society, culture and techno-material arrangements.

Integrating the cultural and climatic specificities that social, economic and behavioural variables bring to the study of building energy performance for PEB design, aims here at supporting guidance to enable successful PEB’s post-occupancy performance

evaluations. Success at one level includes a balance between energy demand and occupancy, but it is also a complex measure that incorporates ontological aspects of the human condition, such as security, comfort, control, health, and cultural and social needs being met.

The current deliverable is also intended to **explore how user operated systems and semi-automatic systems in domestic low energy settings** are in accordance with and/or conflict with social practice logic.

Various technologies are being deployed during the project and tested in the demo cases that are based on semi-automatic systems. These imply a need to consider carefully aligning user practices with technologies and control systems. The current state of the literature on whether this alignment can work, for whom, when and how is therefore of importance. *What are the critiques from social practice angles? And, how might tools and guidelines to support designers and key players involved in the design and construction of PEB work or not?*

2.1.1 Building Management System

As discussed above, research shows that households are typically not focussed upon energy consumption and/or constrained by a range of capabilities. They are also constrained by social conventions and rules that are deeply embedded in society, such as the need to care for others, to have a clean body, and to present a warm (or cool, if it is hot weather) home to guests. Individual householders may be unaware of options to run regular white goods in eco-efficient ways. **The idea arises of a house designed around household practices, in which occupants are guided, informed, and enabled to perform practices in line with cultures and social contexts as well as within ecological limits.**

The findings from the literature review show that energy demand is largely the result of everyday practices. Although building technologies and monitored systems hold the promise to decrease energy consumption through improving performance efficiency, the resource intensity of home practices is dynamic and in various ways wider factors encourage increasing overall energy demand, thus potentially negating the benefits that might accrue from householder efforts or from building technologies.

However, when we compare PEBs and smart homes concepts, considering that automated appliances and technologies are being introduced into PEB design, research studies highlight the fact that the permeability of the automated solutions into the housing market has not increased as expected. We can speculate that this might be due to several factors such as affordability, desirability, interoperability, skills and knowledge, access and availability, etc.

When intending to promote ‘user centric approaches’, **our focus seeks to avoid the trap of envisaging an ‘ideal consumer’, but instead to recognise the diversity of**

users and practices. The housing sector tends to define home technology users' target groups in narrow terms - which tends to build an image of the exemplar tech-manager and sustainable thinker, a kind of 'Resource Man' figure (Strengers 2014). This figure becomes then a target for smart technologies and energy saving ambitions. As a consequence, domestic technologies continue to be designed by focusing on this specific technology user. However, in so doing, these efforts and ambitions are misaligned with the realities of everyday energy demand.

Shifting the focus to understanding energy practices and its embedded interrelations is an opportunity to address an integrative PEB design practice where gender, diversity and multiculturalism are core elements. Thus engaging with energy practices themselves and understanding how they are interconnected among and within everyday contexts also presents an opportunity to avoid unexpected gaps in operational performance when designing automated technologies and even more when referring to PEBs.

According to Strengers and Nichols (2017), automated home technology design confronts practice-oriented approaches in several respects, all originating with initial assumptions regarding patterns of causation and agency. Automated home technology advocates often promote "convenience", assuming presumably that simplicity and pleasure guide daily life, and that, therefore the conundrum to be addressed is the potentially competing demands of satisfying this pleasure-seeking while also reducing domestic energy demand. A practice-oriented approach would also recognise convenience as shaping energy demand, however, through an understanding that integrating and managing home technology implies "complexity" rather than "freeing up time" from daily activities. Convenience is negotiated across a vast array of social and cultural obligations, codes, meanings, and demands, rather than a simple matter of personal choice. This reality is distant from how home technologies are positioned by an emerging smart home products and services industry, seeking to deliver sustainable homes filled with "pleasance", aiming at making it become a less energy intensity pillar of modern lifestyles.

The great majority of system/user interfaces are oriented towards 'smart' remote controls, with very little information about indoor environmental quality and even less (or nothing) on guiding users toward more energy efficient options, rather than functioning as real decision support tools. If suitably redesigned, how might such an interface fare in responding to and informing users' energy practices?

Human Computer Interaction (HCI) and User Experience (UX) research is focusing on understanding 'rhythms, patterns and cycles of everyday family life' (Eggen et al. 2014) emulating user-centred design. As Jensen et al. (2018) argue, in many cases, the resulting apps attempt to tap into householders' desires, and configure indoor expectations around luxury; potentially increasing energy consumption, thus subverting any sustainable lifestyle goals that occupants may intend to achieve.

In line with Strengers et al. (2018) stated, aiming to disrupt the ‘solutionism’ raised by home technologies, HCI design could ensure a broader permeability of automated and connected home devices and systems by allowing more assorted expressions and performances, together with the inclusion of a wider range of potential users, across genders, cultures, households, etc.

The CULTURAL-E interface, reachable both via App & Web application (with smartphone, tablet or computer), **is intended to provide understandable information on indoor conditions and energy consumption, giving the user the ability and the tailored details needed to change parameters in an informed way.** The interface will provide hints on energy implications (like in summer “please, consider closing the window since the temperature outside is higher than inside”) and will put in place strategies to reduce energy consumption and improve indoor conditions. While this is a step forward from earlier luxury-oriented apps, it still has many limitations in terms of linking to broader social and cultural contexts.

According to the literature review, two strategies that can assist users over time are “goal setting” and “comparisons with peers”. With “goal setting” the user is asked to set a goal for a parameter, like monthly energy consumption for heating, and try not to exceed that goal. According to Hsiaw (2013), ‘goal-setting theory suggests that goals serve as a reference standard in the cognitive comparison process of self-satisfaction and evaluation’, in addition, as stated by Heath et al. (1999), ‘goals are simply reminders of tasks to do, which is belied by evidence that people report less or more satisfaction with the same outcome when their goals differ’.

In relation to social comparison, as referred to by Hsiaw (2013), ‘each agent compares their material outcome against the expectation of their peers [...]. Nonetheless, every agent prefers to compare himself to a peer with the least self-control possible, regardless of the severity of his impulsiveness’.

The notion that we are as humans responsive to benchmarks we set in accordance with others is not new. Moreover, based on the work from Locke et al. (2002), it is stated that ‘while publicly announced goals may also influence behaviour through social censure or praise, the fact that individuals respond to goals outside the public domain indicates that social reputation concerns are not the sole driver’.

2.1.2 Building Comfort systems

Innovative technologies as part of CULTURAL-E: The hybrid ventilation system, the smart air movement for thermal comfort and the decentralized packed heat pump system.

Research on indoor thermal comfort evidences how user’s expectations are frequently unfulfilled when automated appliances and technologies are integrated within the housing management system. **The thermal comfort standards on which the**

technology design is formed is based on very specific and stable indoor climate conditions, which most households do not actually subscribe to. It raises the following questions: *How can a climate control system which allows long-term sustainability based on automated technology be designed? Could an adaptive approach to thermal comfort be an operative yet sustainable design produced by integrating automated technologies?*

In PEBs, there is a known limit of energy available; the sustainability of climate control practices is determined by the availability of energy resources. Then, **adaptive standards for thermal comfort and sustainability for PEB design may be considered and modelled based on the cultural and climatic specificities.**

User control of hybrid ventilation and climate control technologies is also important: ‘the building should give occupants the chance to adjust the conditions to suit themselves. Discomfort is increased if control is not provided, or if the controls are ineffective, inappropriate or unusable’ (Nicol and Humphreys 2002).

As stated by Behar (2016), the social sciences research about how ventilation practices relate to indoor comfort perceptions of households reveals a number of insights into how these practices are often limited by the physical arrangement of ventilation systems within the home. The investigation of ventilation routines indicates that individuals do not always use technologies according to their design purpose. By exploring moments of “disruption”, the aforementioned study found that while some ventilation activities have adapted since living with innovative technologies, this process of change is slow and unpredictable and not always aligned with designers’ intentions for sustainable lifestyles. This highlights the need to consider how occupants’ ventilation practices are integrated during the design, construction and handover of new low energy housing to ensure that new homes can enable, and perhaps even encourage, people to live comfortably yet with set resource use parameters.

Innovative ventilation systems comprise components such as heat exchangers, fans, ductwork, switches, sensors and filters, many of which are not found in the current housing stock. Although the expectations that these technologies will provide fresh air in airtight dwellings whilst reducing energy demand, the findings of the literature review questions such technological determinism, prevalent in the buildings research, which assumes that new technological interventions will somehow stimulate change by themselves. Instead, to fully realise the potential of innovative ventilation systems in terms of energy and indoor air quality (IAQ), inhabitants would need to change the way they ventilate their homes too; technologies by themselves may not create this change.

The design of PEB with innovative ventilation techniques incur different ventilation practices compared with a traditional home. If people do not adapt the ways they ventilate but continue to use traditional strategies such as opening windows, PEBs may

use more energy than expected, contributing to the ‘performance gap’ between designed and actual energy use.

Within the CULTURAL-E project, the discourse around practice theory and energy demand extends the project scope to the design and construction teams, when focusing on a specific set of technologies, including them in the discussion of the residents’ associated practices. Rather than pointing to residents’ as exhibiting inappropriate “behaviour”, CULTURAL-E seeks to understand how both practices and spatial configurations contribute to an enhanced reduction of domestic energy use in relation to the ways people adapt to living with innovative ventilation technologies.

A growing body of work shows that the physical configuration of ventilation components does not account for occupants’ actual practices, and thus socio-technical arrangements. As a result, homes are likely to be uncomfortable, e.g. overheating, and lead to residents resorting to the use of active cooling systems. This would of course work against the success of PEBs in terms of both energy use and IAQ.

‘It was also found that ventilation is ‘practiced’ by residents through the routinised performance of dynamically connected clusters of embodied habits, conventions, values and objects. These relate to a host of activities related to providing and maintaining a comfortable, safe and healthy home environment’ (Behar 2016).

The importance of past experience on people’s lifestyles is also highlighted. While residents seek to make sense of the innovative ventilation systems, many might be unclear or not engaged about what the technologies are supposed to do, how they work and what households should do to operate the equipment and to prevent problems.

The interactions between residents and professionals involved in designing, constructing and managing homes have the potential to be leveraged to enable residents to develop more sustainable ventilation practices.

From the literature findings we surmise that the **design, construction and handover of PEBs, may need to integrate practice theory concepts** in order to ensure that new homes can enable, and perhaps even encourage, people to live comfortably yet with minimum resource use. **Only in this way do innovative ventilation systems have the potential to play an effective role** in the success of new PEBs in EU climates.

2.1.3 Technology solutions for building flexibility

“Flexibility refers to the capacity to use energy in different locations at different times of day or year (via storage or by changing the timing of an activity including whether it takes place at all); to switch fuels; to smooth or create peaks in demand; or, to re-arrange practices in ways that reduce energy demand” (Torriti 2018).

Flexibility is necessary from a temporal supply-demand perspective in PEBs. Time-value deeply affects how households can vary energy demand and how it varies, e.g. depending on the energy culture and households' unit typologies. By operationalising the 'Energy flexibility' concept, its applicability into the PEB design process could be assessed.

According to Cass and Shove (2018), energy flexibility research aims at reducing demand rather than simply organising technologies aimed at meeting peak demand, as Demand Side Management (DSM) or Demand Side Response (DSR). The aim of strategies such as real-time energy and pricing is to modify the timing of energy demand at household level. However, results to date show limited benefits: "Currently, smart-metering technologies feedback and current forms of real-time pricing (in the domestic setting) have had only modest effect. Meta-studies of household smart metering feedback trials show reductions in demand of e.g. 3-5%" (MaKerracher and Torriti 2013); a reasonable explanation for this fact is that householders are not always in a position to change the timing of their energy demands at their own convenience.

However, as referred in the aforementioned research, 'daily and weekly schedules are defined by collective social and temporal rhythms, not by individual choice'. Considering this idea further, the insights from the literature review suggest that variations in demand relate to the synchronisation and sequencing of practices that comes in the form of energy consumption. Going on to argue that these arrangements are significant for understanding and characterising the extent and nature of flexibility, the conclusion which emerges is that **different forms of flexibility are outcomes of how sets of social practices intersect over time.**

In understanding the features of the timing of energy demand, the key to discovering this consists of getting to know what people are doing when there is a peak in demand. *What are the cultural drivers establishing morning and evening peaks, variations during the week or between week-days and week-ends?* Techniques of combining the data on domestic electricity use with information about the timing of activities like those relating to ICT, cooking, heating or lighting, are further deployed within the section dedicated to 'Time geography' research (section 5.3).

FIGURE 1 - AVERAGE 24-HOUR ELECTRICITY USE PROFILE FOR SAMPLE OF 250 OWNER OCCUPIED HOMES. 2010-11 (DATA SOURCE DECC 2013: ANDERSON 2016C:3)

The figure above shows an example of patterns of diurnal energy demand. It is possible to compare the time profiles of different sectors of the population, or of weekends and weekdays, aiming at understanding these dynamics for integrating the related energy practices as demand variables into the design process. Comparing such data across geographies, cultures, households or socio-technical arrangements, may bring further understanding of how these different demand profiles might be manipulated through intervening in practices.

Recent studies have investigated the forms of coordination on which patterns of demand depend. **The combinations of synchronised practices and the sequencing of energy demand are key for understanding how flexible energy demand might be.**

To understand the dynamics of energy demand, a deep investigation into exactly which practices are 'synchronised' and sequenced, and when, is required. Also, it is necessary to interpret how these arrangements might change over time, and vary from one climatic area to another, and/or how they are otherwise characterised across different cultural and social contexts.

As research to date has shown: 'First, certain practices are likely to be more 'flexible' than others depending on how they are positioned in relation to other practices. Second, some people (or groups of people) are likely to be more 'flexible' than others, depending on the range of practices with which they are engaged. Third, flexibility, in both senses, appears to be an outcome of how entire complexes of social practices are configured in space and time' (Shove and Noel 2018). Flexible practices are thus the converse of closely-coupled sequencing and/or rigid synchronisation, whereas flexible people are less dependent upon sequencing and more upon the range of practices in which they are involved. Furthermore, it is important to note that many inflexibilities are in fact imposed upon households by external requirements, for example, to be at work or

school at particular times, or otherwise to hold to particular temporal rhythms and patterns. Thus, the idea of flexible societies; promoting ‘flexibility’ by “changing the ways in which daily lives are coordinated and the practices of which they are made.

In other words, the goal of balancing demand to the needs of more distributed sources and timings of supply seek to enable relevant alterations in when different activities take place and their related intensity. Henceforth, designing PEBs, as a new home concept, is involved temporally with the scenarios and systems that allow households and communities to be more energy-flexible.

Enabling social-temporal dynamics that are compatible with reduced and/or renewable energy depends on much more than pricing, determinist technology, or individual convictions. Rather, the possibilities for change on a community scale depend on how social practices are arranged in relation to each other, and on the forms of flexibility (or not) that appear as consequence. Such conditions are not stable, and they are linked to the cultural influences which drive the synchronisation or not of everyday energy practices. These findings argue for further **design alternatives which emerge from understanding how the social-temporal energy dynamics within the building community are interrelated**, and for analysing and learning from past as well as present regimes of ‘flexibility’ in different practices and how technologies could contribute to it.

2.2 Understanding the drivers of everyday energy practices

CULTURAL-E aims at supporting PEB design. Beyond the design and construction phases, an indirect goal is to contribute to the evolution of domestic energy demand, enabling sustainable energy transitions. This implies a vision of cultural change as a key ingredient of successful reductions in household energy use (O’rouke and Lollo 2015), sustained and avoiding potential ‘rebound effects’ (Hertwich 2005) in PEB households.

In this perspective, it is necessary to implement **an approach that accounts for cultural diversities, ‘recognising households as a key unit of social organisation**, thereby challenging concepts of households as more or less self-contained enclaves of individualised private life. Interestingly, households frequently display their own practice cultures, that is, unique combinations of practices that meet individual members’ needs and that emerge from their social interactions and joint practices both within the household and outside’ (ENERGISE 2019). Households, of various compositions performing different practices are an essential element of analysis, aim to complement other energy demand analyses.

In providing a working definition for this project of the key aspects of domestic energy, the principal drivers guiding energy demand at domestic level are described as the INTERPLAY of the following 4 sets of factors in sections 3.2.1-3.2.4 below.

The aim is to use these drivers as a framework to categorize different energy users' profiles, referencing cultural and social schemes. It is the understanding of the interrelationships among the proposed aspects, across time, space, practices, organization, etc., that can lead to a tailored design of PEBs which accounts for diversities rather than assuming standardised conditions. In fact, on one reading, the trend of the recent decades for standardisation inside buildings has only led to lower user satisfaction and increased consumption and costs. On the contrary, the proposition here is that diversities and peculiarities can provide a contribution to improving occupants' wellbeing while reducing energy amount and waste.

2.2.1 Individual householder factors

This section refers to individual factors and their connections with wider social and material conditions (e.g. media coverage of energy issues, energy use patterns in workplaces, technological innovation concerning energy generation, economic incentives for micro-generation of energy at household level), which result in turn in differences in household dynamics.

- **Personal views, values and convictions.** These aspects concern resource use more generally, and energy use in particular, and usually arise from the subject's inner beliefs which often are a consequence of long-term environment, social context and socio-economic and educational background. Non-cognitive drivers of human action are important, such as affect or emotions (Sahakian 2015) or bodily memory (Wallenborn and Wilhite 2014) on people's (lack of) engagement in practices, which further strengthens the case for moving beyond exclusively cognitive explanations about the way energy demand is articulated in households.

- **Routines and habits.** Users' actions are the expression of 'individuals engagement in taken-for-granted or tacit routines and habits (and related reductions in cognitive effort needed to make decisions in complex situations). In these accounts, energy use is frequently treated as an enabler of everyday practices' (ENERGISE 2019). Individual lifestyles are usually connected with social status and users' means, which through time shape socially constructed "needs" and "wants" as drivers of personal routines.

- **Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations.** Energy end use at household level is strongly affected by organisation in everyday life linked to householders' performed activities, evidence of 'a close link exists between time use patterns within households and their resource use, including energy' (Jalas 2005; Rau 2015; Torriti 2017). In recent decades, these aspects are increasingly bound up with work-life balance and management, which have brought shifts in home design and time-space organization.

- **Expectations and prior experiences.** The key driver for users' actions consists of achieving comfort and wellbeing in indoor spaces. Ideal conditions and convenience

targets are acquired mechanisms given by individual long-term environmental history and adaptation processes.

- **Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies.** Education level is a key element for raising awareness in energy efficiency and sustainability, which obviously shape the individual actions towards the environment. Nonetheless, education allows the acquisition of skills and knowledge necessary for a proper understanding and efficient use of a system or technology.

2.2.2 Household characteristics

Hereafter an overview is proposed regarding household peculiar features and composition that shape energy demand.

- **Composition** (Druckman and Jackson 2008), relationships and interactions between household members. These variables significantly influence both quality and quantity of household energy use, such as family structure, generation mix, work-life management, technologies and media, etc.

- **Temporal and spatial arrangements.** As above, these features are usually driven by work-life management or individualism versus communitarianism, which shape the household organization in everyday life linked to household characteristics.

- **Income in households** (Schaffrin, A. and Reibling, N. 2015) and economic availability clearly impacts on the adoption of specific measures, technologies and practices. It enables and disables different materiality options, and also has indirect links to time availabilities, educational/skills/knowledge, and other factors more associated with capabilities and aspirations.

2.2.3 Shared norms, values, expectations and rules

Social factors concerning energy use tend to be (re)produced and enforced within domestic settings. Household-specific patterns of energy use both shape and reflect those in other social settings.

- **The role of policy, regulations, laws and subsidisation.** Policy frameworks adopting measures to promote the spread of innovative and efficient technologies, sustainable practices, etc.

- **Demographic factors** also play a role in (re)shaping domestic energy use, including space and water heating. “Needs” and “wants” are generated by social environments, and ‘recent cross-sectional research on environmental views and habits has revealed significant intergenerational differences concerning perceptions of luxury and necessity as well as attitudes and actions concerning the frugal use of resources (including energy) and associated efforts to avoid wasteful behaviour’ (Lavelle and Fahy 2012).

- **Routines and habits, social conventions.** These aspects include standards of social practices related also to the response to sudden natural events, e.g. the attitude to override climatic and natural events with technologies versus to welcoming seasonal differences and natural trends, or to prefer diversity over static environments. Other aspects are also linked to appearance and societal conventions, such as dress codes which influence comfort sensations, and thus the energy demand and system settings to achieve the desired conditions.

- **Social responsibilities, time-space considerations.** Household management, practices in everyday life and time-space organization at household level are linked to performed activities at societal level. In fact, as reflected in research studies, 'the pace and social organization of society can have significant effects on how much energy is used both within households and outside' (Jalas (2002). e.g. work management and its synchronisation with other daily activities clearly affects household energy consumptions.

2.2.4 Building characteristics and operability

- **Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information.** Technologies and tools have evolved at a pace where technological adoption has run a pace far faster than cultural change (Brager and Dear 2008). This is important to how consumers respond in adopting (or not) a given new technology designed to save energy and decrease costs.

- **House size (DSFA 2009), design and construction.** Housing stock is typically shaped over centuries, spanning periods where household features have changed, and materials, configurations, designs and expectations are reflected during both original construction but also subsequent renovations and retrofits. Housing is thus shaped according to the organization of space, organization of values, organization of communication and organization of time, typical of a specific historical and cultural period. Homes are the direct reflection of societal dynamics, together with individual purposes and actions. The final configuration directly impacts on energy demand, on its fabric and on the implementation of systems and technologies. It significantly varies depending on culture and societal structure.

3 Climate Areas

This section brings insights on how climatic conditions are accounted for in the PEB design process. In addition, reflections are proposed on how climatic conditions configure the cultural drivers within societies and how this interconnection may impact the household's energy demand in different European climatic areas.

3.1 Integrating Climatic Conditions within the Building Design

A brief literature reference where revising how the climatic variables have been integrated within the Building design EU standards in the most recent decades.

Since the first human settlements and building constructions, 'designers' took into consideration climate conditions, according to Vitruvius, the most fundamental function of architecture is to provide shelter from the dynamic conditions of our environment, and, vice versa, building' environment (territory and climate) must be considered as a factor to integrate in its design and construction. Buildings were the materialisation of human living condition needs in response to local climate, and they were configured by their availability to use natural resources. In recent times, **the built environment has shifted its basic protection function as to be providing comfort.**

The expectations to control the indoor environment has transformed the amount and proportions of the Building systems. Technologies enabled the development of mechanical control systems which were able, even, to manipulate indoor conditions from a separate position to the passive functions of the building themselves; then, being able to isolate indoor from outdoor environment, as Maver (1971) indicated such trends in modern architecture were 'replacing the functions of the building structure by engineering service systems'.

Among the different schools of thought and practices approach in the recent decades on the domains of architecture and building engineering, a great importance has been dedicated to grow **the concept of bioclimatic design, which is an 'approach that takes advantage of the climate through the right application of design elements and housing technology** to control the thermodynamic processes within the building. Therefore, this control promotes energy saving as well as ensuring comfortable conditions into buildings' (Goulard and Pitta 1994).

Sustainability also plays a key role, as the bioclimatic architecture intends to incorporate a rational use of resources and materials into the design process; in addition, sustainability becomes a consequence of integrating the built environment and the specific climatic condition by means of providing healthy and comfortable indoor living spaces. Furthermore, bioclimatic architecture is frequently conceptualized by means of its 'passive' solutions and measures applied into the project design, but rather than this, in practice, it includes the use of mechanical systems when required but conditioned to increase the performance of the design while responding to energy efficiency principles.

A major objective of the bioclimatic architecture is to ‘increase’ the potential of energy conservation by the climatic considerations incorporated in design. This definition by itself has a second meaning which recognises that controlling climate is not the unique factor that determines the energy uses and intensity occurring in the household.

E.g. Stasinopoulos (1993) indicated that bioclimatic architecture had just become just a method to reduce the energy consumption and the act of energy saving is much more motivated by necessity than by choice. And, Wines (2000) also observes that ‘it is necessary to create and to promote an architectural language really integrated’ - and it can be added – into the cultural aspects of the household, by means of bringing it to the forefront the everyday life patterns of energy demand.

Despite ‘the proven advantage of integrating bioclimatic concepts into building design’ (Maciel et al. 2007), **the reality of the energy demand dynamics demonstrates that the ‘human factor’ is hard to manipulate and predict**, however, all the scientific knowledge accumulated since the second half of the last century through the definition of thousands of technical guidelines, analysis and modelling tools, case studies, monitored data among other sources. **Henceforth, integrating culture specifics through climate considerations is likely to be a fruitful activity**. Understanding the interrelated variables that culture and climate bring into building science is only feasible by applying social theories on users’ energy behaviours and daily routines, aiming at developing a clear guidance criterion to drive PEB design.

3.2 Climate and Culture – Interacting factors

The section offers some insights from the literature review on how climate and culture variables are interconnected and become interdependent.

Many recent scholarly (Shin 2017), contributions to the cultural aspects of energy history share the conviction that ‘culture is not just an analytical framework but has also become a point of intervention for the active creation of our energy future’.

According to Van de Vliert (2018) ‘the circumstances in which societies adapt their cultural values and practices to cold, temperate and hot climates include the availability of funds to cope with climate. Country-level studies have inferred that sustainable energy practices are least prevalent in poorer countries with more demanding climates, moderately prevalent in poor and rich countries with temperate climates, and most prevalent in richer countries with more demanding climates’. Inequalities within countries are significant markers of energy efficiency. Richer households generally have better homes with higher specifications regarding energy efficiency, although they may also have technologies and adopt practices that are higher energy demand, such as pools/spas, or extra heated rooms. Also, in the aforementioned richer countries with more demanding climates, there are social democratic political traditions that have supported energy efficiency in building codes and energy efficient housing as a right,

thus leading to a relatively high quality of housing stock. This raises another aspect of (political) culture as well as climate culture that affects housing energy efficiency.

Furthermore, as referred to by Hulme (2015), 'climate can be understood culturally, as an idea that humans use to stabilize relationships between weather and their patterned lives. In its various manifestations around the world, the idea of climate enables humans to live with their weather through a widening and changing range of cultural resources, practices, artefacts and rituals'. In cooler climate countries, these range from clothing to conventions of appropriate home furnishings to language and meanings of comfort and warmth.

These reflections on climate refer to the deep material and symbolic interactions which occur between weather and cultures in places, as well as interactions which are central to the idea of climate. **Aiming to avoid framing climate as an interdependent global physical system or as a statistical equipment of weather data, 'climate needs to be understood equally as an idea that takes shape in cultures and can therefore be changed by cultures' (Hulme 2015).**

Regarding climate areas in Europe, following the Köppen-Geiger¹ climate classification, the vast majority of Europe can be divided in four main climatic areas:

- Oceanic climate, which corresponds to Cfb, Cfc, Cwb, Cwc in the Köppen classification;
- Mediterranean climate, which corresponds to Csa, Csb in the Köppen classification;
- Continental climate; which corresponds to Dfa, Dwa, Dfb, Dwb, Dsa, Dsb in the Köppen classification;
- Sub-arctic climate, which corresponds to Dsc, Dsd, Dwc, Dwd, Dfc, Dfd in the Köppen classification.

¹ Graphic maps available at: <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>

FIGURE 2 - KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLIMATE CLASSIFICATION IN EUROPE²

The Köppen-Geiger system includes more than 20 different categories, which do not quality for transposed into the 2CAP Energy Atlas. ASHRAE proposed a modified classification reducing the categories to 5 main climate zones based on Heating Degree Days (HDD), Cooling Degree Days (CDD) and humidity with the scope to adapt the climatic area to building design requirements.

The climate classification method is reported in the ANSI/ASHRAE/IESNA Standard 90.1-2007 Normative Appendix B – Building Envelope Climate Criteria, which will be the reference climate classification to be incorporated into the 2 CAP Energy Atlas. The tables available in the following document show the climate zone classification number for a wide variety of International locations³.

²Source: <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm> . {access date : 3 May 2020}

³Source: www.built-environments.com/International_Climate_Zones.pdf . {access date : 3 May 2020}

4 Energy culture: cultural and social determinants of domestic energy demand

In general terms, the human determinants of energy demand can be considered to lie with the behaviours of the individuals concerned, and the environment they find themselves in (environmental determinism), or with the conventions, cultures and largely unwritten, codes and rules by which they live (social constructivism).

The first one, favoured for its immediate applicability, arguably minimizes and oversimplifies the variables that influence energy demand, since human experience is highly influenced also by social norms, interactions and constructions. For these reasons, according to Vischer (2008), a user-centred theory is more located in between these two extremes: subjects' behaviour is influenced by the environment but not determined by it, while being affected by other aspects like feelings, intentions, attitudes, expectations and social context.

According to Shove (2003), **occupants' actions are deeply influenced by social norms, as well as cultural and economic factors**. Thus, instead of focusing on individual actions and attitudes, the focus should be put on the transformation of collective conventions (Wilhite and Shove 1998).

While cultural and social determinants of domestic energy demand are important considerations for PEB design, they do not lend themselves well to integrated modelling of household energy demand. In fact, while social practice, cultural habits, adaptation and social norms largely explain energy end-use, we are only at the beginning of systematically cross-analysing social and cultural data with building modelling data. At this preliminary stage, selected bundles of everyday practices are juxtaposed in the implementation of a multi-layer analysis. This approach has its base in studies of technology and society, seeking to open the way to new avenues for modelling energy demand, 'beyond the usual technology and economic-based approach' (Wilhite and Shove 1998).

Cultural and social variables include a very wide range of aspects and topics, with scales spanning from household level to global, with the common factor being social and cultural structures or conventions that exist beyond individual attitudes. According to Watson et al. (2016), these include:

- **organizational cultures**, referring to organizational or institutional social order;
- **management strategies**, as the processes that control individual users and user groups;
- **social norms and practices**, referring to tacit knowledge, conventions and actions.

Contrary to an individually centred approach where users' attitudes and behaviours are juxtaposed directly with technologies and standards of comfort, using these categories holds the possibility of discerning social and cultural patterns in different populations.

After Stephenson et al. (2010), the concept of energy culture borrows from systems thinking and behavioural theories to move beyond both narrow behavioural perspectives, and overly broad systemic models. **Energy cultures are not only related to territorial and climatic characterisation of collective energy demand, but also to social values and practices among societies.** Energy cultures are not monolithic, differences are still being rooted to physical geographies and climatic conditions, as well as variations in status and social groups, material dimensions and demographic structures, indeed they include; ‘sociocultural factors that shape collective energy demand and create variations in how energy is generated, distributed, viewed, and used both within and between countries’ (Wilhite et al. 2000; Stephenson et al. 2010, 2015; Rau et al. 2019).

Energy cultures thus vary substantially within countries, as well as across geopolitical boundaries, ‘which draws attention to the need for new units of analysis ‘beyond the nation-state’ as part of new and innovative cross-national and cross-cultural comparisons in energy research’ (ENERGISE 2019).

4.1 Energy Cultures Framework (ECF)

Stephenson et al. (2010), propose methods for energy cultures research. In order to identify opportunities for behaviour change, the authors outline an **‘Energy Cultures’ conceptual framework (ECF) for the understanding of the factors that influence energy consumption attitudes.** Using a multi-disciplinary methodology based on the literature review, this culture-based approach provides a structure for addressing the problem of multiple interpretations of ‘behaviour’ by suggesting that it is influenced by the interactions between three core vectors, i.e. norms, energy practices and material culture.

FIGURE 3 - ENERGY CULTURES FRAMEWORK (2013)

The three main concepts constitute the core of the framework, but they include wider systemic contextual features. **The ECF** is meant for clustering users according to similar interacting norms, material cultures and practices, returning a population segmentation by means of reasonably distinctive energy cultures. This categorization **can then contribute to a deeper understanding of the consumer behaviour which leads to energy end-use, and thus to the identification of the most suitable and effective interventions according to user attitudes, preferences and aspirations.**

In ENERGISe (2019), this ECF is recalled. This research work aims at achieving a greater scientific understanding of the social and cultural influences on energy consumption by developing and validating options for a bottom-up transformation of energy use in households and communities across Europe. Also, in this case, the basic hypothesis is that patterns in energy use arise from social settings -e.g. communities, associations, local and regional institutions- that shape household-specific practices. As stated in ENERGISe (2019), 'it explicitly recognises the existence of distinctive, culture-specific combinations of practices adopted and shared by particular units of social organisation (e.g. households, communities, organisations, nation-states). This implies a view of cultural change as a key ingredient of successful energy sustainability transitions'. Given this, the goal is to spot cultural and social aspects that can influence measures towards energy efficiency.

In the above-mentioned document, a modified version of the ECF of Stephenson is proposed with examples, and it is reported hereafter.

Element	Examples
Material conditions	Technologies, energy infrastructure, house characteristics such as insulation, energy sources and heating devices
Attitudes, perceptions and social norms	Aspirations, expected comfort levels, environmental concern, respect for tradition, social acceptability of wasteful/resource-intensive activities
Everyday practices	The temporal and spatial dynamics of practices unfolding in the home that play a role in when and how the home is heated, as well as what rooms are heated and when (such as cooking and washing), use of appliances, use and maintenance of technologies

TABLE 1 - ENERGY CULTURES FRAMEWORK (ECF). MODIFIED VERSION - SOURCE: ENERGISe.

Building upon the definitions offered in the previous table, in this task a literature review has been conducted in order to identify the more specific drivers that influence household energy end-use and management, taking into consideration cultural and social diversities as highlighted and categorized by the Energy Cultures Framework.

4.2 Implications of cultural and social drivers

Different drivers are potentially responsible for differences in household management and energy demand. Findings have been reported in tables categorized according to the ECF as implemented in the project ENERGISE (2019).

In the proposed tables, the drivers defined are grouped according to the three core categorizations of the ECF and a definition is given for each one.

Material conditions		
Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information, etc	Income	Household size, design and construction
Driver	Definition	
Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information, etc	How technologies shift energy and associated costs, either by enabling efficiency or by enabling different energy demand patterns (more or less) through the establishment of new norms of technology-adaptive living.	
Income	Estimating how household income impacts on the adoption of specific measures and technologies	
Household size, design, construction	Impact on the energy demand and on the implementation of systems, technologies and materials.	

TABLE 2 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO MATERIAL CONDITIONS

Attitudes, perceptions and social norms			
The role of policy, regulations, laws and subsidisation	Demographic factors	Routines and habits, social conventions	Social responsibilities, time-space considerations
Driver	Definition		
The role of policy, regulations, laws and subsidisation	Policies etc. encouraging consumers to adopt measures and incentives available for households		
Demographic factors	How demographic factors at NUTS2 level impact on the household energy demand		
Routines and habits, social conventions	Social conventions across climate zones, social classes, and generations		
Social responsibilities, time-space considerations	Space and time organization in everyday life linked to socially performed activities, e.g. work management and organization affects household energy consumptions		

TABLE 3 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO ATTITUDES, PERCEPTIONS AND SOCIAL NORMS

Everyday practices					
Routines and habits	Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations	Expectations and prior experiences	Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies	Composition, relationships and interactions between household members	Temporal and spatial arrangements
Driver			Definition		
Routines and habits			Individuals' normalised (unquestioned) actions		
Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations			Space and time organization in everyday life linked to individually performed activities		
Expectations and prior experiences			Ideal conditions and lessons learnt		
Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies			Education level and skills which allows a proper understanding and an efficient use of a system or technology		
Composition, relationships and interactions between household members			Family structure, generations turnover, internal dynamics		
Temporal and spatial arrangements			Space and time organization in everyday life linked to household characteristics		

TABLE 4 - DRIVERS REFERRING TO EVERYDAY PRACTICES

4.3 Household composition and Time Geography of energy demand

Household composition

The household unit is a base unit for understanding energy demand in the residential sector. When intending to design PEBs from a user-centric approach, the wide range of households and their composition in terms of family structures needs to be accounted for, including blended and multi-generational households, etc. Many households are heterogeneous, with different members having different needs and/or different practices, with very different energy demand. Households include gendered, generational, and inter-cultural relations, to name a few. Moreover, while there are some generalisations that may be drawn across ‘types’ of households, such an approach inevitably oversimplifies household energy demand and loses resolution and detail that may be important in the design of PEBs.

Time is then an important way to understand the dynamics of energy demand in and across household members. Starting from *work-life balance*, Erickson (1997) conducted a cross-cultural ethnographic survey about the “scheduling” aspect of convenience. The author found that being “busy”, in contemporary society, was an important indicator of a successful life, and this has led during the years to a change in working schedules and in space organization to accomplish those schedules. This was confirmed in another anthropological study conducted at “Silicon Valley” in California (Knowlton 1982), where people used an inordinate amount of time in “making their busy lives manageable”. People have started to equip their homes so as to manage work, in an era of work pressure and fear of missing out. This creates pressures around high trafficked areas; bathrooms, kitchens, eating spaces, etc, and around hybrid office/leisure spaces, for

example, to (re-)arrange domestic spaces and life around multiple pressing time-sensitive tasks and practices. Associated demand for additional bathrooms to allow morning starts to include multiple working family members, etc have emerged. Thus, the idea of being busy has also become part of broader culture, giving meaning and status to household members, and placing its own constraints upon energy demand. In such ways, conventions evolve, energy-intensive ways of life become normal and energy demand becomes embedded in society (Wilhite et al. 2000).

This shift in **work-life balance has obviously led also to the redefinition of societal patterns**, in particular in the ones known by Altman et al. (1980) as **(i) organization of space** -i.e. purposes, activities, values- **(ii) organization of meaning** -i.e. social status, social identity, income, appropriate behaviour, cognitive schemata organization- **(iii) organization of communication** -social interactions, movement patterns, privacy needs- **(iv) organization of time** -i.e. time flow, future/past, rhythms of human activities. Many of these aspects can be grouped into *occasions* -i.e. who does what, with whom, when and in what context, and where.

From this perspective, observing family and societal structures among different cultures, can give deeper insights into the process by which environmentally-related and pro-environmental actions are shaped, and thus provide a more realistic model for predicting energy end use patterns at household level. These dimensions will be incorporated in the energy cultures clustering exercise referred to EU territories, as part of the 2CAP Energy Atlas.

Time geography

Hägerstrand, (1976) who developed the time-geographic approach, wrote that: 'it is very easy to dream up blue-prints for new undertakings but very hard to imagine their fate and their consequences for other legitimate processes when put into practice. Perhaps the trouble is that thought does not encounter in its own world the constraints of space and time'. **Time and space are the main grounds for several constraints on energy demand in people's everyday lives**, and 'time geography is an integrative approach to studying the coordination of human activities in society and nature. It concerns environmental problems caused by humans and aims to develop knowledge about human life that may facilitate social and ecological sustainability' (Ellegård 2017).

Time geography research offers a means to consider several household members' daily activities at the same time, recognising that the time-space context in which the activities are performed might constrain households' ability to reduce energy use. This perspective emphasises the ways in which timing, location and synchronisation between activities and individuals are drivers that enable or disable energy efficiency in people's everyday lives.

Time-geography provides a meaningful explanation for the aforementioned proliferation of bathrooms. Many other appliances, spaces and energy using technologies are

multiplied to allow dual operation for multiple individuals' benefit. The total energy demand at domestic level from housing appliances increases because of the rising numbers of devices and more frequent use, together with the individualization of appliances.

Time geography promises a better comprehension of how people decide what to do where and when, and hence, the result of energy demand. They perform activities to achieve the goals of the projects of importance to them. For doing so, they need resources and energy, and they are playing a crucial role in enabling resource, consequently, energy is not important in itself, it is important because it makes it feasible to use various systems and appliances for different purposes.

Practices take time to perform, they are developed somewhere and must be integrated with activities in several projects and adjusted to other individuals. The practices in one project must be performed in a sequence that does not hinder the achievement of other project goals. This sequencing implies that practices are performed following specific processes of actions that are meaningful to the individual. Practice sequences described and analysed at both, individual and aggregate levels, could serve to model individuals' and households' electricity use. The time-diaries contain information about:

- time of the day
- what activity was performed
- where it was performed
- with whom it was performed

Time geography uses time-diaries from research case studies and from the territorial time use statistics to provide energy use data, in relation to everyday practices, at the time that focusing on individuals and groups behavioural patterns at different territorial levels. It serves, then, to cluster the various energy cultures within different climatic areas and regions by using an empirical method, which responds to the principles of the user centric design.

FIGURE 4 - THE AGGREGATE PRACTICE PATTERN (BASED ON THE PRACTICES SEQUENCES OF ALL INDIVIDUALS) IN THE POPULATION (N=463) DURING A WEEKDAY DAY (PALM AND ELLEGÅRD 2011).

Time geography provides understanding of the influence of practice sequences and synchronization in everyday life which reveal that households are a complex matter from an energy use perspective. When considering time and timing in depth, analyses can be made of the various projects in which practices are depicted in daily life at both, individual and household levels. Time and timing ground to develop new and more precise concepts, that integrate the important aspects of synchronisation that highly influence daily life.

Research findings considering both time and timing might be helpful in designing PEBs that enable people to take their own actions in the attempt to positively balance the energy use. People need to recognize their own daily life in information, which might be elevated to managing housing systems.

“Time-use data, qualitative research and methods of sequence analysis to investigate the synchronisation of practices (with each other and at specific times), and their sequencing, and to show how temporal rhythms vary over time. The time-geographical opportunities to research projects, to visualize daily activities and discuss the constraints encountered to capture the unique and complex, intertwined everyday life activity pattern of each household. Integrating the conceptual framework developed within time geography could help to figure out how various households or clusters use energy. Household energy use is a collective rather than individualized process” (Palm and Ellegård 2011).

5 Concept for the Atlas

In this section, the concept for the Atlas is introduced as a design tool by answering the following questions: *How can the Atlas tool be conceptualised to support the PEB design process? How can user energy behaviour be integrated into an Atlas?*

FIGURE 5 – FIGURATIVE COMPOSITION OF CONCEPT FOR THE ATLAS. SOURCES: (PVSITE PROJECT 2016; CASS AND SHOVE 2017; GE2O PROJECT 2013)

The Atlas configuration is expected to contain 2 different layers of information:

FIRST LAYER.

It is based on an interconnected GIS map composed by data sets related to the EU building sector, defined by the following tasks: (i) “National and local regulatory frame and boundary conditions for PEBs”; (ii) “Culture and climate as variables in energy use in domestic buildings”. When filtering various layers simultaneously, new aggregated information will appear once a more compressive understanding of energy factors affecting PEB design is achieved, as well as enabling to identify specific regions by their cultural and climatic characterisation.

Graphics will be automatically generated and shown when filtering and selecting specific territory, it will be an intermediary space among the first and the second levels of information. These graphics will serve as a precursor to the 2nd layer, which will further develop the socio-technical analysis on different energy cultures and climatic territories based on this graphical filtering.

Energy consumption variables consider a breakdown of data by type of domestic service in the residential sector. Aiming at complementing the meta-analysis of the literature review, these variables will support the characterisation of the different households' patterns of energy demand in each climate area

1. Space Heating
 2. Space Cooling
 3. Water Heating
 4. Lighting and appliances
 5. Cooking
- 1st Level of accuracy. Data from occupied High-Performance Residential Buildings, the information required is:
 - Geographical area: Mainly, referring to the demo territories (Norway, France, Germany and Italy)
 - Units: The figure on the data sheet will be expressed by %.
 - The need to provide the average energy consumption of a household unit within High-Performance Buildings on a yearly basis.
 - Further information: (i) energy consumption in both cooling and heating seasons and (ii) daylight and night energy consumption schemes.
 - 2nd Level of accuracy. NUTS2 is the expected level of detailed information extended to EU territories, the information required is:
 - Geographical area: All European territories.
 - Building typology: EU residential building stock
 - Units: The figure on the data sheet will be expressed by %.
 - The need to provide the average energy consumption of a household unit, without building typology distinction.
 - Further information: (i) energy consumption in both cooling and heating seasons and (ii) daylight and night energy consumption schemes.

Climatic variables

1. Heating Degree days
2. Cooling Degree Days
3. Avg. solar irradiation during daylight over per year
4. Avg. ambient temperature per year
5. Avg. ambient temperature over the heating season
6. Avg. ambient temperature over the cooling season

7. Maximum ambient temperature per year

Socio-economic variables

1. Population density NUTS2
2. Gross domestic product of the area from the last census
3. Disposable income of households
4. Electricity consumption of households
5. Gas consumption of households
6. Total energy consumption in the residential sector per country
7. Gas prices per household consumer
8. Electricity prices per household consumer

SECOND LAYER

It is defined by the analysis of energy demand patterns from the lens of ‘everyday practices’, ‘rules’, ‘demographics and social norms’ and ‘material conditions’ referring to each territory and climate area defined previously. This text and graphical material will aim at indicating general trends to inform the future design of PEBs. It intends to provide insights to enable designers to configure a positive balance on the building’s energy performance, supporting the dimension of renewable energy and storage systems according to a tailored energy demand of households in their daily practices.

The following table shows how the different data variables of the 2CAP Energy Atlas relate to each cultural and social driver as outlined in section 5.2. The 2nd Layer of the Atlas will be based on the analysis and interrelation of this data and drivers framed in the different territories, aiming to characterise the various energy culture clusters within the 4 climatic zones at EU level.

		Material conditions			Attitudes, perceptions and social norms				Everyday practices						
		Technologies, operability, availability of real-time information, etc	Income	Household size, design and construction	The role of policy, regulations, laws and subsidisation	Demographic factors	Routines and habits, social conventions	Social responsibilities, time-space considerations	Personal views, values and convictions	Routines and habits	Individual responsibilities, time-space considerations	Expectations and prior experiences	Knowledge of energy use, skills in using technologies	Composition, relationships and interactions between household members	Temporal and spatial arrangements
Energy consumption in households	Space Heating / Space Cooling / Water Heating / Lighting and appliances / Cooking	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Climatic Variables	1) Heating Degree days	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓		✓	✓		
	2) Cooling Degree Days	✓		✓	✓				✓	✓		✓	✓		
	3) Avg. solar irradiation during daylight over year	✓		✓	✓			✓				✓	✓		
	4) Avg. ambient temperature over year	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓		✓
	5) Avg. ambient temperature over heating season	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	6) Avg. ambient temperature over cooling season	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
	7) Maximum ambient temperature over year	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓
Socio-economic Variables	1) Population density NUTS2		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓		✓	
	2) Gross domestic product of the area last census	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
	3) Disposable income of households	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	4) Electricity consumption of households	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	5) Gas consumption of households	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	6) Final energy consumption in household sector per country:	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	7) Gas prices for household consumer	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓	
	8) Electricity prices for household consumer	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓	

TABLE 5 - 2CAP ENERGY ATLAS - DATA VARIABLES CATEGORISED BY SOCIO-CULTURAL DRIVERS WITHIN THE ECF

6 Data sets for building the 2CAP Energy Atlas

The EU Building Stock Observatory (BSO)

BSO was established in 2016 as part of the Clean energy for all Europeans package and aims to provide a better understanding of the energy performance of the building sector through reliable, consistent and comparable data.

FIGURE 6 - EU BUILDING STOCK OBSERVATORY

The BSO contains a database, a data mapper and factsheets for monitoring the energy performance of buildings across Europe. It covers a broad range of energy related topics and provide information on the building stock, energy consumption, building elements and technical building systems installed, energy performance certificates, nearly zero-energy buildings and renovation rates, but also areas like energy poverty and financing aspects⁴

The database. There are 250 indicators feeding into the BSO database. The indicators are organised according to ten thematic areas:

- building stock characteristics
- building shell performance
- technical building systems
- nearly Zero-Energy Buildings
- building renovation
- energy consumption
- certification
- financing
- energy poverty
- energy market

⁴ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-of-buildings/eu-bso> [access date : 2 May 2020]

Every set of data can be viewed per topic, year and country, or the EU as a whole. Once you have selected the indicators, the data is presented in summary tables and graphs, with references to every data source.

The sources come from Eurostat, the European Commission's Joint Research Centre, EU funded projects, data from national and official statistics in the EU countries, databases on energy performance certificates and data from market providers, among others.

Among the data set which will be displayed in the 2CAP Energy Atlas, it will include data on building technologies from the EU building stock observatory database. Aiming at integrating indicators about most applied technologies for heating, cooling and ventilation in each country, e.g. as part of HARP Project, Marchetti (2019) developed a complete report on heating appliances installed in EU homes, backing up on detailed data from BSO among the sources of information. It provides statistics for the countries involved in the HARP project⁵.

IEA Energy Efficiency Indicators 2019

This statistical report is designed to help understand what drives final energy use in IEA member countries in order to improve and track national energy efficiency policies. This is the fourth edition of a comprehensive selection of data that the IEA has been collecting each year, after its members recognised in 2009 the need to better monitor energy efficiency policies. This year, the report continues to progressively expand its scope to countries beyond IEA. It includes country-specific analysis of end uses across the largest sectors – residential, services, industry and transport.

⁵Source : https://heating-retrofit.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/HARP_D2.2_Building-vs-heating-stock-matrix-V1.2.pdf [access date : 2 May 2020]

FIGURE 7 - FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY END USE. BREAKDOWN OF FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION FOR IEA MEMBERS IN 2017 ⁶

Eurostat – Energy Consumption in Households 2017

Energy consumption in households by type of end-use. In the EU, the main use of energy by households is for heating their homes (64.1% of final energy consumption in the residential sector). Electricity used for lighting and most electrical appliances represents 14.4% (this excludes the use of electricity for powering the main heating, cooling or cooking systems), while the proportion used for water heating is slightly higher, representing 14.8%. Main cooking devices require 5.6% of the energy used by households, while space cooling and other end-uses cover 0.3% and 0.9% respectively. The heating of space and water consequently represents 78.9 % of the final energy consumed by households.

FIGURE 8 - EUROSTAT - ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND USE BY HOUSEHOLDS 2017⁷

⁶ IEA (2019), Energy Efficiency Indicators 2019, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-efficiency-indicators-2019> [access date : 2 May 2020]

⁷ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Energy_consumption_in_households#Context [access date : 2 May 2020]

The Odyssee-Mure project

The Odyssee-Mure project is co-ordinated by ADEME with the technical support of Enerdata and Fraunhofer. It is supported by H2020 programme of the European Commission and is part of the activity of the EnR Club.

Odyssee and Mure databases. The project relies on two complementary internet databases, that are regularly updated by the network of national teams (once to twice a year):

- Odyssee, managed by Enerdata, that contains detailed energy efficiency and CO₂-indicators with data on energy consumption, their drivers (activity indicators) and their related CO₂-emissions.
- Mure, coordinated by Fraunhofer-ISI with the technical support of Enerdata, that contains a description, with their impact evaluation whenever available, of all energy efficiency measures implemented at EU or national level. Mure was initially developed by ISINNOVA.

Objectives: The general objective of the project is to provide a comprehensive monitoring of energy consumption and efficiency trends as well as an evaluation of energy efficiency policy measures by sector for EU countries and Norway:

- Evaluate and compare energy efficiency progress by sector and relate this progress to the observed trends in energy consumption.
- Contribute to the evaluation of national energy efficiency policy measures and analyse their dynamics of implementation.
- To provide results in an interactive and attractive way to decision makers and actors involved in energy efficiency, the project has developed specific data and policy tools. The originality of the project is to cover all sectors and end-uses with a homogeneous and harmonised approach and to provide an overall picture of the trends and measures by sector.

Comprehensive monitoring of efficiency trends and policy evaluation in EU countries, Norway, Serbia and Switzerland.

FIGURE 9 - COUNTRY PROFILES WITHIN ODYSSEE-MURE PROJECT⁸

European Environment Agency

The European Environment Agency (EEA) is an agency of the European Union, whose task is to provide sound, independent information on the environment. The EEA aims to support sustainable development by helping to achieve significant and measurable improvement in Europe's environment, through the provision of timely, targeted, relevant and reliable information to policymaking agents and the public.

E.g. Observed trend in heating and cooling degree days (1981-2017)

These maps show observed linear trends in heating degree days (left) and cooling degree days (right) over 1981–2017 for all EEA member and cooperating countries, with a baseline temperature for HDDs and CDDs are 15.5 °C and 22 °C, respectively.

⁸ Source: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/> [access date : 2 May 2020]

FIGURE 10 - OBSERVED TREND IN HEATING AND COOLING DEGREE DAYS (1981-2017) ⁹

⁹ Source: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/figures/trend-in-heating-and-cooling-1> [access date : 2 May 2020]

7 Understanding culture and climate variables on energy demand at households' level

Elements for Climate and cultural differences in energy use in domestic buildings.

7.1 Sub-arctic climate

7.1.1 Energy consumption in households

7.1.1.1 Data from monitored high-efficiency buildings

Zero energy buildings at Skarpnes¹⁰ - 'A pilot in the Research Centre on Zero Emission Building (ZEB)' (Sørensen 2017)

Five detached family houses were designed as zero energy houses in a pilot project within the Research Centre on Zero Emission Building. These houses were built between 2014 and 2015, and are located in the southern part of Norway, in Skarpnes (Arendal). The size of each house is 154 m², distributed over two floors. Built after the passive house standard, NS 3700.

Building characteristics:

- U-value External wall: 0.12 W/m²K
- U-value Roof: 0.08 W/m²K
- U-value Floor on ground: 0.09 W/m²K
- U-value Windows and doors: < 0.8 W/m²K
- Normalized thermal bridge value: 0.03 W/m²K
- Air tightness: 0.6 air changes per hour (at 50Pa)
- Specific Fan Power: 1.5 kW/m³/s
- Mechanical ventilation with heat recovery: 86 %
- Low temperature water-based floor heating
- Main heat source: ground source heat pump COP = 4,2-5,4. Energy production: PV-panels

As shown in Figure 11, Space heating is the largest share of energy consumption during winter, while the consumption for DHW is almost constant over the year. Results from the study show that measured energy is on average 35% higher than calculated.

¹⁰Source: <https://www.zeb.no/index.php/en/conference/item/814-5-zero-energy-dwellings-at-skarpnes-arendal> [access date: 9 May 2020]

FIGURE 11 - MONITORED VS. CALCULATED ENERGY USE AT SKARPNES, ZEB, PICTURE FROM PRESENTATION BY STEINAR GRYNNING, ÅSE L. SØRENSEN, JUDITH THOMSEN, LARS GULLBREKKEN

Risvollan housing cooperative

In two studies, monitored heat and electricity in the Risvollan housing cooperative is analysed (Sørensen et al 2019a; Sørensen et al 2019b). Risvollan is located in Trondheim, Norway, and was built in the 1970s. There are a total of 1058 apartments distributed over 121 apartment blocks. Space heating and domestic hot water is provided by district heating. The main part of the apartments has electric under-floor heating in the bathrooms. The Risvollan housing cooperative is also a case for the Research Centre on Zero Emission Neighbourhoods in Smart Cities (FME ZEN).

For the year 2018 the delivered energy outcomes at Risvollan were:

- Average specific electricity delivered: 56,7 kWh/m² heated floor area.
- The apartments used 87 % of the electricity, with an electricity consumption of 49,2 kWh/m²
- Average specific heat delivered: 139 kWh/m² heated floor area.
- The total delivered energy to the housing corporation is 196 kWh/m², this also includes common areas and garages.
- Heating (space heating and DHW) contributes to a share of 70 % of the total delivered energy.
- The monitored heating demand in Risvollan buildings is high compared to low energy buildings.
- In the EBLE Project (Evaluation of residential buildings with low energy demand) (Thomsen et al. 2017), delivered energy for space heating and DHW was monitored. Space heating measured for 20 passive houses was between 23 to 58 kWh/m². DHW for 24 passive houses was measured between 18 to 42 kWh/m².

7.1.1.2 Average data at national level

Statistics Norway (SSB) provides available data for energy consumption in Norwegian households. SSB is the national statistical institute of Norway and the main producer of official statistics. The latest official statistic for energy consumption in Norwegian households is from 2012.

Figure 12 shows the distribution of energy consumption per energy carrier split by type of dwelling and by region¹¹.

FIGURE 12 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN HOUSEHOLDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS, 2012, SSB

In Norway the heating demand is mainly covered by electricity. In 2012, 73 % of households covered their heating demand with electricity. 27 % of households had installed a heat pump. Average energy consumption per household was 20 230 kWh, but as shown in Figure 13 there are regional differences. The differences in energy consumption can partly be explained by the composition of residential buildings in the different regions. Areas with a larger share of single-family houses will have a higher energy consumption than areas with a larger share of multifamily houses, such as Oslo. In 2019, single-family houses accounted for 50 % of the residential building stock.

In the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE) historical data of energy use for households is available from 1990 to 2018, including predictions for 2030 and 2040¹².

According to the NVE’s analysis (Figure 13), 67 % of the energy use is for space heating. Electronic equipment is the second largest post with 15 %, 13 % goes to domestic hot water and 5 % is for lighting. It is expected that the share for room heating will be reduced as the building stock becomes more energy efficient.

¹¹Source: <https://www.ssb.no/en/energi-og-industri/statistikker/husenergi/hvert-3-aar/2014-07-14> [access date: 05.2020]

¹² Source: <https://www.nve.no/energibruk-effektivisering-og-teknologier/energibruk/energibruk-i-bygg/?ref=mainmenu> [access date: 05.2020]

FIGURE 13 - TYPE OF END-USE ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN HOUSEHOLDS, NVE

Figure 14 shows the development in energy consumption from 1990 to 2018 and predicted energy consumption for 2030 and 2040. The predicted reduction for 2030 and 2040 is based on an expectation that buildings, electronic equipment and lighting will be more energy efficient, besides having a warmer climate. Likewise, an increasing use of electrical vehicles will lead to a higher electricity consumption. After 2010 the total energy use has been stable at approximately 48 TWh. The main energy source has historically been electricity, and this is also expected to be the main source in the future scenarios.

FIGURE 14 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION AND TYPE OF ENERGY SOURCE IN HOUSEHOLDS, HISTORICAL AND PREDICTED, NVE

The data from Eurostat is based on data collected from the European Commission, EU funded projects and data received from national statistics. Figure 15 and Table 6 show the data available of the Norwegian residential sector from year 2017. It includes: the share of fuels for final energy consumption, the share of fuel for space heating and water heating and the share of final energy consumption by type of end-use. Figure 15 shows the share of final energy consumption split by type of end-use. Compared to the data from NVE, space heating has a smaller share in the data from Eurostat, but it is still the largest share.

FIGURE 15 - SHARE OF FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY TYPE OF END-USE, EUROSTAT

	Electricity	Derived heat	Gas	Solid fuels	Oil & Petroleum products	Renewables and wastes
Final energy consumption (%)	83.3	2.7	0.2	0	1.6	12.2
Space heating, 2017 (%)	63.1	4.9	0.4	0	3.7	28
Water heating, 2017 (%)	96.2	3.8	0	0	0	0

TABLE 6 - SHARE OF FUELS IN THE FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN THE RESIDENTIAL SECTOR, 2017, NORWAY, EUROSTAT

7.1.1.3 Trends

Odysee-MURE¹³

FIGURE 16 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF RESIDENTIAL PER M2 AND YEAR, ODYSSEE-MURE

FIGURE 17 – MAIN DRIVERS OF THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION VARIATION IN HOUSEHOLDS, ODYSSEE-MURE

¹³ Source: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/norway.html> [access date: 9 May 2020]

7.1.2 Socio-economic factors

Norway Statistics (2018 and 2019)

- Population (2019): 5 367 580
- Unemployment rate (2019): 3,8 %
- GDP per inhabitant (2018, EU28=100): 151

Eurostat (2011)¹⁴:

- Employment rate (persons aged 20-64): 78,7 %
- Unemployment rate (persons aged 15-64): 1,9 %
- Share of dwellings built after 2000: 12,7 %

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Oslo og Akershus	213.5	216.2	220.6	224.7	229.3	235.8	239.8	244	248.2	249	252.5	255.9
Hedmark og Oppland	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.6	7.6	7.6	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.6	7.7	7.7
Vestlandet	17.3	17.5	17.7	17.9	18.1	18.4	18.6	18.8	19	18.9	19	19
Trøndelag	10.6	10.7	10.8	10.9	11.1	11.2	11.4	11.5	11.6	11.5	11.7	11.8
Nord-Norge	4.3	4.3	4.3	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.5

TABLE 7 - POPULATION DENSITY - NORWAY (PERSON PER KM2) ¹⁵

7.1.3 Climatic factors

Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS)¹⁶

The PVGIS shows the information available from Norway and the Subarctic climate area. PVGIS provides free and open access to:

- PV potential for different technologies, grid-connected and stand-alone systems.
- Solar radiation and temperature, as monthly averages or daily profiles.
- Full-time series of hourly values of both solar radiation and PV performance.

¹⁴ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistical-atlas/gis/viewer/?config=census.json&ch=9,16&mids=2,17,CNTOVL&o=1,0,7,0,7¢er=60,32922,12,49693,5&ics=17&> [access date: 3 May 2020]

¹⁵ Source: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=demo_r_d3dens&lang=en [access date: 4 May 2020]

¹⁶ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/pvgis> [access date: 4 May 2020]

- Annual Typical Meteorological data for nine climatic variables.
- Maps, by country or region, of solar resource and PV potential ready to print.
- The PVMAPS software includes all the estimation models used in the PVGIS.

FIGURE 18 - TOOL INCLUDED IN THE PVGIS PLATFORM (LAST UPDATE 15/10/2019)

ENERGYPLUS, Climatic data for Europe ¹⁷:

A summary of data can be found in the accessible files (.stat file) such as:

- Monthly Solar Irradiance Wh/m²
- Monthly Drybulb and Mean Coincident Wetbulb Temperatures °C
- Heating/Cooling Degree Days/Hours
- Relative Humidity %
- Average Temperature for typical and extreme summer/ winter/ autumn / spring
- Min. and max. temperature over the year

¹⁷ Sources :

<https://energyplus.net/weather/simulation> [access date: 4 May 2020]

https://energyplus.net/sites/all/modules/custom/weather/weather_files/whichweatherdatashouldyouuseforenergysimulations.pdf [access date : 4 May 2020]

https://energyplus.net/weather-region/europe_wmo_region_6 [access date: 4 May 2020]

There are several climatic files available in the following sources: Climate one building¹⁸ and the Norwegian Meteorological institute¹⁹

7.1.4 Literature review

Based on the topics and themes studied in the present deliverable, a literature review process has been conducted for the sub-arctic climate, such as indoor temperature preferences, the oversupply of heat or the control of indoor climate management systems.

Indoor temperature preferences

According to Thomsen et al. (2017), the preferred living room temperature for the residents they interviewed was between 22 to 24 °C (except for one). These are higher temperatures than used as a basis for energy calculations according to current standards. There is also a general preference to lower temperatures in bedrooms, the preferred temperature is between 15 and 19 °C. This proves that it is a challenge to manage different temperatures between various rooms in households. Window airing is used to lower the temperature, especially in the bedroom and during the summer season.

Overheating is perceived as less of a problem if it occurs in short periods during the summer. However, it can be perceived as troublesome, especially when it comes to the bedroom. The measurements and interviews show that the use of exterior window shading to facilitate aeration of the dwelling reduces the risk of excessively high temperatures in summer. The Mechanical Ventilation with Heat Recovery (MVHR) was not meant for cooling, as this is not expected to be necessary in a Norwegian climate. It is up to each resident to install sun shading themselves.

Many more studies on residential passive houses with MVHR indicate that bedrooms are perceived as too warm even in winter, which may explain the substantial extent of window ventilation observed in some passive houses during the heating season.

¹⁸Source: http://climate.onebuilding.org/WMO_Region_6_Europe/NOR_Norway/index.html [access date: 9 May 2020]

¹⁹Sources :
http://sharki.oslo.dnmi.no/portal/page?_pageid=73_39035,73_39049&_dad=portal&_schema=PORTAL&6009_BAT_CHORDER_3197941 [access date: 9 May 2020]

<https://seklima.met.no/observations/> [access date: 9 May 2020]

Preferred lower bedroom temperatures seem to be more difficult to achieve in high-performance buildings with MVHR, even at low outdoor temperatures during winter. Berge & Mathisen (2016) found an extensive use of window ventilation in bedrooms. It appears to be mainly driven by the desire for lower bedroom temperatures, and probably not for increasing the fresh air supply.

These findings are consistent with a study conducted by Georges & al. (2016). Several informants complained about warm bedrooms. Many Norwegians prefer cold bedrooms (below 16 ° C). They cannot achieve this without opening the windows, even though they keep internal doors closed all day. Unfortunately, this way of regulating bedroom temperature has major consequences for room-heating in the entire home.

In the majority of a selection of European case studies (Thomsem et al. 2011), concerns were expressed about thermal comfort. Informants often experienced the building as too hot in the summer and/or too cold in the winter. This perceived discomfort caused different types of personal actions, which had a potential to interfere with the concept and the calculated energy balance. In order to improve internal conditions, the users in almost every case intervened with the planned use. They found common and known ways of improving their comfort levels in the buildings without considering how to optimize the new system. None of the respondents had much prior knowledge of energy efficient buildings before moving in or starting to work in the case study buildings. They did not know what to expect from their new environment and were unfamiliar with the concepts. Many of the informants complained about the lack of information on systems and insufficient training. The studies also show that the occupants preferred to control at least some operational aspects.

Perceived indoor air quality

An overview of existing user evaluations of energy-efficient buildings shows that they are often higher rated than conventional buildings in regard to indoor climate, however, users can also have specific concerns (Lappegard Hauge et al. 2011). The varying results from the user evaluations reflect differences in the quality of buildings. Complaints may also be a result of improper use.

Lappegard Hauge et al (2011) identified three important areas for further research on user evaluations, which still seems to be valid:

- There is a shortage of research that considers the social context for evaluation; the social environment, the process of moving into an energy-efficient building and prior knowledge of environmental issues influence evaluation of the buildings.
- Energy-efficient buildings may also require specific architectural solutions and further research should consider architectural and aesthetic aspects in the evaluation.

- Research on the use and operation of energy-efficient buildings is increasing, but there is still a gap, particularly in relation to the different ways of providing information and training in operation and use.

In another more recent study (Thomsem et al. 2017) it was found that most of the residents were satisfied with the air supply and air quality. However, during the winter season some residents found that the air was too dry. The low relative humidity of the indoor air during winter season was confirmed by the monitoring results. Low relative humidity and perceived dry air during the winter season is a general problem indoors. This is caused by high air change rates in combination with low humidity contribution from interior activities.

Oversupply of heat

Fresh air and heat in residential buildings have traditionally been controlled and supplied separately in each room by opening windows and regulating local heat emitters, such as radiators or floor heating. In super-insulated and airtight residential buildings, such as buildings with passive house (PH) standard, an outdoor air system with mechanical exhaust and supply ventilation with heat recovery (MVHR) is used for the provision of fresh air. Therefore, the need for window ventilation during the heating season is supposed to be significantly reduced or even eliminated. Recent studies show that this is not the case and that systematic airing to reduce bedroom temperature can affect energy use in the wrong direction (Berge et al. 2016; Berge and Mathisen 2016).

In such buildings, the space-heating (SH) distribution system can be simplified because there is no heat-emitter in each room, or by each window. Investigations point out the need for more knowledge to support the simplification of the SH distribution system.

Georges et al. (2016) have especially focused on apartment buildings heated with a reduced number of radiators. Their contribution aims at comparing the balance between energy efficiency, thermal comfort and user satisfaction using simplified SH distribution. For this purpose, two flats built according to the Norwegian PH standard have been investigated using building simulations, field measurements and occupant interviews. With a simplified distribution, one may suspect that occupants experience the thermal environment of rooms without heat emitters as too cold, typically bedrooms. On the contrary, the super-insulation and the high-efficiency heat recovery prevent significant temperature zoning from taking place between rooms. Even though the SH distribution is simplified, residents complain about the bedroom temperature which is too warm if they do not open windows.

According to Georges et al. (2016), this way of controlling indoor temperature has a strong adverse influence on space-heating needs. Another limitation is the time needed to heat a bedroom only using internal door opening. It takes several hours to adjust to a

higher set-point temperature; an aspect that can be critical if the bedroom temperature should be changed between daytime and night-time.

Berge et al. (2016) have studied the thermal conditions during winter in highly insulated dwellings with mechanical ventilation with heat recovery (MVHR). Previous observations indicate an oversupply of heat to bedrooms and a successive extensive window ventilation, which leads to an increased space-heating demand. Various MVHR solutions and control strategies, as well as building design solutions, were investigated regarding their impact on the thermal conditions in bedrooms and on the space-heating demand.

The results illustrate that the supply-air temperature and the temperatures in the living room and bathroom have significant effects on the thermal conditions in the bedrooms. A one-zone MVHR solution, with approximately the same supply-air temperature to all rooms, has clear limitations regarding the provision of thermal comfort in bedrooms.

With a two-zone MVHR solution, the supply-air temperature to the bedrooms being controlled independently from other rooms, thermal conditions in bedrooms can be improved and the space-heating demand reduced.

Berge and Mathisen (2016) conducted a post-occupancy evaluation (POE), consisting of a user survey and long-term measurements, in a high-performance residential project in Norway. The results support earlier indications that the indoor climate in high-performance residential buildings with MVHR is improved, compared to other building standards. However, the findings clearly demonstrate a need for temperature zoning in residential buildings. The preferred lower bedroom temperatures appear to be difficult to achieve in high-performance residential buildings with MVHR. An important factor that influences bedroom temperatures was found to be the control strategy for the supply air temperature, where a potential for improvement was observed.

The implementation of mechanical ventilation systems with heat recovery (MVHR) in new high-performance residential buildings constitutes a fundamental change from traditional heating and ventilation strategies. A MVHR with one ventilation zone, which is commonly used in new residential buildings, will supply approximately the same temperature to all rooms and consequently contribute to balancing the room temperatures within the dwelling. This adjustment affects air change rates, the air distribution between rooms and temperatures, and consequently calls for an evaluation of the impact on the perceived and actual indoor climate and to what degree the desired indoor climate conditions are provided.

Control of the indoor climate/Management systems

According to Thomsen et al. (2011), residents need easily accessible information about control, regulation and maintenance of the technical installations, especially for innovative and unfamiliar solutions. Dissemination of information and follow-up was seldom well taken care of in the projects they investigated.

Berge and Mathisen (2016) suggest introducing demands regarding controllability of bedroom temperatures, which enables the occupants to adjust the bedroom temperature within a feasible range independently from other rooms in a dwelling.

Gøransson (2014) has studied central management systems in households, "what management systems do, should do and will do in the future" based on the manufacturer's and the end-user's opinions.

Korsnes et al. (2016) have investigated how residents interact with a high performance zero emission building in the ZEB living lab. The degree of automation of the building's environmental services (such as heating, cooling, ventilation, and light) has been left open to test different control scenarios: manual, automatic and several modes combining both approaches.

In the first wave of qualitative experiments conducted in the laboratory between September 2015 and March 2016, six different groups were invited to live in the house for 25 days each. During this time, the script - i.e. the programs controlling the building according to ideal indoor environmental and energetic conditions - is kept as stable as possible. At the same time a user override is provided where applicable. Based on direct observation (mainly through sensors registering temperature, humidity, CO2 levels, light levels, presence, energy use, and airing) and interviews before, during and after the stay, compliance and deviation from the script have been registered and analysed along the dimensions of skill, meanings and technology.

The goal of this analysis has been twofold: 1) to provide a detailed account of which expected or unexpected occupant actions matter and in which way they impact on the energy consumption outcomes of a high performance zero emission building, 2) revisiting concepts like *scripts and anti-programs* (e.g. Akrich 1992; Latour 1992), *domestication* (e.g. Silverstone & Hirsch 1992; Sørensen 2006), and *social practice* (e.g. Schatzki et al. 2001; Reckwitz 2002) and exploring how they can explain occupants' interactions with automated domestic environments.

Media attention

Energy efficient buildings have become the norm for new buildings. However, there is still a need for increased knowledge regarding the interaction between the user and the perceived and preferred indoor climate conditions in the different rooms in high-performance housing. Any improvement and innovation in this type of housing can

stimulate interest and receive media attention. Public interest appears to be a good opportunity to spread knowledge and experiences (Hauge et al, 2011).

Search on online data bases

Several relevant reports or articles were found on the Research Centre on Zero Emission Buildings (ZEB) website²⁰.

1. **Methods for investigation:** Post-occupancy evaluations (POE) can provide valuable knowledge about residents' perception and preferences regarding indoor climate. Combining measurements of specific parameters (for example indoor climate parameters, energy use and window opening periods) and user surveys (in order to evaluate perceived indoor climate and habits) gives an important basis for understanding the user perspective and developing new solutions. The number of studies looking at the interaction between the occupants' behaviour and the energy consumption seems to increase. They are both multidisciplinary. Thomsen et al. (2011) evaluated the interplay of buildings and users in seven European case studies. The evaluation should be regarded as a starting point for an exploration of the interactions between users and buildings with low energy consumption. The objective was to improve our understanding of the dynamics between energy efficient buildings and their users. The focus of these case studies has mainly been on the use, operation, indoor environmental comfort and the social and cultural context of the buildings. Which user actions and attitudes may influence building performance and how are user actions and attitudes influenced by the buildings?
2. **Interviews and web-based questionnaires:** The most common methods to study preferences related to air quality and thermal comfort and interaction between users and the installations seem to be qualitative interviews performed with a selection of residents and web-based questionnaires/surveys with residents in selected residential areas. The Örebro model (Andersson et al. 1998) is widely used in Scandinavia to map perceptions, complaints and symptoms related to the indoor climate. Recent studies combine it with additional questions regarding user attitudes, user behaviour and occupant satisfaction, particularly regarding the heating and ventilation system and the perceived indoor climate in the various rooms (Berge and Mathisen 2106).
3. **Living Lab:** ZEB has gone a step further and has built a multipurpose experimental facility, a living laboratory. It is a detached single-family home that is planned to reach a zero-emission balance during its lifetime. It is occupied by people using the building as their home. The focus is on the occupants and their use of innovative building technologies like intelligent control of installations and equipment,

²⁰ The main objective of ZEB (<https://www.zeb.no/index.php/en/>) is to develop competitive products and solutions for existing and new buildings that will lead to innovation and implementation within the field of energy efficient zero-emission buildings. ZEB is multidisciplinary; researchers within the fields of architecture, social science, materials science, building technologies, energy technologies, and indoor climate jointly study the interaction between the physical environment and the users.

interactive user interfaces and interplay with the energy system. Living Lab is used to study various technologies and design strategies in a real-world living environment:

- User centred development of new and innovative solutions, focusing on user needs and experiences.
- Performance testing of new and existing solutions within a context of realistic usage scenarios.
- Detailed monitoring of the building and its installations as well as the users' influence on them.

Requirements in the regulations (TEK17) *Termisk inneklima*/ Thermal indoor climate

- (1) Thermal indoor climate in rooms for permanent use²¹ shall be organized in the interests of health and satisfactory comfort for their intended use.
- (2) At least one window or one door shall be open to the open air and to outdoor air in a room for permanent use.

Recommendations to 1): When heating is required it is recommended that, as far as possible, the air temperature is kept below 22 ° C. Air temperature should be adapted to the room's function and use, and opportunities for *individual control possibilities* should be sought.

When outdoor temperatures are high, it is difficult to avoid indoor temperatures exceeding the recommended values. Exceeding the highest limit should therefore be acceptable during hot summer periods with outdoor air temperature above that exceeded by 50 hours in a normal year (see meteorological statistics for maximum temperatures). Passive measures that can help to avoid overheating are, for example:

- reduced window area in sun-exposed facades
- exposed thermal mass
- exterior sun screening
- openable windows that allow for ventilation
- location of air intake / design of ventilation systems so that temperature rise in the system due to high outdoor temperature is minimal (<2 ° C).

For residential buildings without installed cooling, higher indoor temperatures should be acceptable for short periods. This is because residential buildings have a usage pattern that gives the user greater personal influence and the ability to adapt to high indoor temperatures, e.g. by lighter clothing and ventilation in the residence zone.

Recommendations to 2): By choosing windows that can be opened, the room can be ventilated when the ventilation or temperature control system should fail. Windows that

²¹ Rooms for "permanent use" in the dwelling are the living room and corresponding rooms, kitchen and bedrooms.

can be opened to the outside air offer good opportunities for quick ventilation, for example when cooking and washing.

7.1.5 Considerations

Some relevant socio-technical elements from the Subarctic climate, e.g. Norway as CULTURAL-E demo case, could be summarised as follows:

Data from monitored buildings	Data at National Level	Socio-economic factors	Indoor preferences	Technology preferences
In NZEB projects measured, energy is higher than calculated, e.g. referred project had an average of 35 % over the expected results.	Share of final energy consumption, Eurostat, (2017), by type of end-use: - Space heating – 44% - Lighting and appliances – 37% - Water heating – 14% - Other end-uses – 5%	- Population 2019: 5,367,580 inhab. - Unemployment rate 2019: 3.8 % - GDP per inhabitant (2018, EU28=100): 151	Living room temp. for the residents interviewed, was between 22 to 24 °C	- MVHR in NZEBs constitutes a fundamental change from traditional heating and ventilation strategies in Norway - MVHR in NZEBs do not satisfy thermal comfort expectations in bedrooms.
- Average heat delivered: 139 kWh/m ² heated floor area. - The total delivered energy is 196 kWh/m ² , this also includes common areas.	Development in energy consumption from 1990 to 2018, and predicted energy consumption for 2030 and 2040 in households for 2030 and 2040: - Space heating – 67% - Water Heating – 15% - Lighting – 5% - Electrical equipment – 15%	Population Density 2018: - Oslo og Akershus: 255.9 inhab. - Hedmark og Oppland: 7.7 inhab. - Vestlandet: 19 inhab. - Trøndelag: 11.8 inhab. - Nord-Norge: 4.5 inhab.	- The preferred bedroom temp. was 15 to 19 °. Bedroom - Overheating problems in NZEBs.	- Installation of external sun shading is not a common practice. - Accessible information about control, regulation and maintenance of the technical installations, especially for innovative and unfamiliar solutions.

7.2 Oceanic climate

7.2.1 Energy consumption in households

7.2.1.1 Data from monitored high-efficiency buildings

CaveZero Project²²

Detailed sheets are available for the 13 experimental buildings within the project and six of them are located in the oceanic climate.

FIGURE 19: EXAMPLE OF A DETAILED SHEET OF CAVEZERO PROJECT

²² Source: <https://cavezero.eu/cases-2/> [access date: 5 May 2020]

PowerHouseEurope Project²³

This project aimed at boosting the number of nearly-Zero Energy homes across the UE by “sharing ideas and expertise between Public, Cooperative and Social Housing professionals”. There are 150 projects across Europe, approximately a third located in oceanic climate and 11 projects in France.

</p>		

FIGURE 20 - INFORMATION AVAILABLE BY PROJECTS POWERHOUSEEUROPE

²³Source: http://www.powerhouseeurope.eu/nc/cases_resources/case_studies/list_view/ [access date: 5 May 2020]

COMEPOS Project²⁴

This is a French project focused on showing the feasibility of PEH on the whole territory. There are 17 projects, but construction work is still in progress with housing companies: the results on the monitoring of the houses are not currently authorized for dissemination.

FIGURE 21 - COMEPOS WEB-PAGE AND LOCATION OF DEMO HOUSES

²⁴Source: http://www.powerhouseeurope.eu/nc/cases_resources/case_studies/list_view/ [access date: 6 May 2020]

AZEB project²⁵

AZEB is a European project which aim is to show that a PEH project can be affordable and a methodology has been developed within the project framework to ensure this. Several demo cases are studied in the project.

FIGURE 22 - AZEB WEB-PAGE AND DEMO HOUSES

²⁵ Source: <https://azeb.eu/cases/> [access date: 6 May 2020]

BBC Observatory "The Low Consumption Buildings Observatory"²⁶

Almost 300 high-performance buildings were referenced. In October 2009, the Ministry of Ecology, Sustainable Development and Energy (MEDDE), ADEME and the Effinergie association formalized the launch of an experience sharing tool on low-energy building operations: BBC OBSERVATORY. In 2012, two new directions were initiated: Promoting renovation projects, and offering feedback on the first BBC-Effinergie certified projects by early application of RT2012.

Objectives:

- Propose a referencing of the BEPOS universe in France
- Capitalize on the first Bepos-Effinergie 2013 operations

In 2017, the site evolved to integrate the concept "Carbon-Greenhouse Gas Emission" with the publication of the 2017 Effinergie labels.

Now the objectives are the following:

- Support the generalization of positive energy buildings and the massification of renovation
- Contribute to the development of future regulations
- Identify training needs
- Publish annual technical and economic studies for public bodies and professionals
- Publish the Effinergie certification dashboard every quarter
- Distribute transaction sheets describing the transactions every month
- Participate in consultation groups on future regulations
- Host conferences on positive energy buildings and renovation

The following tools are also available:

- Search engines
- Geolocation maps
- A database
- Operation sheets presenting the technical and economic solutions for each project
- An interactive tool analysing the dynamics of low-consumption construction and renovation at different territorial scales.

²⁶ Source: <https://www.observatoirebbc.org/bepos> [access date: 6 May 2020]

L'OBSERVATOIRE
DES BÂTIMENTS
BEPOS ET
BASSE CONSOMMATION

Efficacité énergétique
et confort dans les bâtiments

PRÉSENTATION
PROJETS
STATISTIQUES
PUBLICATIONS
EN RÉGION
CONTACT

Rechercher des bâtiments Bepos

Les informations présentées dans ce module sont issues de travaux menés par l'ADEME et Effinergie afin de réaliser un **benchmark** sur les opérations dites "à énergie positive" en France. Cette analyse regroupe des opérations construites à **différentes périodes** (de 2000 à 2005, de 2005 à 2012, après 2012) suivant les évolutions des réglementations thermiques. Par ailleurs, les opérations référencées ont été soit **auto-déclarées** à énergie positive, soit **lauréates** d'un appel à projet à énergie positive, soit **certifiées** par un organisme certificateur. Enfin, certaines opérations ont été instrumentées et des mesures de **consommations réelles** ont été analysées.

Nous vous proposons donc d'identifier les bâtiments à énergie positive suivant les critères ci-dessous

2285 Résultat(s) << < 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 ... > >>

- Fiabilité -

- Niveau énergétique -

- Région -

- Département -

- Travaux -

- Type bâtiment -

Nom du bâtiment

Recherche Avancée...

	Rénovation - Maison du temps libre	Ville Bâtiment Travaux Origine	Chalandray (86) Tertiaire - Public Rénovation Appel à projet BBC-Effinergie	Surface Consommation Construction Livraison	411,00 m ² 48,97 kWhep/(m ² .an) 1980 01-2022
	Rénovation - Résidence Bois de la Barre	Ville Bâtiment Travaux Origine	Angers (49) Logements collectifs - Public Rénovation Certifié BBC-Effinergie Rénovation	Surface Consommation Construction Livraison	4276,00 m ² 36,92 kWhep/(m ² .an) 1979 08-2021
	Collège J.Ellul	Ville Bâtiment Travaux Origine	Bordeaux (33) Tertiaire - Public Neuf Certifié BEPOS effinergie 2017	Surface Consommation Construction Livraison	8569,20 m ² 26,20 kWhep/(m ² .an) 2020 07-2021
	Résidence Horizon - Ilot 6.1	Ville Bâtiment Travaux Origine	Sathonay Camp (69) Logements collectifs - Privé Neuf En cours de certification BBC-Effinergie 2017	Surface Consommation Construction Livraison	2378,10 m ² 53,40 kWhep/(m ² .an) 2020 06-2021
	ZAC Léon Blum - Lot A1	Ville Bâtiment Travaux Origine	Issy les Moulineaux (92) Logements collectifs - Public Neuf Certifié, En cours de certification BBC-Effinergie 2017	Surface Consommation Construction Livraison	4378,40 m ² 37,10 kWhep/(m ² .an) 2019 06-2021
	Résidence Sénior Services - Zac Girondins	Ville Bâtiment Travaux Origine	LYON (69) Logements collectifs - Privé Neuf Certifié Effinergie+	Surface Consommation Construction Livraison	6278,60 m ² 67,80 kWhep/(m ² .an) 2018 05-2021

FIGURE 23 - SEARCH WEB-PAGE OBSERVATORY BBC

FIGURE 24 - AVAILABLE INFORMATION FOR EACH PROJECT - OBSERVATORY BBC

ZEBRA Data Tool²⁷

²⁷Source: <http://www.zebra-monitoring.enerdata.eu/nzeb-activities/panel-distribution.html#nzeb-definitions-by-country.html> [access date: 9 May 2020]

FIGURE 25 - ZEBRA MONITORING TOOL

Available information is summarized in the following figure:

7.2.1.2 Average data at national level

International Energy Agency (IEA)²⁸

Global view including building sector (residential and services). See section 6 for more details about this source.

Odysee-MURE²⁹

See section 6 for more details about this source.

²⁸ Source: <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-efficiency-indicators-2019#data-service> [access date: 8 May 2020]

²⁹Source: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/france.html#buildings> [access date: 8 May 2020]

FIGURE 26 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF SPACE HEATING PER M2

FIGURE 27 - MAIN DRIVERS OF THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION VARIATION IN HOUSEHOLDS

FIGURE 28 - FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY SECTOR

Eurostat³⁰

See section 6 for more details about this source.

FIGURE 29 - EUROSTAT DATA FOR HOUSEHOLD ENERGY CONSUMPTION

³⁰Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Energy_consumption_in_households#Context [access date: 9 May 2020]

IEA³¹

See section 6 for details about this source.

FIGURE 30 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION – RESIDENTIAL

FIGURE 31 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION DISTRIBUTION IN %

³¹Source : <https://webstore.iea.org/Content/Images/uploaded/Energyefficiencyindicators-short.xlsx>. [data [access date: 9 May 2020]]

FIGURE 32 - EVOLUTION OF ENERGY USES SINCE 2000 (BASE 100)

ADEME report³²

This data comes from the French Environment and Energy Management Agency and can be compared to those from IEA (i.e. Previous Figure 30-31).

FIGURE 33: EVOLUTION OF ENERGY USES SINCE 1990 (BASE 100)

³²Source: <http://multimedia.ademe.fr/catalogues/chiffres-cles-climat-air-energie-2014/data/catalogue.pdf> [access date: 9 May 2020]

EDF data

EDF is the largest electric utility company in France. The data below shows the distribution of electricity consumption by use (Figure 34).

FIGURE 34 - TYPICAL ELECTRICAL APPLIANCES USE

Observatoire des territoires = “Region observatory” (NUTS1/2)³³

Several analyses are available at NUTS 1 and NUTS 2 levels.

7.2.1.3 Trends

Eurostat report³⁴

Some relevant information can be used for the Atlas:

Energy Use in Buildings for residential and non-residential buildings

³³Source: <https://www.observatoire-des-territoires.gouv.fr/observatoire-des-territoires/de/energie-et-territoires> [access date: 6 May 2020]

³⁴ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/fra.pdf> [access date: 6 May 2020]

On site renewable energy production

FIGURE 35: RESIDENTIAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION (ALL END-USES) AND TREND IN ON SITE RE PRODUCTION AS SHARE OF TOTAL CONSUMPTION ON BUILDINGS

FIGURE 36: ON-SITE RENEWABLE ENERGY GENERATION

Number of appliances (see also previous figures)

FIGURE 37: AVERAGE NUMBER OF APPLIANCES

Eurostat tool³⁵

FIGURE 38: FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN HOUSEHOLD BY TYPE OF FUEL (kTep)

³⁵Source:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/graph.do?tab=graph&plugin=1&pcode=ten00125&language=en&toolbox=data>
[access date: 9 May 2020]

7.2.2 Socio economic factors

Eurostat, the « My Region » Tool³⁶

FIGURE 39 - FIGURE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA AVAILABLE IN EUROSTAT FOR OCEANIC CLIMATE

Available data for NUTS1/NUTS2/NUTS3 geocodes:

- Population
- Employment rate
- Unemployment rate
- GDP per habitant

³⁶Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/RCI/myregion/#?reg=FR10&ind=28-2_tran_r_acci [access date: 7 May 2020]

Eurostat: the “Statistical ATLAS” tool at NUTS1/NUTS2/NUTS3 level³⁷

FIGURE 40 - SCREENSHOT OF THE TOOL

Regioviz tool, Social/Demographic indicators for Europe and France regions³⁸

Regioviz Europe corresponds to the initial version of the application ordered by the CGET and aims to position and compare the new French regions in a European context. The definition of indicators and territorial meshes of analysis is based on discussions with SGAR regarding their need for territorial observation in a European context. This version of Regioviz offers 25 indicators from Eurostat. These indicators are structured into 3 themes: social structures, economic structures and demographic structures. Three territorial analysis grids are available: NUTS1, NUTS2 and the infra-national decision mesh, which corresponds to a mixture of NUTS1 and NUTS2. The data files used to feed the application are currently available.

Regioviz France offers 29 indicators (in 2014) from INSEE (Nat department for statistics). These indicators are structured into five themes: Unemployment/standard of living, employment structure, qualifications - training, demographic structures and housing. The data is proposed in five territorial networks and study zones: Employment zones, living areas, EPCIs, urban areas and urban units.

³⁷Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistical-atlas/gis/viewer/?config=census.json&ch=9,42&mids=2,11,CNTOVL&o=1,0,7,0,7¢er=47,22482,6,96272,5&> [access date: 7 May 2020]

³⁸ Source: <https://riatelab.github.io/rgvzall/build/?france> [access date: 9 May 2020]

FIGURE 41 - SCREENSHOT OF REGIOVIZ FRANCE

Observatory of territories³⁹

This is an interactive mapping application of the Territorial Observatory that aims to improve knowledge of territories, by analysing the characteristics of a geographic area or by comparing two areas between them.

The following has been made available:

- more than 500 indicators to be mapped on more than 30 scales, from municipalities to European countries, covering more than fifty themes related to spatial planning
- the zoning perimeters (ZRR, AFR, QPV, etc.)
- portraits of territories offering a general territorial diagnosis on the territory of their choice
- the possibility of visually comparing territories, or even mapping one's own data
- the possibility of adding several indicators and zoning
- the geographic selection of different territories
- to export maps produced and data in different formats

³⁹Source: <https://www.observatoire-des-territoires.gouv.fr/outils/cartographie-interactive/#c=home> [access date : 4 May 2020]

FIGURE 42 - EXAMPLE OF AVAILABLE DATA IN THE OBSERVATORY OF TERRITORIES (FRANCE)

Eurostat

- 1) Population density NUTS2⁴⁰
- 2) Disposable income of households⁴¹
- 3) Final energy consumption in household sector per country⁴²
- 4) Gas prices per household consumer⁴³
- 5) Electricity prices per household consumer⁴⁴

⁴⁰ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tgs00024> [access date: 5 May 2020]

⁴¹ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/ilc_di12 [access date: 5 May 2020]

⁴² Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/refreshTableAction.do?tab=table&plugin=1&pcode=ten00124&language=en> [access date : 5 May 2020]

⁴³ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/nrg_pc_202 [access date: 5 May 2020]

⁴⁴ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/nrg_pc_204 (per type of user) <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/ten00117> [access date: 5 May 2020]

7.2.3 Climatic factors

Eurostat and European Environmental Agency

- 1) Heating Degree days. NUTS2 – Data sheet source
(ANNUAL)⁴⁵
(MONTHLY)⁴⁶
- 2) Cooling Degree Days. NUTS2 – Data sheet source
(ANNUAL)⁴⁷
(MONTHLY)⁴⁸
- 3) Average ambient temperature per year⁴⁹

DJU = Degree day - Heating and cooling – Annual and monthly⁵⁰

⁴⁵ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/nrg_chddr2_a [access date: 3 May 2020]

⁴⁶ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/nrg_chddr2_m [access date: 3 May 2020]

⁴⁷ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/nrg_chddr2_a [access date: 3 May 2020]

⁴⁸ Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/nrg_chddr2_m [access date: 3 May 2020]

⁴⁹ Source: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/indicators/global-and-european-temperature-9/assessment> [access date : 3 May 2020]

⁵⁰ Source: <https://cegibat.grdf.fr/simulateur/calcul-dju> [access date: 3 May 2020]

FIGURE 43 – SCREENSHOT DEGREE DAY - HEATING AND COOLING (FRANCE)

PVGIS⁵¹

PVGIS is available in English, French, Italian and Spanish for any location in Europe and Africa, as well as for a large part of Asia and America. PVGIS provides free and open access to:

- PV potential for different technologies and configurations of grid-connected and stand-alone systems.
- Solar radiation and temperature, as monthly averages or daily profiles.
- Full time series of hourly values of both solar radiation and PV performance.
- Typical Meteorological Year data for nine climatic variables.
- Maps, by country or region, of solar resource and PV potential ready to print.
- PVMAPS software includes all the estimation models used in PVGIS.

⁵¹ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/pvgis> [access date: 2 May 2020]

FIGURE 44 - TOOL INCLUDED IN THE SAME PLATFORM

MeteoFrance⁵²

Climatic data made available by the French national meteorological observatory.

FIGURE 45 - SCREENSHOT METEOTRANCE

⁵² Source: <http://www.meteofrance.com/climat/france> [access date: 9 May 2020]

SolarGIS⁵³

SolarGIS is a commercial tool based on the same principle as PVGIS. Some data is freely available (for France/Oceanic and the rest of the world).

FIGURE 46 - SCREENSHOTS SOLARGIS

7.2.4 Literature review

An analysis of the articles below was conducted to extract some relevant information concerning oceanic climate about occupants' behaviour, comfort preferences, energy consumption and socio-economic factors.

A series of scientific articles have been analysed, the main findings are described here:

Critical review of standards for indoor thermal environment and air quality

According to Khovalyg et al. (2020), standards use categories to define the comfort level depending on the type of occupants and activities.

⁵³ Source: <https://solargis.com/maps-and-gis-data/download/france> [access date: 1 May 2020]

Indoor environmental classes in the reviewed standards.				
Standards	Categories	II	III	IV Concerning oceanic climate
ISO 17772	High: should be selected for occupants with special needs (children, elderly, handicapped)	Medium: normal level used for design and operation	Moderate: will still provide an acceptable environment. Some risk of reduced performance of the occupants	Low: should only be used for a short time of the year or in spaces with very short time of occupancy
ISO 7730 EN 15251, EN 16798	A High level of expectation (spaces occupied by very sensitive and fragile persons with special requirements)	B Normal level of expectation and should be used for new buildings and renovations	C Moderate level of expectation and may be used for existing buildings	- Values outside the criteria for I-III categories. This Category should only be accepted for a limited part of the year
ISHRAE 10001	Class I: aspirational Class A: exceptional	Class II: acceptable Class B: moderate	Class II: min. acceptable Class C: acceptable	-
GB/T 50785	I	II	III	-

FIGURE 47 - INDOOR ENVIRONMENTAL CLASSES IN THE REVIEWED STANDARDS CONCERNING OCEANIC CLIMATE

During winter it appears that the minimum temperature which defines an acceptable level of comfort is around 19-20°C, however this temperature can go up to 24-25°C. In the same way, in summer, the comfort temperature is between 23 and 26°C but can go up to 21°C.

FIGURE 48 - OPERATIVE TEMPERATURE IN THE REVIEWED STANDARDS CONCERNING OCEANIC CLIMATE

Regarding the air speed, due to mechanical or natural ventilation, a limit value of 0.2 m/s is applied.

The acceptable temperature ranges depending on the outside temperature (Figure 49).

FIGURE 49 - RELATION AMONG INDOOR OPERATIVE TEMPERATURE IN REGARD TO OUTDOOR MEAN RUNNING TEMPERATURE IN THE REVIEWED STANDARDS CONCERNING OCEANIC CLIMATE.

For indoor air quality, it is mentioned that the minimum air renewal rate must be 4 l/s/ person.

FIGURE 50 - RELATION BETWEEN VENTILATION RATE AND FLOOR AREA

Understanding the spectrum of domestic energy consumption: Empirical evidence from France

In this article, Belaïd (2016) analyses statistical data from the study conducted with 36,000 occupants of residential buildings. The paper distinguishes four consumer profiles:

- mid-sized urban dwellings heated by gas,
- small apartments heated with electricity in a large city,
- the apartments built between 1975 and 1989 with collective heating
- rural homes or small-town dwellings heated with oil or electricity.

The study shows that energy consumption is not only linked to the characteristics of the building and its location:

- tenants consume less than owners (4-23%)
- the level of income has a low impact
- the impact of the typology: dwellings located in rural areas consume 4–17% more energy than those located in the suburbs.

FIGURE 51 - THE EFFECTS OF HOUSEHOLD AND BUILDING CHARACTERISTICS ON THE ANNUAL DOMESTIC ENERGY OF FRANCE.

Behavioral attitudes towards energy saving: Empirical evidence from France

Belaïd and Joumni (2020) summarize the different factors that can affect household energy-saving behaviour in the figure below (52). A methodology is applied to evaluate a score of energy-saving behaviour with four dimensions of influencing factors (socio-demographic attributes, ideological and situational factors, dwelling characteristics, and available energy control solutions and obstacles.). A ranking of energy-saving behaviour practices is performed by order of difficulty. The main conclusion is that most of the socio-demographic factors were found to be significant at 5%, including gender, age, ethnicity and marital status. In general, being in a family with or without children (as opposed to being single), being a French citizen, and being female, all have a positive impact on energy-saving behaviour.

FIGURE 52 - FOUR DIMENSIONS OF INFLUENCING FACTORS TO ENERGY-SAVING BEHAVIOUR

Local and national determinants of household energy consumption in the Netherlands

In this study, Mashhoodi et al. (2000) focused the research on the location dependency of the recommended national actions in favour of the energy performance of buildings (Third National Energy Efficiency Action Plan) in the Netherlands.

A parametric analysis (geographic parameters) using linear regressions makes it possible to build a map of energy performance according to local socio-economic variations.

The results show that two of the determinants are national:

- the number of frost-days,
- wind speed.

Whereas seven determinants seem to be local:

- income,
- household size,
- building age,
- surface-to-volume ratio,
- population density,
- number of summer days,
- land surface temperature.

FIGURE 53 -MAPS OF THE ENERGY PERFORMANCE ACCORDING TO LOCAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIATIONS

Changing energy cultures? Household energy use before and after a building energy efficiency retrofit

The works of Rau et al. (2020), which was performed for the Irish context based on data coming from retrofitting operations of 20 households in social housing, reached two interesting conclusions:

- Promising quantitative results, namely 23% and 12% drops on average in gas and electricity use after energy efficiency retrofiting, contrast with evidence of change resistant domestic practices and possible rebound effects resulting from a shift in expectations concerning thermal comfort.
- The Energy Culture Framework (ECF) is useful when trying to identify which households may be more open to initiatives to transform householders' energy practices such as advice on how to reduce domestic energy use, particularly those with high energy usage and indoor temperature, without having to live in uncomfortable conditions.

FIGURE 54 - ENERGY CULTURE FRAMEWORK

The socio-economic, dwelling and appliance related factors affecting electricity consumption in domestic buildings

In this paper, (Rory et al. 2015) Jones et al. develop a review that focuses on electrical consumption in residential buildings. Concerning Oceanic climate, the following conclusions are shown as relevant:

- Type and size of dwelling, as well as number of occupants can explain 30–40% of the variation in Danish electricity consumption, whereas the Belgian data could only explain 10–30% of the variation.
- In Denmark, 64% of electricity consumption can be attributed to the number of adults in the house, the number of children, appliance consumption and the total floor area.
- After deep analysis of reviewed articles, 14 socio-economic factors can strongly affect energy performance depending on the country studied (Figure 55).

Summary of the effects of socio-economic factors on electricity consumption in domestic buildings studied in the literature.

Factors	Total number of citations	Significant positive effect on domestic electricity consumption	Significant negative effect on domestic electricity consumption	No effect on domestic electricity consumption
Number of occupants	23	19 [4,8,10-15,17,20,21,24,26,27,29,34,37-39]	1 [19]	3 [23,35,36]
Family composition				
Presence of children	10	4 [5,10,13,28]	2 [14,20]	4 [4,14,29,34]
Presence of teenagers	5	4 [14,20,23,41]	0	1 [14]
Presence of adults	1	1 [17]	0	0
Number of adults	2	2 [22,28]	0	0
Presence of elderly people (over 65 years old)	4	0	2 [13,29]	2 [4,34]
Age of HRP	8	8 [4,5,12,13,15,19,24,29]		0
Employment status of HRP	2	0		2 [24,34]
Education level of HRP	5	2 [17,29]	1 [20]	2 [4,34]
Socio-economic classification of HRP	2	1 [5]	0	1 [29]
Tenure type	12	7 [8,10,21,22,24,30,37]		5 [4,8,12,29,37]
Household income	21	18 [4,6,10,14-17,20,22,24,26,27,32-34,36,39,41]	0	3 [8,12,35]
Disposal income	5	5 [3,11,13,29,38]	0	0

FIGURE 55 - EFFECTS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS ON ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN DOMESTIC BUILDINGS.

7.2.5 Considerations

Some relevant socio-technical elements from the Oceanic climate, e.g. France as CULTURAL-E demo case, could be summarised as follows:

Data from monitored buildings	Data at National Level	Socio-economic factors	Indoor preferences
PEB example - Nanterre (France). Units kWh/(m2/y) - Primary energy need: 23.3 (heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting and water heating) - Final energy consumption: 23.3 - Space heating: 3.9 - Space cooling: 0.0 - Water heating: 8.9 - Lighting & ventilation: 11.4	Share of final energy consumption by type of end-use 2017: - Space heating: 66% - Space cooling: 6% - Lighting and appliances: 17% - Water heating: 11%	Available data for NUTS2 geocodes: - Population - Unemployment rate - GDP per habitant - Disposable income of households - Final energy consumption in household - Gas prices for household consumer - Electricity prices for household consumer	- Minimum comfort temperature in winter is around 19 - 20°C, with exceptions up to 24 - 25°C.
NZEB example - Angers (France). Units kWh/(m2/y) - Primary energy need: 34 kWh/m2/y (heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting and water heating only) - Final energy consumption: 36.6 - Space heating: 16.9 - Space cooling: 0.,0 - Water heating: 14 - Lighting & ventilation: 5.7	Trends 2000-2017 - Electrical appliances recorded a 5% of increase with a +1.8%/year trend - Space heating consumption share dropped by 10% - Cooking decreased by 0.2%/year - Water heating decreased 1.1%/year - Residential energy consumption decreased by 0.2%/year since 2000,	Population density, available data at NUTS2 geocodes 	- Comfort temperature in summer is between 23 - 26°C, with exceptions down to 21°C.

7.3 Continental climate

7.3.1 Energy consumption in households

7.3.1.1 Data from monitored high-efficiency buildings

Aktiv Stadthaus in Frankfurt a. Main is used as an example of PEH Multi-family building. Data on Energy demand is based on measured data from *Aktiv Stadthaus* Frankfurt, Germany⁵⁴.

FIGURE 56 - AKTIV STADTHAUS FRANKFURT, GERMANY, SOURCE: HEGGER HEGGER SCHLEIFF (HHS) PLANER + ARCHITEKTEN AG

Technical data from *Aktiv Stadthaus*, Frankfurt a. M.

- Building insulation according to *KfW Effizienzhaus 55*:
 - e.g. Exterior Wall: $U_{AW} \geq 0.15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ (22 cm insulation)
 - e.g. Window: $U_W \geq 0.8 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
- Ventilation with heat recovery
- Underfloor heating and fresh water stations for domestic hot water (energy consumption as useful heat energy before generation with e.g. a heat pump)

⁵⁴ Sources :

www.abg.de/projekte/innovation-und-technik/aktiv-stadthaus.php [access date: 10 May 2020]

www.stz-egs.de/aktiv-stadthaus-2/ [access date: 10 May 2020]

egs-plan.de/projekt/aktiv-stadthaus-effizienzhaus-plus-speicherstra%C3%9Fe [access date: 10 May 2020]

FIGURE 57 - AKTIV-STADTHAUS: DISTRIBUTION OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF A PEH IN % AND AKTIV-STADTHAUS: DISTRIBUTION OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF A PEH IN kWh/(m²*A)

Cultural habits:

- 2.3 people per household with 90 m² living area (40 m² living space per person)
- Heating: 21 °C indoor temperature during heating period, underfloor heating and towel radiator in bathroom
- Domestic hot water: 1 shower per day and person (duration: 5 min., 37.5°C water temperature)
- Lighting: LED
- Household appliances with the high energy efficiency (A++ / A+++):
fridge, dishwasher (3 washes per week), electric cooker (40 min. per day), washing machine and dryer (2 washes per week)

- User appliances and others: television and computer (4 hours a day), others: coffee machine, hairdryer, kettle, electric iron, microwave, smartphone...

After completion during the monitoring phase, a series of post-occupancy interviews in households were carried out by the “*Berliner Institut für Sozialforschung GmbH*” (BIS). The following figures show an extract of the results of the user survey. The majority of users would recommend a highly efficient home (PEH) to family and friends, see Figure 58.

FIGURE 58 - WOULD YOU RECOMMEND A HIGHLY EFFICIENT HOME TO YOUR FAMILY AND FRIENDS? (PEB)

FIGURE 59 - INTERIOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY (IEQ) I

FIGURE 60 - INTERIOR ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITY (IEQ) II

In 2018, a consortium of *Berliner Institut für Sozialforschung GmbH*, *Steinbeis-Transferzentrum EGS* and *HHS PLANER + ARCHITEKTEN* published a practical Guideline for planning Plus Energy houses. It covers recommendations for the planning phase, building envelope with building integrated photovoltaics, local renewable energy use, building technology as well as monitoring and involvement of users⁵⁵.

The calculation of an expected electricity consumption of a household is part of the planning process. An approach to estimate the energy consumption of users of a PEH building according to *aktivplus e.V.* shows the following Equation :

$$\text{Annual user consumption per unit} = 500 \times (1,4 + P) \text{ [kWh/a]}$$

Equation 1: Energy consumption of users of a PEH building according to *aktivplus e.V.*

500: basic consumption of an energy saving household

P: persons per unit

According to Equation a PEH household with 2,3 Persons has an annual electricity consumption of 1.850 kWh.

⁵⁵Source: www.bbsr.bund.de/BBSR/DE/Veroeffentlichungen/ZukunftBauenFP/2019/band-15-dl.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3 [access date: 2 May 2020]

7.3.1.2 Average data at national level

The average energy consumption of households in Germany at national level according to *Umweltbundesamt* (2017) is shown in the following Figures.

FIGURE 61 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF GERMAN HOUSEHOLDS 2017 IN %, UMWELTBUNDESAMT⁵⁶

FIGURE 62 - ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF GERMAN HOUSEHOLDS 2017 IN KWH/M² LIVING AREA, OWN CALCULATIONS BASED ON UMWELTBUNDESAMT AND DESTATIS

⁵⁶Source: www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/private-haushalte-konsum/wohnen/energieverbrauch-privater-haushalte#endenergieverbrauch-der-privaten-haushalte [access date: 5 May 2020]

Electrical energy consumption by households

Merkmale	2010	2012	2014	2015	2016	2017	2017 zu 2016 in %	2017 zu 2010 in %
Petajoule								
Strom insgesamt	503	493	472	465	462	463	0,1	-8,1
Gigawattstunden								
Strom insgesamt	139 756	136 823	131 024	129 183	128 418	128 502	0,1	-8,1
Anzahl in 1 000								
Haushalte	40 301	39 707	40 222	40 773	40 959	41 305	0,8	2,5
Kilowattstunden								
Strom je Haushalt	3 468	3 446	3 258	3 168	3 135	3 111	-0,8	-10,3
1-Personen-Haushalt	2 222	2 208	2 103	2 052	2 017	2 005	-0,6	-9,8
2-Personen-Haushalt	3 555	3 523	3 345	3 268	3 220	3 205	-0,4	-9,8
3 und mehr Personen-Haushalt	5 307	5 305	5 035	4 923	4 863	4 856	-0,1	-8,5
darunter:								
Strom je Haushalt für Elektrogeräte	2 862	2 874	2 708	2 639	2 609	2 600	-0,3	-9,2
1-Personen-Haushalt	1 773	1 775	1 681	1 646	1 619	1 619	0,0	-8,7
2-Personen-Haushalt	2 908	2 913	2 758	2 700	2 656	2 656	0,0	-8,7
3 und mehr Personen-Haushalt	4 510	4 566	4 331	4 238	4 177	4 186	0,2	-7,2

1: Strom für Raumwärme, Warmwasser (Hygienezwecke), Beleuchtung und Elektrogeräte.

FIGURE 63 - ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF HOUSEHOLDS IN GERMANY, DESTATIS 2019⁵⁷

The “*Stromspiegel*” publishes electricity consumption data annually by classifying the electricity consumption households depending on building type and domestic hot water production. The consumptions vary from A=very low until G=very high. The electricity consumption of the example PEH household according to Equation would be B=low.

⁵⁷Source : www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Umwelt/Materialfluesse-Energiefloesse/Tabellen/stromverbrauch-haushalte.html [access date : 4 May 2020]

Gebäudetyp	Warmwasser	Personen im Haushalt	Verbrauch in Kilowattstunden (kWh) pro Jahr						
			gering				sehr hoch		
			A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Haus	ohne Strom	1 Person	bis 1.300	bis 1.700	bis 2.000	bis 2.500	bis 3.000	bis 4.000	über 4.000
		2 Personen	bis 2.000	bis 2.500	bis 2.800	bis 3.100	bis 3.600	bis 4.400	über 4.400
		3 Personen	bis 2.500	bis 3.000	bis 3.500	bis 3.800	bis 4.300	bis 5.300	über 5.300
		4 Personen	bis 2.900	bis 3.500	bis 4.000	bis 4.300	bis 5.000	bis 6.000	über 6.000
	mit Strom	1 Person	bis 1.500	bis 2.000	bis 2.400	bis 2.900	bis 3.500	bis 5.000	über 5.000
		2 Personen	bis 2.500	bis 3.000	bis 3.500	bis 4.000	bis 4.500	bis 6.000	über 6.000
		3 Personen	bis 3.000	bis 3.600	bis 4.200	bis 4.900	bis 5.800	bis 7.500	über 7.500
		4 Personen	bis 3.500	bis 4.200	bis 5.000	bis 5.500	bis 6.500	bis 8.100	über 8.100
Wohnung	ohne Strom	1 Person	bis 800	bis 1.000	bis 1.300	bis 1.500	bis 1.800	bis 2.200	über 2.200
		2 Personen	bis 1.300	bis 1.600	bis 2.000	bis 2.400	bis 2.600	bis 3.000	über 3.000
		3 Personen	bis 1.600	bis 2.000	bis 2.500	bis 2.900	bis 3.400	bis 4.000	über 4.000
		4 Personen	bis 1.900	bis 2.300	bis 2.800	bis 3.200	bis 3.900	bis 4.500	über 4.500
	mit Strom	1 Person	bis 1.200	bis 1.500	bis 1.800	bis 2.000	bis 2.300	bis 3.000	über 3.000
		2 Personen	bis 2.000	bis 2.500	bis 2.800	bis 3.100	bis 3.500	bis 4.100	über 4.100
		3 Personen	bis 2.500	bis 3.100	bis 3.600	bis 4.000	bis 4.600	bis 5.700	über 5.700
		4 Personen	bis 2.800	bis 3.600	bis 4.000	bis 4.800	bis 5.400	bis 6.800	über 6.800

FIGURE 64 - STROMSPIEGEL 2019⁵⁸

⁵⁸Source: www.stromspiegel.de/fileadmin/ssi/stromspiegel/Broschuere/stromspiegel-faktenblatt-2019.pdf [access date: 7 May 2020]

Administrative districts

In Germany the NUTS 2 level corresponds to governmental regions known as *Regierungsbezirke*.

FIGURE 65 - GERMAN NUTS 2⁵⁹

Regions in the European Union⁶⁰.

Average data at regional level. Energy consumption by domestic services

The energy consumption for building heating depends mainly on the type of the building (e.g. single family, double, small or huge multifamily building) and the building age. Compared to these factors the different regional climate is negligible for the buildings heating energy consumption. The “*Institut Wohnen und Umwelt*” (IWU) has developed a classification of the building typology of Germany, see Figure 66.

⁵⁹Source : www.esf.de/portal/SharedDocs/PDFs/DE/FP%202014-2020/nuts-klassifikation.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4 [access date : 9 May 2020]

⁶⁰ Source: ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/5916917/KS-RA-11-011-EN.PDF [access date : 9 May 2020]

Nach IWU-Wohngebäudetypologie ergeben sich folgende Wohngebäudetypen:

- EFH: Einfamilienhaus
- RH: Reihenhaushaus
- MFH: Mehrfamilienhaus
- GMH: Groß-Mehrfamilienhaus
- HH: Hochhaus

Klasse	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Baujahr	< 1859	1860 - 1918	1919 - 1948	1949 - 1957	1958 - 1968	1969 - 1978	1979 - 1983	1984 - 1994	1995 - 2001	2002 - 2009

Tabella: Klassifizierung der Baujahre nach IWU-Studie

FIGURE 66 - CLASSIFICATION OF BUILDING TYPOLOGY IN GERMANY, IWU 2011

The energy consumption for domestic hot water depends mainly on the number of residents, user behaviour and the type of hot water production (e.g. electrical or boiler). The electricity consumption for households depends mainly on the number of residents as well as user behaviour.

As the energy consumption by domestic services does not depend mainly on regional climate there is no data available at regional level.

7.3.2 Socio-economic factors

- 1) Population density NUTS2, see link below⁶¹
- 2) Gross domestic product of the area last census

Germany	2017	2018
	Gross domestic product Mill. EUR	Gross domestic product Mill. EUR
Baden-Württemberg	495.149	511.420
Bayern	605.390	625.161
Berlin	139.683	147.057
Brandenburg	71.164	73.722
Bremen	33.033	34.294
Hamburg	116.380	120.332
Hessen	280.934	292.016
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	43.751	44.914
Niedersachsen	287.771	296.164
Nordrhein-Westfalen	685.187	705.066
Rheinland-Pfalz	143.730	149.148
Saarland	35.546	35.961
Sachsen	122.282	126.364
Sachsen-Anhalt	61.653	63.504
Schleswig-Holstein	93.515	97.074
Thüringen	62.172	63.804
Deutschland	3.277.340	3.386.000

TABLE 8 - GROSS DOMESTIC PRODUCT GERMANY, DESTATIS 82111-0001

⁶¹ Source: ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tqs00024 [access date: 6 May 2020]

3) Disposable income of households

2017 Germany	Disposable income private households	Disposable income private households per inhabitant
	Mill. EUR	EUR
Baden-Württemberg	269.770	24.552
Bayern	323.615	24.963
Berlin	73.068	20.330
Brandenburg	50.549	20.225
Bremen	14.539	21.384
Hamburg	44.427	24.404
Hessen	143.823	23.092
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	30.912	19.190
Niedersachsen	174.357	21.920
Nordrhein-Westfalen	398.530	22.263
Rheinland-Pfalz	92.513	22.731
Saarland	20.432	20.527
Sachsen	81.306	19.920
Sachsen-Anhalt	43.562	19.537
Schleswig-Holstein	65.983	22.864
Thüringen	42.529	19.738
Deutschland	1.869.916	22.623

TABLE 9 - DISPOSABLE INCOME PRIVATE HOUSEHOLDS GERMANY, DESTATIS 82411-0001⁶²

4) Electricity consumption of households

As shown in chapter 4.1 the regional data for electricity consumption is inconclusive and not available.

5) Gas consumption of households

The “BDEW Bundesverband der Energie-und Wasserwirtschaft e.V” has published a study on “How is Germany heating buildings? (2019)”. 48 % of the buildings use gas as an energy source followed by oil with a share of 25 % and 14 % district heating, see Figure 67.

⁶² Source: ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/ilc_di12 [access date: 9 May 2020]

FIGURE 67 - USED ENERGY SOURCES FOR HEATING IN GERMANY, BDEW 2019

There are regional differences in the use of energy sources for heating see Figure 68.

FIGURE 68 SHARE OF ENERGY SOURCE FOR HEATING DEPENDING ON REGIONS, BDEW 2019⁶³

⁶³ Source: www.bdew.de/media/documents/Pub_20191031_Wie-heizt-Deutschland-2019.pdf [access date: 6 May 2020]

As explained in previous chapters, no regional data for gas consumption in Germany is available.

6) Final energy consumption in household sector per country:

FIGURE 69 - FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF GERMAN HOUSEHOLDS, UMWELTBUNDESAMT⁶⁴

7) Gas and electricity prices per household consumer.

Energy prices for household, VAT included (source: BMWi 2019)

- gas price (2019): 6,79 ct/kWh
- electricity price (2019): 31,24 ct/kWh

No regional data in Germany available.

⁶⁴Source: www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/private-haushalte-konsum/wohnen/energieverbrauch-privater-haushalte#endenergieverbrauch-der-privaten-haushalte [access date : 7 May 2020]

FIGURE 70 - PRICE FOR GAS AND ELECTRICITY OF HOUSEHOLDS (2018)⁶⁵

7.3.3 Climatic factors

Weather data from single year does not represent the typical long-term weather patterns and therefore are not suitable for energy simulations. Energy simulation programs use hourly weather data based on a synthetic year which represents the temperature, solar radiation, and other variables of long-term average climatic conditions. Single years can have warm or cold winters and summers and the prediction of energy demand on that basis is very variable⁶⁶.

⁶⁵ Sources:

ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3217494/10164477/KS-EI-19-001-DE-N.pdf [access date : 5 May 2020]

ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3217494/10095393/KS-HA-19%E2%80%911001-EN-N.pdf/d434affa-99cd-4ebf-a3e3-6d4a5f10bb07 [access date: 5 2020]

⁶⁶ Sources:

energyplus.net/weather/simulation [access date: 5 May 2020]

energyplus.net/sites/all/modules/custom/weather_files/whichweatherdatashouldyouuseforenergysimulations.pdf [access date: 5 May 2020]

A summary of data can be found in the .stat file such as:

- Monthly Solar Irradiance Wh/m²
- Monthly Dry-bulb and Mean Coincident Wet-bulb Temperatures °C
- Heating/Cooling Degree Days/Hours
- Relative Humidity %
- Average Temperature for typical and extreme summer/ winter/ autumn / spring
- Min. and max. temperature over the year

The Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) provides open source data about solar radiation and PV performance⁶⁷.

Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS)

Try the PVGIS tools:

PV Performance

Grid connected Tracking PV Off grid

PV Performance tool

Solar radiation

Monthly Daily Hourly

Solar radiation tool

TMY

Typical Meteorological Year

Temperature, wind, humidity, air pressure, ...

TMY tool

PVGIS is available in English, French, Italian and Spanish for any location in Europe and Africa, as well as large part of Asia and America.

PVGIS provides free and open access to:

- PV potential for different technologies and configurations of grid connected and stand alone systems.
- Solar radiation and temperature, as monthly averages or daily profiles.
- Full time series of hourly values of both solar radiation and PV performance.
- Typical Meteorological Year data for nine climatic variables.
- Maps, by country or region, of solar resource and PV potential ready to print.
- PVMAPS software includes all the estimation models used in PVGIS.

FIGURE 71 - PHOTOVOLTAIC GEOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION SYSTEM (PVGIS)

Source for climatic data for Europe, *EnergyPlus*: energyplus.net/weather-region/europe_wmo_region_6

⁶⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/pvgis> [access date: 5 May 2020]

The PV Performance Tool calculates the performance of any photovoltaic plant:

FIGURE 72 - PVGIS: PV PERFORMANCE TOOL, STEP 1: CHOOSE LOCATION

GRID CONNECTED

PERFORMANCE OF GRID-CONNECTED PV
?

TRACKING PV

OFF-GRID

MONTHLY DATA

DAILY DATA

HOURLY DATA

TMY

Solar radiation database* PVGIS-SARAH

PV technology* Crystalline silicon

Installed peak PV power [kWp]* 1

System loss [%]* 14

Fixed mounting options

Mounting position* Building integrated

Slope [°]* 30 Optimize slope

Azimuth [°]* ↓ Optimize slope and azimuth

PV electricity price

PV system cost (your currency)

Interest [%/year]

Lifetime [years]

FIGURE 73 - PVGIS: PV PERFORMANCE TOOL, STEP 2: INPUT TYPE OF PV, SLOPE AND AZIMUTH

Result data can be seen in Figure 74

- yearly PV energy production (kWh)
- the yearly solar irradiation (kWh/m²)
- year to year variability (kWh)

FIGURE 74 - PVGIS: PV PERFORMANCE TOOL, STEP 3 RESULTS

7.3.4 Literature review

Indoor temperature preferences

People feel comfortable at a room temperature of 20 - 22 °C, but different temperatures are perceived as comfortable in different rooms: living room 20 - 22°C, bedroom 16 - 18°C, bathroom 24 - 26°C (Dena 2007). This is confirmed by measurement data from monitored plus energy buildings with interior temperatures between 18 - 24 °C during the heat seasons (Van Treeck, Lorz 2018; Mahler, Nusser 2018). This leads to real energy consumption for building heating which are higher than calculated energy demands based on an average indoor temperature at a constant 20°C⁶⁸. According to Ackermann (2020) higher temperature differences within an apartment and fluctuations in the time of day are visible, especially in existing buildings which have minimal or no insulation. Room temperatures in living rooms are primarily dependent on user behaviour, such as ventilation behaviour and thus indirectly also on individual temperature perception (Mahler, Nusser 2018).

In general, surface heating systems with high radiation components are perceived as pleasant (BBSR 2007). In addition, individual room temperature control can react appropriately to the different temperature requirements.

Relative indoor air humidity

At room temperatures between 19 – 23 °C the relative air humidity can fluctuate from about 35 - 70% and still be perceived as comfortable Schild (2013). Moisture content requirements are primarily due to hygienic and health reasons: air humidity should not be less than 35%, otherwise respiratory organs can dry out. However, air humidity should be below 80% to prevent the formation of mould and condensation. Ventilation systems with heat recovery reduce ventilation heat losses in comparison to pure exhaust air systems or exclusive window ventilation. However, if ventilation systems are

⁶⁸ DIN V 18599-10: Boundary conditions of use for calculation of energy demand of buildings,

equipped with heat recovery systems without moisture recovery, there is a risk of heating air that is too dry with air humidity below 35% in the winter months (BBSR 2007).

Knowledge about own energy consumption

Knowledge of their own energy consumption and the impact on additional costs has a significant impact on the user behaviour. Apartments without consumption-based heating costs tend to have higher indoor temperatures (Loga 2003). Part of the research within the PEB *Aktiv-Stadthaus*, Frankfurt is the implementation of user interfaces in every unit (Mahler, Nusser 2018).

Each apartment receives information on the current state of the electricity and heat consumption and comparisons to the rest of the building via a display. A resident survey via questionnaire prompts feedback on energy consumption via the installed user interface; which is considered as useful equipment, and residents consulted them on a weekly basis. Feedback on their own electricity and heat consumption is of great interest.

Most of the residents surveyed agreed with the statement "I am motivated to contribute to a good energy balance of the house, and my behaviour is the key". It can be assumed that in addition to the highly efficient household appliances in the apartments, this motivation allows residents to be aware and to make decisions about their energy demand, as consequence, it becomes a key factor in positively balancing the building's energy outcomes.

7.3.5 Considerations

Some relevant socio-technical elements from the Continental climate, e.g. Germany as CULTURAL-E demo case, could be summarised as follows:

Data from monitored buildings	Data at National Level	Socio-economic factors	Indoor preferences	Technology preferences
<p>PEB Example Aktiv-stadthaus: Energy consumption in kwh/(m2/y)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Space heating: 35 - Space cooling: 0 - Lighting & ventilation: 6 - Water heating: 13,5 - Appliances: 19,8 	<p>Available data for NUTS2 geocodes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Population - Unemployment rate - GDP per habitant - Disposable income of households - Final energy consumption in household - Gas prices for household consumer - Electricity prices for household consumer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Different temperatures are perceived as comfortable in different rooms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - living room 20 - 22°C - bedroom 16 - 18°C - bathroom 24 - 26°C - Measurement data from monitored PEB, preferred interior temperatures between 18 - 24 ° C 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PEB Post-occupancy survey reveals that the use of high-efficient home technologies are well integrated in the households' daily practices, but cultural factors are determinants to allow users to contribute to balancing the building's energy outcomes positively. 	

7.4 Mediterranean climate

7.4.1 Energy consumption in households

7.4.1.1 Average data at national level

Object: Mediterranean territories

FIGURE 75 - KÖPPEN-GEIGER CLIMATE CLASSIFICATION IN EUROPE⁶⁹

⁶⁹Source: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/households/energy-consumption-by-end-use.html> [access date: 6 May 2020]

National reports are available in the Mediterranean area⁷⁰ for the following countries:

- Italy (Cultural-E Demo Country)⁷¹
- Spain⁷²
- Portugal⁷³
- Slovenia
- Greece⁷⁴

FIGURE 76 ODDYSSEE-MURE NATIONAL REPORTS EXAMPLES

Ranking Scoreboard. Data available for:

- Italy (Cultural-E Demo Country)
- Spain
- Portugal
- South of France
- Slovenia
- Croatia
- Greece
- Malta
- Cyprus

⁷⁰ Source: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/national-reports/> [access date: 9 May 2020]

⁷¹ Source <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/national-reports/energy-efficiency-italy.pdf> [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁷² Source <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/national-reports/energy-efficiency-spain.pdf> [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁷³ Source <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/national-reports/energy-efficiency-portugal.pdf> [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁷⁴ Source <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/national-reports/energy-efficiency-greece.pdf> [access date: 6 May 2020]

LEVEL

TREND

Households	Indicators						
	Heating per m2 adjusted to EU climate	Trend- Heating	Other thermal uses	Trend - Other thermal use	Appliances (incl. Lighting and AC)	Trend - Appliances	Solar Water Heater penetration
Countries	koe/m2	trend(00-15)	toe/dw	trend(00-15)	toe/dw	trend(00-15)	% dwelling
cro	29,46	-0,03	0,27	-0,01	0,23	0,01	2,0%
cyp	16,76	-0,03	0,34	-0,01	0,27	-0,01	73,2%
esp	9,45	-0,04	0,19	-0,02	0,25	0,02	4,4%
fra	12,34	-0,02	0,22	-0,01	0,21	0,00	2,3%
grc	18,35	-0,03	0,15	0,00	0,22	0,01	30,2%
ita	15,43	-0,01	0,23	-0,01	0,18	0,00	3,6%
mlt	14,50	0,00	0,17	0,00	0,21	-0,02	9,8%
prt	11,09	-0,04	0,38	-0,02	0,12	0,00	6,4%
slo	13,49	-0,01	0,29	-0,01	0,14	-0,01	4,5%

FIGURE 77. LEVEL AND TREND INDICATORS FOR MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES

Eurostat

	Space heating	Space cooling	Water heating	Cooking	Lighting and appliances	Other end uses
EU-28	64.1	0.3	14.8	5.6	14.4	0.9
Belgium	73.8	0.1	11.4	1.7	12.7	0.4
Bulgaria	54.3	0.5	17.2	8.4	19.7	0.0
Czechia	69.0	0.1	16.2	6.3	7.0	1.5
Denmark	62.5	0.0	21.2	1.8	14.2	0.2
Germany	67.1	0.2	16.1	6.4	9.3	0.9
Estonia	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ireland	59.0	0.0	19.8	2.4	18.0	1.4
Greece	56.2	4.4	13.5	4.9	21.0	0.0
Spain	43.4	0.9	19.1	7.7	28.9	0.0
France	66.1	0.2	11.1	5.4	17.3	0.0
Croatia	68.7	1.8	10.0	6.5	13.0	0.0
Italy	67.5	0.7	11.9	6.3	12.3	1.4
Luxembourg	65.6	0.0	18.6	7.2	8.0	0.6
Lithuania	70.3	0.0	9.2	6.5	14.0	0.0
Luxembourg	79.3	0.2	7.1	2.3	11.0	0.0
Hungary	77.0	0.1	72.0	4.5	8.4	0.0
Malta	15.0	8.3	19.8	12.0	43.7	1.2
Netherlands	63.6	0.2	16.7	2.1	17.4	0.1
Austria	69.9	0.0	14.9	2.7	10.4	2.2
Poland	65.0	0.0	76.1	9.1	8.8	0.6
Portugal	24.2	0.7	10.1	29.5	19.6	0.0
Romania	63.4	0.3	72.4	9.5	12.4	0.0
Slovenia	63.7	0.5	16.0	4.1	15.8	0.0
Slovakia	68.3	0.1	14.3	5.6	11.7	0.0
Finland	65.8	0.1	14.9	1.0	12.2	5.9
Sweden	54.5	0.0	13.6	1.5	19.1	11.3
United Kingdom	62.1	0.0	17.2	3.0	17.7	0.0
Norway	43.8	0.0	14.2	0.0	37.1	4.9
North Macedonia	63.3	1.9	11.5	9.3	14.0	0.0
Albania	31.7	5.5	21.4	29.8	11.7	0.0
Serbia	60.2	0.5	14.4	7.3	17.7	0.0
Kosovo*	71.3	3.5	6.5	7.1	9.3	2.2
Moldova	70.7	0.1	10.0	11.2	8.0	0.0
Georgia	58.8	0.3	11.3	17.4	12.1	0.0

(*) This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.
 (.) not available

FIGURE 78. SHARE (%) OF FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN THE RESIDENTIAL SECTOR IN MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES BY TYPE OF END-USE (EUROSTAT 2017)

Energy Consumption. Household sector (Italy)

FIGURE 79. ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF HOUSEHOLDS BY ENERGY SOURCE

FIGURE 80. SHARES OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION BY ENERGY SOURCE IN HOUSEHOLDS

FIGURE 81. ENERGY UNIT CONSUMPTION OF ELECTRICAL APPLIANCE IN HOUSEHOLDS (2000=100)

FIGURE 82. MAIN DRIVERS OF THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION VARIATION IN HOUSEHOLDS

7.4.1.2 Data from monitored high-efficiency buildings

CaveZero project⁷⁵

Detailed sheet for Italian demo cases

FIGURE 83: EXAMPLE OF A DETAILED SHEET CAVEZERO PROJECT (ITALY)

⁷⁵ Source: <https://cravezero.eu/cases-2/>. [access date: 6 May 2020]

ITA NZEB Observatory

FIGURE 84. PERCENTAGE OF HIGH-PERFORMANCE BUILDINGS (NZEB) OUT OF THE TOTAL BUILDING BY REGION

As part of the creation of an “**NZEB Observatory**”, a research initiative funded by MISE (Research of the PAR 2016 Electric System), the energy efficiency department of ENEA (Italy National Agency) has started to monitor the construction of NZEB certified buildings according to the 2015 regulation and related enabling factors (procedures, incentives, information-training, research and innovation), to:

- assist national and regional decision-makers in the development of policies and initiatives to promote these buildings and in monitoring their impact,
- conduct technical analysis and communicate with the various players in the sector: Citizens, businesses, professionals, public administrations and government, the existing case studies, providing details about the adopted technologies and relevant considerations on the process (stakeholders, financing, etc.).

The NZEB observatory is divided into:

- National situation benchmark (regions)
- Good practices: selection of NZEB cases and information on performance, costs, technologies, processes.

The screenshot shows the 'Osservatorio nazionale NZEB' website. At the top, there are logos for ENEC, REQUEST, and the European Union. The main header features the 'portale4e' logo and the text 'EFFICIENZA ENERGETICA EDIFICI ESISTENTI'. A navigation bar includes a button for 'PER LE IMPRESE E GLI OPERATORI' with a subtext: 'Guide, buone pratiche e incentivi per migliorare l'efficienza e il comfort della nostre abitazioni'. The main content area is titled 'NZEB - Edifici a Energia quasi ZERO'. It features a graphic with the text 'PROGETTARE EDIFICI A ENERGIA QUASI ZERO' and 'E ≈ 0' next to a house icon. Below this, a section titled 'NZEB, una scadenza imminente' explains that from 2021, new buildings or those undergoing major renovation must meet the NZEB standard. It also mentions that some regions have more ambitious targets, such as Lombardy starting in 2019. To the right, under the heading 'IMMAGINI', there are two photographs of NZEB buildings: '39+6 ALLOGGI ERP CASA SPA A FIRENZE' and 'EDIFICIO RESIDENZIALE A TORINO (ZONA E)'. The latter image includes a small 'casa zero' logo.

FIGURE 85 - ITA NZEB PROJECT

The project includes the following activities⁷⁶:

- Definition of representative indicators.
- Data collection relating to NZEB buildings (overall performance and of the individual components and systems) in a special database.
- Processing of standard forms that will be available on this site.
- Mapping of NZEB and related incentive policies in the area.

⁷⁶ Sources:

http://www.portale4e.it/centrale_dettaglio_imprese.aspx?ID=6 [access date: 6 May 2020]
http://www.portale4e.it/centrale_dettaglio_imprese.aspx?ID=2 [access date: 6 May 2020]

UE NZEB Data

FIGURE 86 - EU PROJECT WEBSITES

7.4.1.2 Trends

National level energy efficiency trends, positioning (absolute/best benchmark) per domestic energy use: Level / Trend / Level & trend.⁷⁷

- Italy (Cultural-E Demo Country)
- Spain
- Portugal
- South of France
- Slovenia
- Croatia
- Greece
- Malta
- Cyprus

FIGURE 87 – ODYSSEE - MURE - TRENDS DIAGRAMMES (ITALY)

⁷⁷ Source: <https://indicators.odyssee-mure.eu/energy-efficiency-scoreboard.html#countryPositioning> [access date: 9 May 2020]

National level energy policies trends, reporting⁷⁸.

- Italy (Cultural-E Demo Country)⁷⁹
- Spain⁸⁰
- Portugal⁸¹
- South of France⁸²
- Slovenia⁸³
- Croatia⁸⁴
- Greece⁸⁵

7.4.2 Socio-economic factors

Eurostat⁸⁶

FIGURE 88 - STATIST DATA AVAILABLE AT EUROSTAT.

⁷⁸ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/ [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁷⁹ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/italy.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸⁰ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/spain.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸¹ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/france.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸² Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/portugal.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸³ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/slovenia.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸⁴ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/croatia.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸⁵ Source: www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-trends-policies-profiles/greece.html [access date: 6 May 2020]

⁸⁶Source

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database?p_p_id=NavTreeportletprod_WAR_NavTreeportletprod_INSTANCE_nPqeVbPXRmWQ&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=normal&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-2&p_p_col_pos=1&p_p_col_count=2 [access date: 6 May 2020]

GEO/TIME	2020	2030	2040	2050
European Union - 27	447.671.046	449.121.599	446.754.877	441.220.961
Greece	10.696.535	10.303.200	9.910.798	9.503.127
Spain	47.321.434	48.746.399	49.377.094	49.348.530
France	67.197.367	68.749.400	69.802.409	70.010.903
Croatia	4.056.285	3.828.089	3.612.487	3.392.559
Italy	60.286.529	59.942.512	59.375.006	58.125.032
Cyprus	887.331	962.854	1.012.858	1.046.219
Malta	506.951	588.691	634.910	668.373
Portugal	10.291.457	10.089.138	9.786.632	9.375.347
Slovenia	2.095.314	2.106.316	2.081.622	2.043.751
Med	45%	46%	46%	46%

FIGURE 89. POPULATION BY AGE, SEX AND TYPE OF PROJECTION IN EU MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES

FIGURE 90. STATIST DATA AVAILABLE AT EUROSTAT. MEDIAN AGE OF POPULATION. CENSUS 2011

FIGURE 91. GDP PER INHABITANT. EUROSTAT REGIONAL YEARBOOK 2019 AND INCOME PER INHABITANT. EUROSTAT REGIONAL YEARBOOK 2019⁸⁷

FIGURE 92. DEGREE OF URBANIZATION. EUROSTAT REGIONAL YEARBOOK 2019⁸⁸

⁸⁷Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistical-atlas/gis/viewer/?config=RyB-2019.json&mids=BKGCNT,C06M02,CNTOVL&o=1,1,0.7¢er=42.51353,18.16981,4&ch=ECF,C06,C02&lci=C06M02&> [access date: 7 May 2020]

⁸⁸Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistical-atlas/gis/viewer/?config=RyB-2019.json&mids=BKGCNT,TYP11,CNTOVL&o=1,1,0.7&ch=C02,TRC,TYP¢er=44.76696,16.85026,4&lci=TYP11&> [access date: 7 May 2020]

IT Composition of the electricity bill⁸⁹

FIGURE 93 COMPOSITION OF THE ELECTRICITY BILL IN ITALY

⁸⁹ Source: <http://arera.it/it/dati/eep35.htm> <https://arera.it/it/dati/ees5.htm> [access date : 9 May 2020]

Electricity Energy consumptions (Italy)⁹⁰

ARERA
Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente

Home / Dati e documenti / Dati e statistiche

Dati statistici

150 anni di energia in Italia

Seleziona settore e argomento per visualizzare i dati statistici disponibili

Settore:

- Acqua
- Gas
- Elettricità**

Argomento:

Visualizza Reset

FIGURE 94 - ANNUAL ELECTRICITY ENERGY CONSUMPTION IN ITALY 2000-2017.

⁹⁰Source: <http://arera.it/it/dati/ees3.htm> [access date: 7 May 2020]

Energy consumptions – Gas (Italy)⁹¹

VENDITE FINALI PER REGIONE								
M(m ³)								
Anno 2017								
	Numero venditori presenti	Vendite						
		Domestico	Condominio uso domestico	Attività di servizio pubblico	Commercio e servizi	Industria	Generazione elettrica	Totale
Piemonte	226	1.428	382	149	771	2.901	1.844	7.474
Val d'Aosta	75	17	7	7	15	63	0	109
Liguria	273	3.614	888	335	1.763	3.936	1.482	12.018
Lombardia	115	185	72	55	253	418	8	991
Trentino Alto Adige	208	1.835	155	182	884	2.098	285	5.439
Veneto	155	418	68	49	183	836	168	1.722
Friuli Venezia Giulia	167	379	160	41	136	309	629	1.655
Emilia Romagna	219	1.836	267	101	1.072	3.228	1.116	7.619
Toscana	198	1.111	104	78	483	1.617	581	3.973
Lazio	148	219	16	20	139	383	24	801
Marche	167	X	24	21	309	536	5	1.373
Umbria	224	1.068	260	112	574	757	3.486	6.257
Abruzzo	178	360	19	17	152	474	51	1.073
Molise	115	80	5	9	36	64	309	502
Campania	185	610	26	74	249	529	800	2.288
Puglia	175	777	16	38	203	727	757	2.518
Basilicata	120	135	6	24	35	155	0	356
Calabria	122	208	3	9	47	70	77	414
Sicilia	141	477	9	25	112	738	1.871	3.233
Sardegna	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Totale	-	15.235	2.486	1.345	7.415	19.841	13.494	59.816

FIGURE 95 ANNUAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION – GAS PER REGION (ITALY)

GEO/HHCOMP	Total	Household composed of one-family nucleus	Household composed of married couple	Household composed of couple in registered partnership	Household composed of couple in consensual union	Household composed of lone father living with at least one child	Household composed of lone mother living with at least one child	Household composed of two-or-more-family nucleus	Household composed of non-family nucleus	One-person household	Multiperson household other than family nucleus
Italy	24.583.190	15.939.517	12.296.179	0	1.204.622	435.852	2.002.864	350.204	8.293.469	7.641.106	652.363
Nord-Ovest	6.923.168	4.356.890	3.302.984	0	400.970	114.268	538.668	61.945	2.504.333	2.331.364	172.969
Piemonte	1.950.833	1.218.394	915.878	0	117.982	32.926	151.608	17.078	715.361	669.476	45.885
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée	59.352	34.316	24.182	0	4.576	912	4.646	353	24.683	23.493	1.190
Liguria	757.543	418.501	302.310	0	35.376	14.257	66.558	7.160	331.882	309.229	22.653
Lombardia	4.155.440	2.685.679	2.060.614	0	243.036	66.173	315.856	37.354	1.432.407	1.329.166	103.241
Nord-Est	4.876.205	3.098.854	2.334.165	0	305.108	80.087	379.494	69.854	1.707.497	1.584.425	123.072
Provincia Autonom	204.278	127.784	89.376	0	15.333	3.556	19.519	3.393	73.101	68.961	4.140
Provincia Autonom	222.445	139.883	106.905	0	13.673	3.177	16.128	1.648	80.914	75.882	5.032
Veneto	1.986.016	1.320.909	1.022.358	0	116.449	31.968	150.134	30.008	635.099	586.234	48.865
Friuli-Venezia Giu	547.451	333.267	249.951	0	30.438	8.900	43.978	6.099	208.085	194.939	13.146
Emilia-Romagna	1.916.015	1.177.011	865.575	0	129.215	32.486	149.735	28.706	710.298	658.409	51.889
Centro (IT)	4.894.956	3.065.325	2.290.713	0	242.832	98.530	433.250	95.490	1.734.141	1.590.573	143.568
Toscana	1.568.540	988.964	745.112	0	90.691	27.962	125.199	33.677	545.899	500.855	45.044
Umbria	367.316	233.272	183.283	0	15.089	6.128	28.772	8.808	125.236	115.304	9.932
Marche	624.576	410.912	318.634	0	32.275	10.467	49.536	13.869	199.795	182.998	16.797
Lazio	2.334.524	1.432.177	1.043.684	0	104.777	53.973	229.743	39.136	863.211	791.416	71.795
Sud	5.248.838	3.653.029	2.956.998	0	161.401	97.500	437.130	90.794	1.505.015	1.360.594	144.421
Abruzzo	523.901	344.700	275.369	0	17.272	9.818	42.241	9.607	169.594	155.067	14.527
Molise	128.137	83.229	68.236	0	3.128	2.341	9.524	1.337	43.571	40.455	3.116
Campania	2.060.307	1.459.499	1.164.609	0	60.963	43.469	190.458	49.940	550.868	486.381	64.487
Puglia	1.533.352	1.094.159	901.252	0	51.795	24.383	116.729	21.736	417.457	380.895	36.562
Basilicata	230.176	154.362	129.030	0	5.132	3.767	16.433	1.734	74.080	68.161	5.919
Calabria	772.965	517.080	418.502	0	23.111	13.722	61.745	6.440	249.445	229.635	19.810
Isole	2.640.023	1.765.419	1.411.319	0	94.311	45.467	214.322	32.121	842.483	774.150	68.333
Sicilia	1.963.411	1.332.276	1.079.610	0	68.739	32.805	151.122	24.031	607.104	559.021	48.083
Sardegna	676.612	433.143	331.709	0	25.572	12.662	63.200	8.090	235.379	215.129	20.250

FIGURE 96. POPULATIONS AND HOUSING CENSUS. DATA ON FAMILIES AND HOUSEHOLDS

⁹¹ Source: <https://arera.it/it/dati/gm64.htm> [access date: 8 May 2020]

GEO/HHCOMP	Total	Household composed of one-family nucleus	Household composed of married couple	Household composed of couple in registered partnership	Household composed of couple in consensual union	Household composed of lone father living with at least one child	Household composed of lone mother living with at least one child	Household composed of two-or-more-family nucleus	Household composed of non-family nucleus	One-person household	Multiperson household other than family nucleus
Italy	17.691.895	11.985.790	9.591.560	0	767.791	314.497	1.311.942	247.633	5.458.472	5.034.731	423.741
Nord-Ovest	4.991.957	3.323.752	2.634.482	0	258.008	82.117	349.145	43.403	1.624.802	1.513.643	111.159
Piemonte	1.359.171	894.086	708.866	0	69.669	23.000	92.551	11.568	453.517	424.506	29.011
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée	38.940	23.918	18.115	0	2.525	592	2.686	231	14.791	14.079	712
Liguria	524.223	301.569	230.469	0	20.561	9.819	40.720	4.763	217.891	203.263	14.628
Lombardia	3.069.623	2.104.179	1.677.032	0	165.253	48.706	213.188	26.841	938.603	871.795	66.808
Nord-Est	3.602.685	2.425.204	1.901.680	0	204.805	61.051	257.668	53.494	1.123.987	1.040.663	83.324
Provincia Autonoma	139.995	94.877	70.798	0	9.541	2.691	11.847	2.785	42.333	39.606	2.727
Provincia Autonoma	163.729	107.968	86.430	0	8.358	2.449	10.731	929	54.832	51.392	3.440
Veneto	1.509.773	1.059.892	849.126	0	79.456	24.920	106.390	23.931	425.950	391.780	34.170
Friuli-Venezia Giu	420.806	271.067	211.135	0	21.354	7.106	31.472	4.750	144.989	135.584	9.405
Emilia-Romagna	1.368.382	891.400	684.191	0	86.096	23.885	97.228	21.099	455.883	422.301	33.582
Centro (IT)	3.581.185	2.335.981	1.817.895	0	159.969	71.602	286.515	72.146	1.173.058	1.078.811	94.247
Toscana	1.157.056	762.360	597.900	0	60.411	20.621	83.428	25.516	369.180	338.956	30.224
Umbria	271.858	181.757	148.012	0	9.640	4.711	19.394	7.273	82.828	75.938	6.890
Marche	475.201	325.724	261.118	0	22.111	8.126	34.369	10.928	138.549	126.911	11.638
Lazio	1.677.070	1.066.140	810.865	0	67.807	38.144	149.324	28.429	582.501	537.006	45.495
Sud	3.615.983	2.597.826	2.164.975	0	91.159	66.854	274.838	57.649	960.508	872.802	87.706
Abruzzo	393.226	266.925	220.113	0	10.750	7.304	28.758	7.558	118.743	109.239	9.504
Molise	98.745	66.339	55.782	0	1.967	1.807	6.783	1.050	31.356	29.182	2.174
Campania	1.276.222	931.663	764.347	0	30.638	27.382	109.296	28.628	315.931	280.561	35.370
Puglia	1.136.469	832.775	705.850	0	30.957	17.890	78.078	14.660	289.034	264.743	24.291
Basilicata	170.624	119.930	102.503	0	3.200	2.824	11.403	1.299	49.395	45.326	4.069
Calabria	540.697	380.194	316.380	0	13.647	9.647	40.520	4.454	156.049	143.751	12.298
Isole	1.900.085	1.303.027	1.072.528	0	53.850	32.873	143.776	20.941	576.117	528.812	47.305
Sicilia	1.378.431	957.590	797.313	0	37.739	23.120	99.418	15.002	405.839	373.908	31.931
Sardegna	521.654	345.437	275.215	0	16.111	9.753	44.358	5.939	170.278	154.904	15.374

FIGURE 97. PRIVATE HOUSEHOLDS BY TYPE, TENURE STATUS AND NUTS 2 REGION: TOTAL, OWNER

GEO/HOUSING	Conventional dwellings	Less than 15 years	From 15 to 29 years
Italy	58.921.309	8.294.037	9.134.345
Nord-Ovest	15.616.405	2.138.047	2.172.487
Piemonte	4.315.119	561.528	587.256
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	125.499	17.660	17.464
Liguria	1.554.507	180.075	192.586
Lombardia	9.621.280	1.378.784	1.375.181
Nord-Est	11.326.220	1.586.122	1.591.244
Provincia Autonoma di Bolzano	494.756	82.646	83.693
Provincia Autonoma di Trento	516.967	80.439	79.949
Veneto	4.805.779	690.127	698.077
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	1.205.555	153.548	158.459
Emilia-Romagna	4.303.163	579.362	571.066
Centro (IT)	11.482.094	1.542.940	1.657.858
Toscana	3.644.369	467.961	490.224
Umbria	877.311	114.851	126.639
Marche	1.531.607	205.528	225.575
Lazio	5.428.807	754.600	815.420
Sud	13.896.666	2.082.350	2.542.660
Abruzzo	1.297.955	169.089	207.440
Molise	311.796	38.911	51.808
Campania	5.731.602	928.403	1.102.417
Puglia	4.032.329	591.821	715.742
Basilicata	574.449	76.532	101.135
Calabria	1.948.535	277.594	364.118
Isole	6.599.924	944.578	1.170.096
Sicilia	4.971.422	745.055	912.529

FIGURE 98. POPULATIONS AND HOUSING CENSUS. DATA ON POPULATION BY HOUSING ARRANGEMENTS. AGE OF PEOPLE

7.4.3 Climatic factors

Climatic Zones (Italy)

The Italian territory divides itself into the following six climatic zones that vary according to the degree-days regardless of the geographical location, as shown in the picture in the left.

The climatic classification of Italian municipalities was introduced to regulate the operation and the period of operation of the heating systems of buildings for containment purposes of energy consumption. The degree-day (GG) of a location is the unit of measurement that estimates the energy needs needed to

maintain a comfortable climate in homes. It represents the sum, extended to all the days of a conventional annual heating period, of the average daily temperature increases necessary to reach the threshold of 20 ° C. The higher the GG value, the greater the need to keep the heating system on.

The Italian demo case is located near Bologna, in Emilia-Romagna region, in the climatic zone E.

Climatic zone	Degree-days	Period	Number of hours
A	municipality with GG ≤ 600	December 1st – March 15th	6 daily hours
B	600 < municipality with GG ≤ 900	December 1st – March 31th	8 daily hours
C	900 < municipality with GG ≤ 1.400	November 15th - March 31th	10 daily hours
D	1.400 < municipality with GG ≤ 2.100	November 1st - April 15th	12 daily hours
E	2.100 < municipality with GG ≤ 3.000	15th October – 15th April	14 daily hours
F	municipality with GG > 3.000	all year	No limit

FIGURE 99. CHARACTERISTICS OF CLIMATIC ZONES

Zone	Number of municipalities	% of municipalities	Inhabitant 2018	% Inhabitant
A	2	0,03%	23.266	0,04%
B	157	1,98%	3.217.288	5,33%
C	981	12,40%	12.826.700	21,25%
D	1.572	19,86%	15.168.668	25,13%
E	4.176	52,77%	27.482.108	45,53%
F	1.026	12,96%	1.641.892	2,72%

FIGURE 100. "SIZE" OF CLIMATIC ZONES. ORIGINAL PROCESSING ON DATA ENEA-ISTAT

Solar Radiation (Italy)

Solar energy is a very important renewable energy source on the national territory.

FIGURE 101. GLOBAL SOLAR RADIATION (MIN/AVG/MAX) ON THE GROUND INTEGRATED ANNUALLY AND AGGREGATED ON A REGIONAL BASIS. 2005-2015. GRAPHIC ELABORATIONS AND DATA SOURCE: RSE (SOURCE: RDS 16002400)

FIGURE 102. GLOBAL SOLAR RADIATION ON THE GROUND INTEGRATED ANNUALLY AND AGGREGATED ON A MUNICIPAL BASIS. AVG 2005-2015 AND 2015. GRAPHIC ELABORATIONS AND DATA SOURCE: RSE (SOURCE: RDS 16002400)

Since the contribution of non-programmable renewable sources (FRNP), such as photovoltaics, is continuously growing and energy storage systems are not yet widespread in Italy in proportion to the plants powered by renewable sources connected to the network, this increases the risk of instability of the electrical system accordingly, due to the imbalances that are created between the production and consumption of the energy fed into the network. Therefore, to reduce the uncertainty related to the exploitation of these type of energy sources, SunRiSE has been developed as an instrument that allows monitoring and forecasting. SunRiSE is a web-GIS portal developed by RSE (Energy System Research), a joint-stock company of the GSE Group, which is proposed as a design tool for consulting data measurements, satellite estimates and forecasts of primary sources of generation from non-programmable renewables, in particular related to solar and wind energies.

The visualization of the consultation data takes place through the activation of different GIS layers, which are represented in the basic cartography of the Italian territory. It is possible to consult the maps of global solar radiation on the ground, in particular the solar irradiance relative to the day before, the accumulated annual energy incident on the horizontal plane for every year since 2005 and, for each year, the 12 monthly maps of the accumulated daily energy.

Forecast maps are also available for up to 2 days from that of reading the data, based on the RAMS weather model, which operationally runs in RSE machines, using data analysis from the European meteorological centre ECMWF. Specifically, the forecasts are provided both for the solar source, through the GHI (Global Horizontal Irradiance) and the DNI (Direct Normal Irradiance), and for the wind source, providing the wind speed estimated at 10 meters from the ground.

FIGURE 103. RSE SOLAR ATLAS, FORECAST AND HISTORICAL DATA. SOURCE: [HTTP://SUNRISE.RSE-WEB.IT/](http://sunrise.rse-web.it/)

The tool has been recently integrated with new levels of information, providing for:

- Wind speed at different heights (10, 25, 50, 75, 100 m above the ground)
- Precipitation intensity
- Air temperature 2 m above the ground
- Photovoltaic production:
 - by market area
 - by province
 - by municipality
- Electric load (actual load)

FIGURE 104. RSE SOLAR ATLAS, FORECAST AND HISTORICAL DATA. NEW FEATURES.

Emilia-Romagna region. Data Sets and Climate change perspective

In the Emilia-Romagna, as the Mediterranean demo region of CULTURAL-E, regional climate forecast datasets are available on the ARPAE [open data](https://arpaepv.datamb.it/dataset/erg5-eraclito) website⁹². ARPAE is Regional Agency for Prevention, Environment and Energy of Emilia-Romagna.

⁹² Source: <https://arpaepv.datamb.it/dataset/erg5-eraclito> <https://arera.it/it/dati/gm64.htm> [access date: 8 May 2020]

FIGURE 105 - AVERAGE EXTERNAL TEMPERATURE AND RAINFALL YEARS 1961-2015

It is evident from current trends and future projections that climate is changing at an annual rate. As the last IPCC report underlined (IPCC - AR4, 2007), “the warming of the climate system is unequivocal”.

FIGURE 106 - MAXIMUM AVERAGE ANNUAL TEMPERATURES YEARS 1961-2015 AND ANOMALIES FOR THE MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM TEMPERATURES YEARS 1971-2000

This connects to the idea that, aiming at designing adaptation strategies over a region, the first action consists of defining the ‘actual or expected climatic stimuli’, which requires to develop a detailed study of present and future climate variability at regional level. It is evident that to characterise the climate system, concerning the climate profile at local scale, the integration of the results obtained over a larger area is required.

FIGURE 107 - SCENARIOS FOR INCREASING THE MINIMUM TEMPERATURES IN WINTER AND MAXIMUM TEMPERATURES IN SUMMER

FIGURE 108 - SEASONAL MAX. AND MIN. TEMPERATURE

FIGURE 109 - EXTREME CLIMATE EPISODES (ICE AND HEAT WAVES) IN A MAJOR REGIONAL CITY

7.4.4 Literature review

The influence of occupant's behaviour in a high performing building

The Italian research group, Fabi et al. (2013) focuses on the possible profiles of occupant behaviour and their resulting effects on energy consumption in a high performing building. Even though the building is not located in an EU country, the analysis provides interesting insights regarding the influence of a set point thermostat.

'Energy consumption doesn't linearly increase accordingly to the occupant's frequency of interaction with a set-point controller. The figure shows the trend of the 10 provable simulations: the maximum variation respect to the standard deterministic model is about 6% with passive users. A high discrepancy has been obtained in terms of interaction with the thermostat set-point: the active users change it more frequently and it results in a wide temperature range (from 19°C to 26°C), while the medium and passive user types interact less frequently (and the temperature range is from 20°C to 21°C)'.

FIGURE 110 – THE SIMULATED THERMAL ZONES

FIGURE 111 – THE SIMULATED HEATING SET-POINT PREFERENCES.

A framework for NZEB design in Mediterranean climate: Design, building and set-up monitoring of a lab-small villa

The Italian group of research composed by Ascione et al. (2019) focused on a single-family house (called BNZEB), placed in south Italy and specifically designed for a Mediterranean climate. Finally, the replicability of BNZEB design in Mediterranean cities, like Lisbon, Montpellier, Madrid, Seville and Athens is evaluated.

FIGURE 112 – COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASURED VALUES AND SIMULATED VALUES: (A) ENERGY DEMAND FOR HEATING AND COOLING NEEDS, (B) ENERGY GENERATION FROM PV SYSTEM.

FIGURE 113 – COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASURED VALUES AND SIMULATED VALUES: (A) AIR TEMPERATURE INSIDE THE LIVING ROOM, (B) RELATIVE HUMIDITY INSIDE THE LIVING ROOM.

FIGURE 114 – MONTHLY ENERGY DEMAND AND GENERATION FROM PV SYSTEM FOR CITIES CONSIDERED ACROSS SOUTH EUROPE.

Overview and future challenges of nearly zero energy buildings (NZEB) design in Southern Europe

In the study, Attia et al. (2017) analyses the present situation and provides an overview on future prospects for Near Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) in Southern Europe. The result presents an overview of challenges and provides recommendations based on available empirical evidence to further lower those barriers in the European construction sector.

Attia et al. (2017: 1) stated that ‘reaching NZEB requires that we change our rules of thumb and design assumptions of the real potential of bioclimatic architecture and passive design in mixed-mode and cooling dominated climates. We need new and different concepts that are geo-climatically developed respecting climate sensitivity and avoiding overheating risks.’

Country	Climate Zone	Min. Energy Efficiency		Primary Energy kWh/m ² .a	RES share	Summer Climate Cities	2010–2015		Latitude	Altitude
		Energy need for Cooling kWh/m ² .a	Energy need for Heating kWh/m ² .a				CDD 25 °C	HDD 20 °C		
Cyprus	1	100–120	15	100	30%	Larnaca	125.7	1051	34.5°N	26 m
	2					Nicosia	304.2	1253	35.1°N	220 m
	1					Paphos	29.3	1039	34.8°N	72 m
	4					Prodrornos	8.5	2831	34.6°N	1380 m
France ^a	H1a	5–20	5–20	50	50%	Paris	75	2294	48.8°N	35 m
	H1b					Strasbourg	123	2843	48.5°N	150 m
	H1c					Lyon	155	2142	45.7°N	200 m
	H2b					Nantes	57	2063	47.2°N	26 m
	H2c					Toulouse	158	1777	43.6°N	150 m
	H3					Marsilia	257	1381	43.2°N	42 m
	D					Kozani	51	2844	40.3°N	710 m
Greece	C	80	80	100	25%	Thessaloniki	135	2110	40.6°N	7 m
	B					Athens	228	1321	38°N	194 m
	A					Iraklion	115	1064	35.3°N	35 m
Italy	A	15	15	120	50%	Lampedusa	368	1060	35.3°N	20 m
	B					Palermo	362	1570	38.1°N	14 m
	C					Napoli	336	1803	40.5°N	72 m
	D					Rome	234	1405	41.9°N	13 m
	E					Milan	168	2439	45.2°N	121 m
	F					Bolzano	245	3552	46.5°N	262 m
Portugal	1	0	30	33	50%	Porto	27	1250	41.9°N	94 m
	2	15	40			Lisbon	61	1093	38.8°N	114 m
	3	30	70			Faro	77	606	37°N	72 m
Romania	1	15	15	120	10%	Constanta	151	2363	44.2°N	40 m
	1					Timisoara	223	2595	43.2°N	87 m
	2					Bucharest	261	2633	44.4°N	77 m
	3					Cluj-Napoca	134	2974	46.7°N	380 m
	4					Brasov	0	6876	45.6°N	610 m
Spain	D3	10	10	60	60%	Madrid	106	2306	40.4°N	667 m
	C2	10	10			Barcelona	53	1597	41.3°N	12 m
	E1	5	15			Burgos	1	3407	42.2°N	859 m
	A4	15	5			Huelva	141	1205	37.15°N	24 m

Note: The baselines applied for the HDD and CDD calculation are 20 °C and 25 °C data from the 2010–2015 was used. The hourly approach shows a significant CDD change regarding day/night variation compared to the HDD.

^a In France, 26 °C is for air-conditioned buildings. For non-air-conditioned buildings, inner temperature should be lower than the reference indoor temperature (TIC REF) during 5 days. TIC REF is determined by standard computation and is depending of the climatic zone.

FIGURE 115 – SUGGESTION FOR NZEB PERFORMANCE THRESHOLD IN SOUTHERN EUROPE'S MEMBER STATES.

Extracting influencing Factors of Occupant Behaviour by Means of a Questionnaire Survey

In this research study, Rinaldi et al. (2018: 1) underline that 'occupants have a notable impact on the building's performance and hence on the energy consumption. High values of the set-point temperature and of the total hours of heating system utilization by occupants cause more energy consumption. In this context, it was shown that especially the construction period of the building affected the occupants' behaviours: in the oldest buildings, the occupants use the heating system for more hours and with higher set-point temperature values, and therefore cause a high fuel consumption. Hence, the common practice of designers to assume fixed set-point temperature and occupants' action independent of the building characteristics, leads to discrepancies between predicted energy consumptions and observed ones. This is an important and new finding, showing that models of occupant behaviour for NZEB buildings cannot be the same for buildings of different construction periods.'

FIGURE 116 – PERCENTAGE OF OCCUPANT BEHAVIOURS FOR THERMAL DISCOMFORT IN WINTER IN FUNCTION OF THE CONSTRUCTION YEAR.

FIGURE 117 – PERCENTAGE OF OCCUPANT BEHAVIOURS FOR THERMAL DISCOMFORT IN SUMMER IN FUNCTION OF THE CONSTRUCTION YEAR.

Behavioural variables and occupancy patterns in the design and modelling of Nearly Zero Energy Buildings

The aim of the study from Carpino et al. (2017: 1) was to assess ‘the influence of housing occupancy patterns on the definition of residential NZEB in Italian climatic conditions [...] according to the National Standards. Successively, different conditions of the building’s usage are analysed using dynamic energy simulations that allow exploration of the different occupation modes. The variability of the family composition and the occupancy scenarios are defined based on the data collected in the specific context. The investigation provides information regarding the effects of human variables (occupants’ needs and preferences) on the final energy performance of low energy

buildings and highlights the combination of variables that are important in the definition of NZEB as net zero source energy’.

FIGURE 118 – OCCUPANCY PROFILES FOR TWO OCCUPANCY SCENARIOS FOR AN AVERAGE WEEKDAY

FIGURE 119 – INFLUENCE OF SEPARATED ENERGY USES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION UPON VARIATION OF FAMILY SIZE, OCCUPANTS’ BEHAVIOUR, AND EQUIPMENT TYPOLOGY

Influence of occupant behaviour lifestyle on an Italian social housing

Becchio et al. (2016: 1034) stated that ‘occupant behaviour lifestyle is one of the most significant driving factors of uncertainty in the prediction of building energy use and thus represents a fundamental aspect that is necessary to modelling. This study examines the difference between the energy consumptions assessed during the design phase and the monitored ones for social housing. A dynamic simulation was employed to demonstrate the impact of occupant behaviour lifestyles and household composition on energy uses.’

FIGURE 120 – INFLUENCE OF SEPARATED ENERGY USES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION UPON VARIATION OF FAMILY SIZE, OCCUPANTS’ BEHAVIOUR, AND EQUIPMENT TYPOLOGY

FIGURE 121 – INFLUENCE OF SEPARATED ENERGY USES ON FINAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION UPON VARIATION OF FAMILY SIZE, OCCUPANTS' BEHAVIOUR, AND EQUIPMENT TYPOLOGY\

Previous figures 'show the incidence of each single variable for these two types of household compositions on the total primary energy consumptions by defining the percentage of low and high consumer lifestyles compared to the average profile for each single energy-related behaviour pattern. For all scenarios, the most influencing occupant-driven variable on energy consumptions is constituted by the temperature set-point and operation-time' (Becchio et.al, 2016: 1039). 'The internal comfort conditions could be achieved even if the indoor temperature is changed (from 21°C to 18°C). This is possible by just modifying the clothing thermal insulation from 1 clo to 1.5 clo in order to achieve the perfect thermal neutrality coincident with comfort satisfaction. In this way, the PMV (Predicted Mean Vote) remains between -0.5 and +0.5. Just in order to not pass the limit of PPD (Predicted Percentage of Dissatisfied) of 10%, the thermal insulation of clothing could decrease to 1.1 clo. Furthermore, nowadays numerous recent studies are focused on the correlation between the temperature and health benefits. An example is represented by analyses made by Stanford Medicine Centre for Sleep Sciences and Medicine that show how sleep with an internal temperature between 16 °C and 18 °C is healthier' (Becchio et.al, 2016: 1040).

7.4.5 Considerations

Some relevant socio-technical elements from the Mediterranean climate could be summarised as follows, e.g. Italy as CULTURAL-E demo case:

Data from monitored buildings	Data at National Level	Socio-economic factors	Indoor preferences
<p>High-efficient Building Example, Milan (Italy): Energy consumption in kwh/(m2/y) - Space heating: 21,2 - Space cooling: 14 - Lighting & ventilation: 6 - Water heating: 66,8</p>	<p>Share of final energy consumption 2017, by type of end-use: - Space heating – 67,5% - Space cooling – 0,7% - Lighting & appliances – 18,6 % - Water heating – 11,9% - Other end-uses – 1,4%</p>	<p>Available data for NUTS2 geocodes: - Population - Unemployment rate - GDP per habitant - Disposable income of households - Final energy consumption in household - Gas prices for household consumer - Electricity prices for household consumer</p>	<p>-The active users change it more frequently and it results in a wide temperature range (from 19°C to 26°C) - The medium and passive user types interact less frequently (and the temperature range is from 20°C to 21°C)</p>

8 Designing the 2CAP Energy Atlas. Functionalities & Insights

8.1 Description of envisioned features and functionalities

Several GIS applications are available and have been assessed as part of the activities conducted under WP2. The most relevant ones are described below:

First technology: RStudio lets users introduce ‘Shiny web applications’ and interactive documents online in the way that works best for their specific requirements. For ‘Shiny applications’, ‘Shiny Server’ should be considered. Project⁹³.

An example of ‘Shiny app’ implementation is the web-application of the iMONITRAF project, which serves to share spatial data about traffic and to provide analysis tools⁹⁴.

A second example which could serve as an inspiration is the decision support system developed by EURAC for the CERPlan project, based on ‘shiny server’ which shows one more possible layout for the Graphical User Interface (GUI).

FIGURE 122 - CERPLAN PROJECT WEBAPP SCREENSHOT

Another example, to demonstrate the potential of this technology, is the ExcEED platform⁹⁵ which includes a geo-clustering tool developed with the same technologies.

Second Technology: The Geonode data management system is a tool to manage and share spatial datasets with a powerful authorization system, metadata catalogue, etc. but minor analysis tool capabilities:

⁹³ Source: <https://rstudio.com/products/shiny/shiny-server/> [access date: 8 May 2020]

⁹⁴ Source: <http://sdi.eurac.edu/AlpinePoKforTransportandMobility/> [access date: 8 May 2020]

⁹⁵ Source: <http://www.exceedproject.eu/> [access date: 8 May 2020]

- Project⁹⁶.
- Online demo⁹⁷
- Example of GRETA project implementation⁹⁸

Third technology: [MapStore](#) is a highly modular open source WebGIS framework developed by [GeoSolutions](#) to create, manage and securely share maps and mashups. Mapstore is one component of the Geonode platform. After the first analysis based on the vision and functionalities foreseen, Mapstore is probably enough to satisfy all the CULTURAL-E requirements:

- Project⁹⁹
- Online demo¹⁰⁰

These technologies were identified as potential tools to be deployed to host the 2CAP Energy Atlas. A further assessment will be conducted upon defining the complete list of data sets and functionality to be managed and shared with the new web-application development.

The envisioned platform could be described by the following four conceptual ideas:

- 1- Including consumption data. Uses of energy and types for PEB:
 - a. Different areas and territories
 - b. Different time-space patterns of energy demand, in relation to the households' climatic locations and cultural clusters
 - c. Different types of buildings
 - d. Layer with existing PEB monitoring data (real information from inhabited buildings, R&D experimental buildings/demo sites, etc).
- 2- Providing snapshots in type:
 - a. Temporal dimension of energy consumptions
 - b. Energy domestic technologies, from the angle of the interrelation with human behaviours
 - c. Cultural dependencies (Comfort, Cleanliness and Convenience)
 - d. Climate change effects from energy uses intensity (i.e. increasing cooling and heating practices on energy consumption)
 - e. How do decades shift energy uses patterns? Accommodating this information into the atlas.
- 3- Sophistication of the tool. Meaning that various kinds of options and features should provide a key insight into design principles and criteria for PEB.
- 4- Source question. The tool will provide unique design advice on energy efficiency, building operability and real energy demand, by incorporating the

⁹⁶ Source: <http://geonode.org/> [access date: 10 May 2020]

⁹⁷ Source: <https://master.demo.geonode.org/> [access date: 10 May 2020]

⁹⁸ Source: <http://greta.eurac.edu/> [access date: 10 May 2020]

⁹⁹ Source: <https://mapstore.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> [access date: 10 May 2020]

¹⁰⁰ Source: <https://mapstore.geo-solutions.it/mapstore/#/> [access date: 10 May 2020]

energy available from renewable sources, aiming at preventing failure when designing PEB.

The Atlas should bring designers to new levels of knowledge; current experience should be captured and improved. A step further on from the Atlas design would be interviewing designers. The Atlas, as a data visualization library, would add questions to energy designers' daily practices.

8.2 Defining the expected outcomes from the 2CAP Energy Atlas for PEB design process

The main expected outcomes from the Atlas are related to building the criteria for PEBs which integrates the cultural and climatic variables related to energy demand. The Atlas aims to provide advice to building designers, as main target users, in the aspects described below, as well as how it links with the different project objectives identified in the section 1 of the document:

- Supporting Objective 1: Define cultural peculiarities related to European climates that strongly impact building energy consumption
 - Contributing to the understanding of current and future energy demand scenarios at household and building levels and how it varies in different climates and energy cultures.
- Supporting Objective 3: Develop climate and culturally tailored solution sets and technologies for Plus Energy Houses (PEHs).
 - Indicating conditions where particular technologies approaches might best be used or avoided
 - Supporting the dimensioning of RES responding to real energy demand at building level.
 - Bringing key criteria for dimensioning storage systems, depending on the time-space consideration of energy practices
- Supporting Objective 4: Understand the variables that building users bring to buildings, and provide interventions designed to shift energy using specific practices.
 - Informing operability and interface design of the BMS depending on cultural-climatic patterns and practices.
- Supporting Objective 5: Identify and evaluate the co-benefits (on top of financial benefits) from Plus Energy Buildings and proposed technologies
 - Characterisation of comfort level standards in consideration of the cultural and climatic factors driving household expectations.

9 Overview of the process & Conclusions

The assessment of climate and cultural differences in energy use of domestic buildings included a number of stages. In the first stage, the organisations participating in the project discussed and agreed the research scope and the definition of the cultural and climatic variables. Then, the research was designed in detail, identifying sources and availability of data. After the initial literature review, an ideation phase helped to develop the vision of the 2CAP Energy Atlas and its expected outcomes. The second stage focused on defining the structure of the various elements of the research study, followed by the meta-analysis of the literature review on the selected topics. The research provided an improved understanding of cultural and climatic variables affecting energy demand and how these findings could contribute to define criteria for successful design of PEBs.

The findings from the research states that energy demand is not only a result of human behaviour. Instead, it is a function of social, technical, behavioural and cultural elements. One way to describe how people use buildings is through the practices they perform in daily life which include knowledge, meanings, materialities, technologies, rules, etc. In most cases, energy demand is related to:

- conscious decisions related to caring for the self or others
- unconscious, repeated, daily practices that are framed by social and cultural rules, conventions and values.

In the vast majority of cases, energy demand is not a selfish issue, or an act related to luxury. It is a fact of meeting basic standards of society, because of community energy practices are unconsciously influencing to the purpose of domestic energy use. (e.g. daily showering, ventilation practices, etc). Energy is necessary to meet basic societal standards. Energy is not a commodity or a personal preference and community energy practices are a key factor in influencing domestic energy use.

Energy efficiency becomes not only a question related to the design or functionality of the smart home app or the quality of the real time data provided. **Energy demand is configured primarily by daily practices, rather than by the provision of energy related information.**

This report thus brings new ways of understanding the nature of building energy performance as it relates to social and cultural life. It addresses the gap between building design expectations and the reality of household energy performance. This gap exists both as a result of the difference in understanding of energy demand and the ways in which energy efficiency is viewed as a technology intervention. Hence, **there is a need to adopt frames such as social practices to help explain and accommodate the broader social and cultural parameters that structure energy demand.** In order to drive the widespread uptake of PEB, it is fundamental to consider not only the

Deliverable n° 2.1
Climate and cultural differences in energy use
in domestic buildings

adoption of smart user-centred technologies, but also the temporal variations in energy demand, and the spatial variations across climate zones, and cultures.

References

- i. Ackermann, T. (2020) Energy demand versus energy consumption taking in account of long-term temperature measurements. *Bauphysik* 42, booklet 1
- ii. Altman I., A. Rapoport and J. F. Wohlwill (1980) - *Human Behavior and Environment* - Published in Volume 4: *Environment and Culture*, New York, Springer Science+Business Media, LLC.
- iii. Anable, J., Anderson, B., Shove, E. and Torriti, J. (2014) *Categories, Concepts and Units: Representing energy demand in and through time*. Working Paper 3, Lancaster: DEMAND Centre
- iv. Anderson, B. (2016). *What makes peak electricity demand? Insights from time use analysis*. Lancaster University, Demand Centre: www.demand.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/11/DEMAND-insight-1-peak-electricity-final.pdf
- v. Andersson K., I. Fagerlund, L. Bodin, B. Ydreborg, *Questionnaire as an instrument when evaluating indoor climate*, in: *Healthy Buildings 88 Stockholm* (1988) 139–146.
- vi. Arrindell W.A., *Book review of Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions, and organizations across nations* by G. Hofstede, *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, col. 41, pp. 861–862, 2003.
- vii. Ascione, F., Borrelli, M., De Masi, R., Rossi, F. and Vanoli, G.P. (2019). *A framework for NZEB design in Mediterranean climate: Design, building and set-up monitoring of a lab-small villa*. *Solar Energy*. 184. 11-29. 10.1016/j.solener.2019.03.083.
- viii. Attia, Shady & Eleftheriou, Polyvios & Xeni, Flouris & Rodolphe, Morlot & Ménézo, Christophe & Kostopoulos, Vassilis & Betsi, Maria & Kalaitzoglou, Iakovos & Pagliano, Lorenzo & Cellura, Maurizio & Almeida, Manuela & Ferreira, Marco & Baracu, Tudor & Badescu, Viorel & Crutescu, Ruxandra & Hidalgo Betanzos, Juan. (2017). *Overview and future challenges of nearly Zero Energy Buildings (nZEB) design in Southern Europe*. *Energy and Buildings*. 155. 10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.09.043.
- ix. Barton, B., Blackwell, S., Carrington, G., Ford, R., Lawson, R., Stephenson, J., Thorsnes, P. and Williams, J. (2013) – “*Energy Cultures: Implication for Policymakers*” – University of Otago, New Zealand
- x. *BBSR 2007 - Healthy Living*, Selbstverlag des Bundesamtes für Bauwesen und Raumordnung, 2007
- xi. Becchio, Cristina & Bello, C. & Corgnati, Stefano & Ingaramo, L.. (2016). *Influence of Occupant Behaviour Lifestyle on an Italian Social Housing*. *Energy Procedia*. 101. 1034-1041. 10.1016/j.egypro.2016.11.131.
- xii. Becchio, Cristina & Bello, C. & Corgnati, Stefano & Ingaramo, L.. (2016). *Influence of Occupant Behaviour Lifestyle on an Italian Social Housing*. *Energy Procedia*. 101. 1034-1041. 10.1016/j.egypro.2016.11.131. Behar C. (2016). *A socio technical perspective of ventilation practices in UK social housing with*

- whole house ventilation systems; design, everyday life and change - UCL Energy Institute
- xiii. Belaïd, Fateh, Haitham Joumni, Behavioral attitudes towards energy saving: Empirical evidence from France, *Energy Policy*, Volume 140, 2020, 111406, ISSN 0301-4215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111406>.
 - xiv. Berge Magnar, Georges Laurent, Mathisen Hans Martin (2016) On the oversupply of heat to bedrooms during winter in highly insulated dwellings with heat recovery ventilation. *Building and Environment*, Volume:106, Pages:389-401.
 - xv. Berge, Magnar & Mathisen, Hans Martin (2015) - The suitability of air-heating in residential passive house buildings from the occupants' point of view – a review, *Advances in Building Energy Research*, 9:2, 175-189, DOI: 10.1080/17512549.2015.1040069
 - xvi. Berge, Magnar, Mathisen, Hans Martin (2016) - Perceived and measured indoor climate conditions in high-performance residential buildings.
 - xvii. Brager, G. and de Dear, R. "Historical and Cultural Influences on Comfort Expectations," in *Buildings, Culture and Environment: Informing Local and Global Practices*, L. R. Cole R.J., Ed., Wiley-Blackwell, 2008, pp. 177-201.
 - xviii. Carlander, J et. al (2019) – "Integration of Measurements and Time Diaries as Complementary Measures to Improve Resolution of BES" – *Energies* 2019.
 - xix. Carpino, Cristina & Mora, Dafni & Arcuri, Natale & De Simone, Marilena. (2017). Behavioral variables and occupancy patterns in the design and modeling of Nearly Zero Energy Buildings. *Building Simulation*. 10. 10.1007/s12273-017-0371-2.
 - i. Cass, N. and Shove, E. (2017) – Changing energy demand -Concepts, metaphors and implications for policy – Insights across DEMAND Centre
 - ii. D'Agostino D. (2017) - Criteria and structure of a harmonised data collection for NZEBs retrofit buildings in Europe - Conference paper published in *Energy Procedia* 140 (2017) 170 – 181
 - iii. Dena (2017): Thermal comfort in the low energy house, Deutsche Energie-Agentur GmbH, 02/2007
 - iv. DIN V 18599-10: Boundary conditions of use for calculation of energy demand of buildings
 - v. Khovalyg D., Kazanci O. B., Halvorsen H., Gundlach i., Bahnfleth W. P., Toftum J., Olesen B. W. "Critical review of standards for indoor thermal environment and air quality" *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 213, 2020, 109819, ISSN 0378-7788, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.109819>
 - vi. Douglas M., Wildavsky A.B. (1982) - Risk and Culture: An Essay on the Selection of Technical and Environmental Dangers. University of California Press, Berkeley (CA).
 - vii. Douglas (1982) - Natural Symbols: Explorations in Cosmology. Barrie & Rockliff, London.

- viii. DSFA (2009) Department of Social and Family Affairs - Effectiveness of Domestic Energy Efficiency Programmes, DSFA, Dublin.
- ix. Dubois, Ghislain, Sovacool et. al (2019) - It starts at home? Climate policies targeting household consumption and behavioural decisions are key to low-carbon futures - *Energy Research and Social Science*, 52. pp. 144-158.
- x. Druckman, A. and Jackson, T. (2008) Household energy consumption in the UK: A highly geographically and socio-economically disaggregated model. *Energy Policy*, 36(8): 3177-3192.
- xi. ENERGISE (2019) – European Network for Research, Good Practice and Innovation for Sustainable Energy, Grant Agreement No. 727642. Deliverable No. 1.3: Publication of conceptual framework. Everyday practices, cultural conventions and energy use: researching new opportunities for reducing domestic energy use in Europe.
- xii. Eggen, B., Van Den Hoven, E., and Terken, J., 2014. Human-Centered Design and Smart Homes: How to Study and Design for the Home Experience? In *Handbook of Smart Homes, Health Care and Well-Being*, 1-9. DOI = http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-01904-8_6-1.
- xiii. Ellegård, Kajsa. *Time Geography* (2017) DOI: 10.1093/OBO/9780199874002-0161
- xiv. Erickson, R. (1997) - Paper or Plastic? Energy, Environment and Consumerism in Sweden and America. Praeger: Westport
- xv. Fabi, Valentina & D'Oca, Simona & Buso, Tiziana & Corgnati, Stefano. (2013). The influence of occupant's behaviour in a high performing building.
- xvi. Fateh Belaïd, Understanding the spectrum of domestic energy consumption: Empirical evidence from France, *Energy Policy*, Volume 92, 2016, Pages 220-233, ISSN 0301-4215, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.02.015>.
- xvii. Fox, E., Foulds, C. and Robison, R. (2017) Energy & the active consumer - a social sciences and humanities cross-cutting theme report. Cambridge: SHAPE ENERGY.
- xviii. Geertz C, (1973) - The interpretation of cultures: selected essays. Basic Books, New York
- xix. Georges, L., Wena K., Alonso, M. J., Berge, M., Thomsen J., Wang, R. (2016) Simplified space-heating distribution using radiators in super-insulated apartment buildings.
- xx. Gøransson, Markus (2014) Sentrale styringssystemer i husholdninger - Produsenten og sluttbrukers syn på hva styringssystemer gjør, bør gjøre og vil gjøre i fremtiden
- xxi. Goulart, S. and T. Pitta (1994). Advanced topics in Bioclimatology to building design, regarding environmental comfort. Florianopolis: PPGEC-UFSC PPGEC-UFSC)
- xxii. Hägerstrand, 1976 - Geography and the study of interaction between nature and society - *Geoforum* 7, p 334

- xxiii. Heiskanen, E., Johnson, M., Robinson, S., Vadovics, E. and Saastamoinen, M. (2010) Low-carbon communities as a context for individual behavioural change. *Energy Policy*, 38(12): 7586-7595.
- xxiv. Hertwich, E. (2005) Consumption and the Rebound Effect. An Industrial Ecology Perspective. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 9(1-2): 85-98.
- xxv. Heath, Chip, Richard P. Larrick, and George Wu, "Goals as Reference Points," *Cognitive Psychology*, 1999, 38 (1), 79–109.
- xxvi. Hiroki S. - Energy/Culture: a reading guide for historical literature. Published in Spring 2018, *The Material Culture of Energy*. Article DOI: /10.15180/180912
- xxvii. Hofstede G. (1980) - *Culture's Consequences: International Differences in Work-Related Values*, Beverly Hills, CA: Sage.
- xxviii. Hofstede G. (1991) - *Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind*, London: McGraw-Hill.
- xxix. Hofstede G. (2001) - *Culture's consequences: Comparing values, behaviors, institutions, and organizations across nations* - Sage Publications.
- xxx. Horta A., Wilhite H., Schmidt L. and Bartiaux F., "Socio-technical and cultural approaches to energy consumption: An introduction," *Nature and Culture*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 115-121, 2014.
- xxxi. Hsiaw, Alice. (2013). Goal-setting and self-control. *Journal of Economic Theory*. 148. 601–626. 10.1016/j.jet.2012.08.001.
- xxxii. Hulme, M. (2015) - *Climate and its changes: a cultural appraisal*. 2015, 2, 1–11 doi: 10.1002/geo2.5
- xxxiii. IEA (2019), *Energy Efficiency Indicators 2019*, IEA, Paris www.iea.org/reports/energy-efficiency-indicators-2019
- xxxiv. Jalas, M. (2002) A time-use perspective on the materials intensity of consumption, *Ecological Economics*, 41: 109–23.
- xxxv. Jalas, M. (2005) The everyday life context of increasing energy demands: Time use survey data in a decomposition analysis. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 9(1-2): 129-145.
- xxxvi. Jensen, C. L. (2017) - Understanding energy efficient lighting as an outcome of dynamics of social practices. *Journal of Cleaner Production* (accepted for publication).
- xxxvii. Jensen et al. (2018) - 30 National summary briefs of national energy supply and demand. ENERGISE – European Network for Research, Good Practice and Innovation for Sustainable Energy, Grant Agreement No.727642, Deliverable 2.5.
- xxxviii. GE2O Project (2013) - Final publishable summary report Geo-clustering to deploy the potential of Energy efficient Buildings across EU, Grant Agreement No.285501
- xxxix. Jensen R.H. et al (2018). Designing the Desirable Smart Home: A Study of Household Experiences and Energy Consumption Impacts. Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3173578

- xi. Jochem, E., Sathaye, J. and Bouille, D. (Eds.) *Society, Behaviour and Climate Change Mitigation*, Kluwer, London.
- xli. Jones R. V., Fuertes A., Lomas K. J. (2015) -The socio-economic, dwelling and appliance related factors affecting electricity consumption in domestic buildings, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, Volume 43, 2015, Pages 901-917, ISSN 1364-0321, doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.084
- xlii. Lappegard H., Åshild, T., Thomas, J & B, (2011) User evaluations of energy efficient buildings: Literature review and further research, *Advances in Building Energy Research*, 5:1, 109-127, DOI: 10.1080/17512549.2011.582350
- xliii. Karresand, H. (2014). *Appliances, activities and actors: Low energy housing - resources and restrictions for energy orders* (PhD dissertation). Linköping University Electronic Press, Linköping. <https://doi.org/10.3384/diss.diva-110761>.
- xliv. Kipping, Anna and Trømborg, Erik (2017) – “Modelling Aggregate Hourly Energy Consumption in a Regional Building Stock” – Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resource Management, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Norway
- xlv. Knowlton B. (1999) - *Silicon Valley: Living the Managed Life*. International Herald Tribune, Paris.
- xlvi. Korsnes M., Berker T., Woods R. (2016) Compliance and deviation. How occupants interact with a high performance zero emission building.
- xlvii. Lavelle, M. J. and Fahy, F. (2012) *Consensus Lifestyle Survey—Report on public attitudes and behaviours towards sustainable consumption and sustainable lifestyles in Ireland: (1) Methodology and profiling*, National University of Ireland, Galway.
- xlviii. Locke, Edwin A. and Gary P. Latham, “Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey.,” *American Psychologist*, September 2002, 57 (9), 705–717.M.
- xliv. Loga et al. (2003): *The influence of building standards and user behavior on heating costs*, IWU, Darmstadt
 - i. Lutzenhiser L. and Shove E. (1999) Contracting knowledge: the organizational limits to interdisciplinary energy efficiency research and development in the US and the UK. *Energy Policy*, 27: 217–27.
 - ii. Lutzenhiser, L. (1993) Social and Behavioural Aspects of Energy use. *Annual Review of Energy and the Environment*, 18(1): 247-289.
 - iii. Lutzenhiser, L. (1994) Sociology, energy and interdisciplinary environmental science. *The American Sociologist*, 25(1): 58-79.
 - iiii. Maciel, A., Ford, B. and Lamberts, R. Main influences on the design philosophy and knowledge basis to bioclimatic integration into architectural design—The example of best practices. In: *Building and Environment*, Volume 42, Issue 10, October 2007, Pages 3762- 3773.

- liv. Mahler, Nusser (2018): Final report on pilot project energy plus efficiency houses no. 38, BBSR
- lv. McKerracher, C. and J. Torriti (2013). "Energy consumption feedback in perspective: integrating Australian data to meta-analyses on in-home displays." *Energy Efficiency* 6(2): 387-405.
- lvi. Mancini, F. (2017) – "Energy Use in Residential Buildings: Characterisation for Identifying Flexible Loads by Means of a Questionnaire Survey" – Department of Planning, Design and Technology of Architecture, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
- lvii. Marchetti, R. (2019) HARP Project – D2.2. Report: Building vs heating stock (space and water) matrix, EU and country level. Project funded under European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme - Grant agreement No 847049
- lviii. Mashhoodi, B., Stead, D. & van Timmeren, A. Local and national determinants of household energy consumption in the Netherlands. *GeoJournal*, Volume 85, 2020, 393–406, doi.org/10.1007/s10708-018-09967-9
- lix. Maver, T. (1971) *Building Services Design: A Systematic Approach*. London: RIBA.
- lx. Mumford, L, 1938, 'Power and Culture', in Merrill, O (ed), *Transactions: Third World Power Conference* (Washington: World Power Conference), vol. 1, pp 167–174
- lxi. Nicol, J.F. and Humphreys, M.A. (2002). *Adaptive Thermal Comfort and Sustainable Thermal Standards for Buildings*. Published in *Energy and Buildings*. DOI: 10.1016/S0378-7788(02)00006-3
- lxii. O'Rourke, D. and Lollo, N. (2015) *Transforming Consumption: From Decoupling, to Behaviour Change, to System Changes for Sustainable Consumption*. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 40(1): 233-259.
- lxiii. Palm, Jenny and Ellegård, Kajsa (2011) - Visualizing energy consumption activities as a tool for developing effective policy. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*. 35. 171 - 179. 10.1111/j.1470-6431.2010.00974.x
- lxiv. PVSITE project (TECNALIA) (2016) – "European climate zones and bioclimatic design requirements" – BEAR & NOBATEK
- lxv. Rau H., Moran P., Manton R., Goggins J. - Changing energy cultures? Household energy use before and after a building energy efficiency retrofit, *Sustainable Cities and Society*, Volume 54, 2020, 101983, ISSN 2210-6707, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2019.101983>
- lxvi. Rinaldi, A., Schweiker, M. and Iannone, F. (2018). On Uses of Energy in Buildings: Extracting influencing Factors of Occupant Behaviour by Means of a Questionnaire Survey. *Energy and Buildings*. 168. 10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.03.045

- lxvii. Robledo-Fava, R. et. al (2019) – “Analysis of the Influence Subjective Human Parameters in the Calculation of Thermal Comfort and Energy Consumption of Buildings” – Energies 2019
- lxviii. Sahakian, M. (2015) Getting emotional: historic and current changes in food consumption practices viewed through the lens of cultural theories. In: Putting sustainability into practice: advances and applications of social practice theories. E. H. Kennedy, M. J. Cohen and N. Krogman. Cheltenham (UK), Camberley (UK), Northampton (USA), Edward Elgar: 134-156.
- lix. Sahakian, M. (2017) Constructing normality through material and social lock-in: the dynamics of energy consumption among Geneva’s more affluent households. Demanding energy: spaces, temporalities and change. A. Hui, R. Day and G. Walker. Palgrave Macmillan
- lxx. Satish, B. (2019) “Beyond energy- efficient built environment – examining the relationship between the users’ cultural values and energy consumption,” in IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 2019.
- lxxi. Schaffrin, A. and Reibling, N. (2015) Household energy and climate mitigation policies: Investigating energy practices in the housing sector. Energy Policy, 77: 1-10.
- lxxii. Schild, Willems (2013): Heat protection, Springer Verlag, 2nd edition, 2013
- lxxiii. Segev, S. (2014) - Reducing energy demand: A review of issues, challenges and approaches - Centre on Innovation and Energy Demand, Science Policy Research Unit, University of Sussex, Brighton, UK
- lxxiv. Segev, S. (2015) - Modelling household conservation behaviour among ethnic consumers: the path from values to behaviours - International Journal of Consumer Studies, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 193-202, 2015.
- lxxv. Shove E. (2003) - Converging conventions of comfort, cleanliness and convenience - Journal of Consumer Policy, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 395-418.
- lxxvi. Shove E. (2003) - Comfort, Cleanliness and Convenience: The Social Organisation of Normality - Oxford: Berg Publishers.
- lxxvii. Shove E. (2005) - Changing human behaviour and lifestyle: a challenge for sustainable consumption - Published in Consumption - Perspectives from ecological economics, I. Ropke and L. Reisch, Eds., Elgar, Cheltenham, pp. 111-132.
- lxxviii. Shove E., Pantzar M. and Watson M. (2012) – “The dynamics of social practice: everyday life and how it changes” – London: SAGE.
- lxxix. Shove E., G. Walker (2014) – “What Is Energy For? Social Practice and Energy Demand” – Insights across DEMAND Centre
- lxxx. Sovacool, B. K. (2014) What are we doing here? Analysing fifteen years of energy scholarship and proposing a social science research agenda, Energy Research & Social Science, 1: 1-29.
- lxxxi. Sørensen, Åse Lekang et al (2019), Electricity analysis for energy management in neighbourhoods: Case study of a large housing cooperative in Norway.

- lxxxii. Sørensen, Åse Lekang et al (2019), Heat analysis for energy management in neighbourhoods: case study of a large housing cooperative in Norway
- lxxxiii. Sørensen, Åse Lekang, Anne Gerd Imenes, Steinar Grynning, Tor Helge Dokka (2017) - Energy measurements at Skarpnes zero energy homes in Southern Norway: Do the loads match up with the on-site energy production?
- lxxxiv. Stasinopoulos, T. N. (1993). A critical review of solar architecture between 1973-93. In: Harmony with Nature, Budapest, ISES
- lxxxv. Stephenson, J., B. Barton, J. Carrington, D. Gnoth, R. Lawson and P. Thorsnes (2010) - Energy cultures: A framework for understanding energy behaviours - Energy Policy. 38. 6120-6129. 10.1016/j.enpol.2010.05.069.
- lxxxvi. Stephenson, J., Barton, B., Carrington, G., Doering, A., Ford, R., Hopkins, D., Lawson, R., McCarthy, A., Rees, D., Scott, M. and Thorsnes, P., (2015) The energy cultures framework: Exploring the role of norms, practices and material culture in shaping energy behaviour in New Zealand. Energy Research & Social Science, 7: 117-123.
- lxxxvii. Strengers, Y., Nicholls, L., Maller, C. (2014) – “Curious energy consumers: humans and nonhumans in assemblages of household practice” – Centre for Urban Research, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Journal of Consumer Culture.
- lxxxviii. Strengers, Y. (2014), RMIT University - Smart Energy in Everyday Life. Are You Designing for Resource Man? Published in Interactions. July 2014 <https://doi.org/10.1145/2621931>
- lxxxix. Strengers, Y. and Nicholls, L. (2017) - Convenience and energy consumption in the smart home of the future: Industry visions from Australia and beyond. Energy Research & Social Science
 - xc. Strengers, Y. et al (2018). Protection, Productivity and Pleasure in the Smart Home: Emerging Expectations and Gendered Insights from Australian Early Adopters. Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. //doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300875
 - xcii. Thomsen, Judith, L. Hauge, Åshild, Denizou, Karine, Sidsel Jerkø, Solvår Wågø, Thomas Berker (2011) User evaluations of energy efficient buildings - The interplay of buildings and users in seven European case studies. ZEB Project report 1 – 2011.
 - xciii. Thomsen, J., Gullbrekken, L., Grynning, S. and Holme J. (2017) Evaluering av boliger med lavt energibehov (EBLE) – samlerapport.
 - xciv. Torriti J. and P. Grunewald (2014). "Demand side response: patterns in Europe and future policy perspectives under capacity mechanisms." Economics of Energy & Environmental Policy 3(1).
 - xcv. Torriti, J (2016) “Understanding the timing of energy demand through time use data: Time of the day dependence of social practices” – School of the Built Environment, University of Reading, United Kingdom. Energy Research & Social Science Journal.

- xcv. Torriti, J. - Reading Theme 4: Flexibility - Insights across DEMAND (2018).
- xcvi. Triandis H.C. (1995) Individualism and Collectivism, Westview Press, Boulder (CO).
- xcvii. Van de Vliert, E. (2007) - Climates Create Cultures. Social and Personality Psychology Compass 1 (2007): 10.1111/j.1751-9004.2007.00003
- xcviii. Van Treeck, Lorz (2018): Final reports on pilot project energy plus efficiency houses in existing buildings, BBSR
- xcix. Vischer J. C., "Towards a user-centred theory of the built environment," Building Research & Information, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 231-240, 2008.
 - c. Watson K. J., J. Evans, A. Karvonen and T. Whitley (2016) - Re-conceiving building design quality: A review of building users in their social context - Indoor and Built Environment, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 509-523.
 - ci. Wallenborn, G. and Wilhite, H. (2014) Rethinking embodied knowledge and household consumption. Energy Research & Social Science, 1: 56-64.
 - cii. Wilhite, H., Shove, E., Lutzenhiser, L. and Kempton, W. (2000) The Legacy of Twenty Years of Energy Demand Management: We know more about individual behaviour but next to nothing about demand, in: Jochem, E., Sathaye, J. and Bouille, D. (Eds.) Society, Behaviour and Climate Change Mitigation, Kluwer, London.
 - ciii. Wilhite, H. and Shove, E. (1998) - Understanding Energy Consumption: Beyond Technology and Economics - Published in ACEEE 1998 Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Buildings.
 - civ. Wilhite, H., Shove, E. and Kempton, W. (2000) - The legacy of twenty years of energy demand management. We know more about individual behavior but next to nothing about demand. Published in Society, Behaviour and Climate Change Mitigation, E. S. J. a. B. D. Jochem, Ed., London, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
 - cv. Wilhite, H. (2016) - "Gender Implications of Energy Use and Energy Access," Energy and Economic Growth.
 - cvi. Wilk, R. R. (2002) Culture and Energy Consumption. In: Energy: Science, Policy and the Pursuit of Sustainability. Bent, R., L. Orr and R. Baker. Washington, Island: 109-130
 - cvii. Wines, J. (2000) Green Architecture. London, Taschen